

D3.2: Land use system vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems
AOGCM	Atmosphere-Ocean General Circulation Model
AT	Austria
BG	Bulgaria
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CH	Switzerland
CMIP5	Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project phase 5
CZ	Czech Republic
DOW	Description of Work
EFAS	European Flood Awareness System
ES	Spain
ESDAC	European Soil Data Centre
EU	European Union
GAP	Good Agricultural Practices
GIS	Geographic Information System
GloFAS	Global Flood Awareness System
GR	Greece
H2020	Horizon 2020
HNV	High Nature Value
HU	Hungary
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IT	Italy
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LAU	Local Administrative Unit
LUS	Land use system
MAP	Multi-Actor Platform
MK	North Macedonia
MRL	Mountain Reference Landscape
MRR	Mountain Reference Region

PDO	Protected Designation of Origin
PT	Portugal
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
RO	Romania
RS	Serbia
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
SAPS	Single Area Payment Scheme
SK	Slovakia
TR	Turkey
UK	United Kingdom – Scotland
VC	Value Chain
WASP	Weighted Anomaly of Standardized Precipitation
WP	Work Package

Reference Regions

- 01 – Austrian Alps. Austria.
- 02 – Stara Planina. Bulgaria
- 03 – Šumava - Cesky Les. Czechia
- 04 – Corsica. France
- 05 – Drôme Valley. France
- 06 – Crete. Greece
- 07 – Transdanubian Mountains. Hungary
- 08 – Central Apennines. Italy
- 09 – Eastern Alps. Italy
- 10 – Northern Apennines. Italy
- 11 – Maleshevski Mountains. North Macedonia
- 12 – Cordilheira Central. Portugal
- 13 – Maciço Noroeste. Portugal
- 14 – Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains. Romania
- 15 – Dinaric Mountains. Serbia
- 16 – Slovak Carpathian Mountains. Slovakia
- 17 – Betic Systems. Spain
- 18 – Sierra Morena. Spain
- 19 – Spanish Pyrenees. Spain
- 20 – Swiss Alps. Switzerland
- 21 – Swiss Jura. Switzerland
- 22 – Beydaglari. Turkey
- 23 – Highlands and Islands. United Kingdom – Scotland

Executive summary

Mountain regions can be considered as socio-ecosystems that provide an important and diverse range of goods and services to society. However, in a scenario of global change, these socio-ecosystems are exposed to different threats that increase their vulnerability. Understanding the extent and magnitude of the vulnerability of European mountain regions to different drivers of change, is of great importance for the design of mitigation and adaptation strategies that enable the sustainability of these ecosystems and their associated value chains. Despite their relevance, limited knowledge exists about the extent and magnitude of mountain areas vulnerability to relevant drivers of change. Most studies have investigated general impacts and vulnerability to climate change in particular mountain ranges. This study represents a step further to understand the vulnerability of European mountain ranges to provide key goods and services at landscape scale. Specifically, this study aims to analyse in a participatory way the vulnerability to key drivers of change of 23 land-use systems (LUS) representing a wide diversity of European mountain regions. The analysis of vulnerability has been carried out with the participation and involvement of stakeholders linked to value chains (VC) of interest in the mountain regions under study. This approach has produced vulnerability matrices and maps which may help to design strategies and policies that enhance the economic, social and environmental sustainability of the VC associated with these mountain systems.

Specifically, this work package (WP3 – Development of visual science-society-policy interface tools) has analysed the vulnerability of the land use systems that provide key resources to the associated VCs (*Deliverable 4.2.: List of Selected Value Chains and Relationship Building* by Blackstock and Flanigan, 2021) from a territorial perspective, working at the so-called Mountain Reference Landscapes (MRL) in each of the [23 reference regions](#) included in the [MOVING](#) project. For an adequate vulnerability analysis and to obtain comparable results, and given the diversity of ecosystems, socio-economic situations and methodologies, a suitable conceptual framework was developed in which the main concepts related to vulnerability analysis at the socio-ecosystem level were defined and agreed upon. The study focused on one key VC in each of the 23 Mountain Reference Regions and limited the spatial scope to a smaller area defined as Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) representative of the VC under analysis and where engagement of local stakeholders and creation of a local stakeholder network can be more feasible. For a proper territorial analysis of the information, the MRLs were related to administrative units of the territory, either at Municipality or Local Administrative Units (LAUs) level, always considering the spatial continuity and representation of the landscape and land use units linked to the VC.

Participatory techniques were used to develop the vulnerability matrices for each MRL. A careful and balanced selection of stakeholders participated in interviews, questionnaires, and workshops, in order to quantify the different components of vulnerability: trends of each driver, sensitivity, impact and adaptive capacity. The participatory process undertaken sought a broad view of the reality of the LUS and the resources linked to the VC. This approach involved the participation of

farmers/producers, extension agents and advisors, managers, and other technical staff with knowledge of the LUS, and researchers, taking advantage of the process of creating the MOVING regional Multi-Actor Platforms (MAP). The participatory approach was enriched with spatial environmental data at European level, to provide a list of susceptibility indicators for the identified drivers of change that were presented to the stakeholders during the workshop to inform the vulnerability analysis.

The first step was to identify the more relevant drivers of change in each MRL, from a proposed list. Based on the information collated during the participatory process, a spatial vulnerability matrix and a vulnerability map were developed per MRL. The objective was to identify the spatial distribution of the vulnerability to the drivers selected in the MRL, so that information on adaptation mechanisms can be more targeted, in a later phase of the project. This Spatial Vulnerability Matrix expresses different levels of vulnerability of the selected LUS to change factors (climate-related or other) in relation to spatial explicit factors. Based on this matrix, specific Vulnerability Maps for the MRLs were constructed selecting the most relevant drivers.

According to the perception of participants in each MRL, the most important drivers of vulnerability in all 23 regions were the climate-related drivers, especially rainfall and temperature. Non-climatic drivers showed great variability in terms of their importance across regions, especially regarding overexploitation, and land use and land cover change. All drivers showed an increase in magnitude over the last 20 years as perceived by stakeholders in the 23 MRLs studied, with climate factors generally showing a greater increase in magnitude than other types of drivers. In particular, "temperature" driver showed the largest increase in magnitude while pollution showed the smallest increase. Some drivers, such as "pests and invasive species", showed a large variability between regions, indicating that the trend is highly dependent on the territorial context. The trend for other drivers was more homogeneous, with "precipitation" showing an overall increase in magnitude, which should be interpreted as global changes in the precipitation regime. The list of drivers with high sensitivity included, in addition to climatic drivers of change, non-climatic drivers of change, among which demographic changes showed the highest sensitivity in all 23 regions. However, although temperature showed high relevance at present, it might show moderate sensitivity in the next 20 years, indicating that, according to stakeholders' perception, it might not affect management practices in the medium term. In contrast, other factors, such as changes in precipitation (mainly reduction), showed high levels of importance both in the current period and in the future. It is also worth to mention that in several regions, stakeholders perceived that some drivers could positively affect the respective land use system. This pattern mainly happened with temperature, land use/land cover change and physical land degradation.

A total of 160 adaptation mechanisms were identified across all MRLs. Most of the proposed mechanisms showed high social and environmental feasibility, while technical and economic feasibility was mostly identified as moderate. While around 50% of these mechanisms were already applied in some of the VCs in the MRLs, around 30% of the mechanisms were considered novel or innovative in each region. The majority felt that non-climate drivers would be most effectively reduced by the adaptation mechanisms identified. Furthermore, very few mechanisms

appear to be able to fully reduce the vulnerability of drivers of change, suggesting that a well-balanced combination of adaptation mechanisms may be the most appropriate approach.

This work has made it possible to identify the diversity of LUSs (agricultural and forestry systems) in the reference regions, as well as to assess and map the susceptibility of the MRLs to climate change and the vulnerability of these land use systems to climate change and other relevant threats in each region, such as depopulation, increase in tourism infrastructure, or others.

The vulnerability matrices developed for the 23 MRLs are the most comprehensive analysis of the vulnerability of land use systems in Europe's mountains to date. This work captures the perceptions of a large number of farmers, managers, extension agents and researchers on the importance of the drivers of change that determine the vulnerability of the systems, indicating that the drivers of change that most affect and will affect in the near future, as well as the resource base for the selected value chains, are specific to each MRL. However, it has been observed that the spatial information provided, as well as the indicators produced, are sometimes difficult to understand and interpret with the actors involved, which highlighted the importance of an adequate knowledge transfer adapted to the variability of the stakeholders. However, the methodology used has proven to provide more comprehensive, substantial, and contextualised knowledge, as well as fostering interaction and increased knowledge exchange between the actors involved.

The information processed and produced in this work provides a solid basis for assessing the challenges faced by the selected value chains in the near future in their respective MRLs, as well as assessing how changes in the value chain can affect, reinforce or minimise the effects of the identified drivers of change. As a follow-up to these results, and with the aim of improving the transfer of the knowledge generated, work is currently underway to develop and provide interactive visual tools - especially maps and indicators - that offer real information on assets, sustainability, and resilience, and that can contribute to the awareness of AKIS (Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems), the VC actors, the civil society and the political actors in mountain areas.

The main document includes the vulnerability matrix of the 23 MRLs and those vulnerability maps that could be calculated. In addition, a more detailed vulnerability analysis report has been included as Appendix for each MRL including information on the context, drivers and its components and the participatory analysis of the driver ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

1. Background

Mountain regions provide a large amount of goods and services whose benefits reach not only communities living within the mountains but also in their area of influence (Egan and Price, 2007; MA, 2005). Despite their relevance, we have limited knowledge about the extent and magnitude of their vulnerability to relevant drivers of change. In Europe, most studies have looked into general impact and vulnerability to climate change in particular mountain ranges (e.g., Elkin et al., 2013), however we still do not have a deep understanding of the impact and consequences of the wide range of potential drivers of change that might affect the sustainability of European mountains socio-ecosystems. This study represents a step further to understand the vulnerability of European mountain ranges to provide key goods and services at landscape scale. We build on the activities carried out in WP3 to characterise land-use systems (Task 3.1) and susceptibility indicators (Task 3.2) to finally construct relevant vulnerability matrices (T3.3) and maps (T3.4) summarising the relevance and potential impact of a wide range of drivers of change with potential affection to 23 land-use systems specifically linked to relevant value chains across mountain regions in Europe. The information gathered in this study will be extremely relevant for the following WPs (WP4, WP5, WP6 & WP7) focusing on the value chain scale, ultimately providing useful insights for practitioners and policy makers. Use by non-specialists may be made easier with the incorporation of the information created in the user-interface tools currently under development (Task 3.5).

2. Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

1. To downscale relevant information on drivers of change to the scale of the MRL and provide adequate detailed information for stakeholders to grasp the scenarios of change affecting their own MRL.
2. To assess the vulnerability of the land use system providing key resources for the Value Chain analysed in each MRLs, to critical drivers of change in a 20-year scenario.
3. To formulate and analyse proposals that can reduce these effects.

The work developed focus primarily on the impact of drivers of change such as climate and land-use change.

3. Conceptual framework

Different concepts, as described next, conform the conceptual framework (Moving Conceptual Analytical Framework) supporting this vulnerability analysis.

Vulnerability refers to the propensity of exposed elements such as human beings, their livelihoods, and assets to suffer adverse effects when impacted by hazard events (Cardona et al., 2012), and it is defined as “the state of susceptibility to harm from exposure to stresses associated

with environmental and social change and from the absence of capacity to adapt” (Adger, 2006). Building upon this definition, vulnerability can be conceptualised in terms of three main components: susceptibility (including exposure to a hazard), sensitivity to it, and adaptive capacity to the shock or the stress generated by the hazard (Adger, 2006; Eakin & Luers, 2006).

Factors affecting vulnerability are called **drivers of change**. Drivers of change “are natural or human-induced factors that directly or indirectly cause changes in the system. A direct driver of change unequivocally influences ecosystem processes and/or sociocultural and economic characteristics and can be identified and measured; an indirect driver of change operates by altering the level or rate of change of other, more direct drivers” (MA, 2005) (Wester et al., 2019). Our analysis system is the Mountain Reference Landscapes (MRL) in which Value Chains (VCs) are analysed in other WPs. See Table 1 with the list of proposed drivers of change.

Table 1: Drivers of change

Climate change - precipitation	Changes in precipitation regime (rain or snow) with potential impact in the hydrological system (rivers and groundwater), soil and vegetation. In most cases, we expect a reduction of precipitation and therefore an increase in drought in the system
Climate change - temperature	Increase in mean temperature seasonal or annual. Here we include changes in average, maximum and minimum temperatures.
Climate change - extreme events	Changes in intensity, frequency, or timing for the following components: flooding, heat waves, storms (wind), hail and frost periods.
Climate change – wildfire	Intensity, frequency, or timing of wildfires (forest and soil)
Land-use and land-cover change	Complete changes in land-cover such as conversion from forest to agriculture linked to climate change or other driving forces (policies, market, etc) Changes in vegetation cover such as reduction of tree cover or shrub encroachment or change in land cover mosaic (composition and structure).
Soil physical degradation	Soil physical degradation through loss of organic matter of the soil, due to erosion, poor tillage, or excessive compaction
Over-exploitation of resources	Water extraction (surface or groundwater) Overgrazing – Livestock and wildlife density
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Changes in intensity and frequency of pest and diseases, either native or invasive
Pollution	Contamination of soil, water (surface and groundwater), or the air by the discharge of harmful substances.
Demographic changes	Demographic changes such as population decline or immigration in the MRL might produce changes in management practices and land-use abandonment. This driver could be a cause of land-use and land-cover change

Susceptibility refers to the probability of each land use system of being affected by a disturbance. It depends on the characteristics of the disturbance regime: magnitude, frequency, duration, and real extent, and also of the characteristic of the constituting elements in the land use system.

Sensitivity refers to the actual or potential degree to which a system is modified or affected by perturbations (Adger, 2006). Each land-use system can get affected by the perturbation to a different extent irrespectively of the susceptibility. It can be obtained from the experience and perception of the stakeholders and from previously carried out scientific studies, if any, generating a co-production of knowledge.

Impact is calculated by the combination of susceptibility and sensitivity. For example, an area can have a very high exposure/susceptibility to increased temperature, but if the sensitivity of the crop under analysis is low to the range of temperatures projected, the impact will be low.

Adaptive capacity is the ability of a system to evolve in order to accommodate environmental hazards or socio-economic and policy changes, and to expand the range of variability with which it can cope (Adger, 2006). Adaptive Capacity Mechanisms are human-mediated actions aimed at improving adaptive capacity in the face of drivers, by adapting to or mitigating their negative effects on the reference variable. These actions can be management practices, norms, recommendations, strategies, plans, programmes, policy, etc.

Combining the previous concepts, we have the final system's vulnerability (Figure 1). For example, taken from Schröter et al. (2005), agricultural vulnerability to climate change is described in terms of not only susceptibility to elevated temperatures, but also crop yield sensitivity to the elevated temperatures and the ability of farmers to adapt to the effects of that sensitivity (e.g., by planting more heat-resistant cultivars or by ceasing to plant their current crop altogether).

Land use system refers to the agriculture, forestry or agro-silvo-pastoral land use system **that provides the key resources to the Value Chain (VC) analysed in each case study**. Different possibilities exist, there may be a direct link between one land use system and one value chain, more than one land use system providing resources to one single value chain and more than one value chain per land use system. For clarification, see examples in Table 2. We characterised spatially the land-use systems with a pan-European **classification**, which helps to simplify the multiple land use system in 10 categories (see section 5.2.3).

The reference variable is the variable with the highest influence in the sustainability of the key resource in the land-use system, that is essential to support the VC (see examples in Table 2).

The vulnerability analysis of the land use system is based on this variable, identifying how the drivers of change affect the quality or quantity of the resource. For most cases, the reference variable is productivity or available quantity, or a combination of both. In some less conventional cases, where the natural resource associated with the value chain is not a productive element (e.g., landscape) other reference variables have been chosen in line with the value chain (see Table 2).

Figure 1: Link between the land use system, value chain and the reference variable

Table 2: Examples of value chain and land-use system characterisation.

Value chain	Land-use system	Key resource	Reference variable
Sheep meat	Extensive open rangeland	Pasture	Pasture productivity/quality
Iberian ham	Agro-silvo-pastoral system	Acorn	Acorn production
Tourism	Mosaic of land-use types	Landscape	Landscape composition

The drivers provided in the list (Table 1) are general factors that might affect the system. The way in which the drivers of change affect the reference variable are the **components** of the driver, which may vary depending on the system. These components have guided the selection of relevant indicators of susceptibility, and more refined adaptation mechanism proposals.

The narrative of the future scenario "management as usual"

The vulnerability analysis considered the period 2020-2040, as it is the scale most relevant to capture the perception and suggestions of stakeholders about adaptive mechanisms at local scale

(Nissan et al., 2019). The vulnerability of the land-use system to the drivers of change was analysed assuming that management practices, policy and legislation remain unchanged for the target future period (potential changes will be analysed in the foresight analysis conducted in WP6). We then used the trends of these drivers perceived by stakeholders in the last two decades, as plausible scenario for the future target period. Furthermore, for climate drivers, we established a range of possible values using two IPCC emission scenarios considering stabilisation (RCP 4.5) and generalized increase (RCP 8.5) which were used as reference during the participatory activities (see section 4.1.2 for details).

Mountain Reference Region vs Mountain Reference Landscape: Due to the complexity to collect primary data on large mountain areas, it has been decided to delimit the analysis to smaller areas representative of the VC and land-use system associated, to enhance the local participation and simplify the data collection, and also to make sure the participatory vulnerability analysis will be comprehensive. Two different terminologies have been adopted:

- “Mountain Reference regions” (MRR) refers to large mountain areas, as defined in MOVING Proposal.
- “Mountain Reference landscapes” (MRL) refers to smaller, local areas, representative of the VC under analysis and where engagement of local stakeholders and creation of a local stakeholder network can be more feasible to undertake participatory activities. It refers to one or more administrative units, such as Local Administrative Units (LAUs), where one or more land use systems and natural assets that are key for the selected VCs are located.

4. Methods

This section introduces the methods to complete two interrelated outcomes of WP3 to characterise the vulnerability of the 23 mountain regions to drivers of change: participatory vulnerability matrix (T3.3) and spatial vulnerability matrix and map (T3.4)

4.1. Participatory Vulnerability matrix (T3.3)

MOVING has developed a comprehensive methodology to assess the vulnerability to critical drivers of change of the land-use system identified in each MRL (Figure 2). The ultimate result of this methodology is a vulnerability matrix per study case characterising the susceptibility, the impact, and the final vulnerability (as defined in the Conceptual Framework). These elements conform a matrix and have been quantified based on a range of participatory techniques (i.e., interviews, questionnaires, and workshops) combined with expert assessment (see Figure 2 for details).

Figure 2: Workflow summary

4.1.1. Selection of Mountain reference landscape, land-use system and Identification of reference variable

The vulnerability analysis is focused on one key value chain per region. Based on this selection an expert assessment was carried to identify the land use system or the mosaic of land use systems which provide the key natural resources for the Value Chain(s) to be analysed and the reference variable that characterises this resource (see section 4).

We also delimited spatially the analysis to a specific MRL within the bigger mountain region. The selected MRLs were intended to be representative of the land use systems associated with the VCs across the MRR, as providers of the endogenous resources used in the VCs. These MRL correspond to areas based on administrative units (the level of Municipality or LAU level 1, or lower) within the boundaries of the respective mountain reference region (MRR). The selected LAUs are spatially continuous and the MRLs should allow for sufficient variability of stakeholders associated to the land use systems and related VCs. At the same time, it has been taken into account that stakeholders can attend the workshops because of the distance issue.

A land-use system map per region, based on pan-European or global classifications (van Asselen and Verburg, 2012; Malek and Verburg, 2017; Levers *et al.*, 2018; Rega *et al.*, 2020), was also developed and then validated by partners at the MRL level (Tasks 3.1 and 3.2). The materials and methods as well as the results in terms of Land cover and Land use characterisation of the MRR, are described in D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions (Pinto-Correia *et al.*, 2022). In that Deliverable a complete data and map characterisation of each MRR is included.

4.1.2. Susceptibility Maps and indicators

A closed set of susceptibility indicators based on existing spatial datasets were selected and developed in Task 3.2 for the list of drivers of change mentioned above (Table 3). The list includes Climate and bio-climate projections, soil loss (present and future), rainfall erosivity (present and future), land abandonment (future), and land cover, among others. These data are available at European scale ranging between 100 m and 1 km grid cells.

We used data from ClimateEU¹ (Marchi *et al.*, 2020) representing historical and projected climate data for Europe. The dataset comprises future projections based on 15 Atmosphere-Ocean General Circulation Model (AOGCM)² of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project phase 5 (CMIP5) for future projections (*5th IPCC Assessment Report – 2013*) and considering the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 4.5 and 8.5. According to Knutti *et al.* (2013) these 15 AOGCM are representative of all major AOGCM's clusters.

¹ Datasets available at <https://sites.ualberta.ca/~ahamann/data/climateeu.html>

² The ensemble projections are averages across the 15 AOGCM: CanESM2, ACCESS1.0, IPSL-CM5A-MR, MIROC5, MPI-ESM-LR, CCSM4, HadGEM2-ES, CNRM-CM5, CSIRO Mk 3.6, GFDL-CM3, INM-CM4, MRI-CGCM3, MIROC-ESM, CESM1-CAM5, GISS-E2R

Table 3 : Bioclimatic indicators available at ClimateEU

Abreviation	(Bio-) climate indicators	
MAT	Average over monthly mean temperatures	°C
Tave_at	Mean seasonal temperature (autumn)	°C
Tave_sm	Mean seasonal temperature (summer)	°C
Tave_sp	Mean seasonal temperature (spring)	°C
Tave_wt	Mean seasonal temperature (winter)	°C
Tmax_at	Maximum mean seasonal temperature (autumn)	°C
Tmax_sm	Maximum mean seasonal temperature (summer)	°C
Tmax_sp	Maximum mean seasonal temperature (spring)	°C
Tmax_wt	Maximum mean seasonal temperature (winter)	°C
Tmin_at	Minimum mean seasonal temperature (autumn)	°C
Tmin_sm	Minimum mean seasonal temperature (summer)	°C
Tmin_sp	Minimum mean seasonal temperature (spring)	°C
Tmin_wt	Minimum mean seasonal temperature (winter)	°C
MWMT	Mean warmest month temperatures	°C
MCMT	Mean coldest month temperatures	°C
TD	Temperature difference between MWMT and MCMT	°C
DDabove18	Degree-days with T above 18°C	
DDabove5	Degree-days with T above 5°C	
DDbelow0	Degree-days with T below 0°C	
DDbelow18	Degree-days with T below 18°C	
EMT	Extreme minimum temperature	°C
MAP	Mean annual precipitation (sum of monthly precipitation)	mm
MSP	Summer precipitation (sum of monthly precipitation from May through September)	mm
PPT_at	Seasonal total precipitation (autumn)	mm
PPT_sm	Seasonal total precipitation (summer)	mm
PPT_sp	Seasonal total precipitation (spring)	mm
PPT_wt	Seasonal total precipitation (winter)	mm
CMD	Climatic moisture deficit	
Eref	Reference atmospheric evaporative demand	
SHM	Ratio summer heat/moisture index $MWMT/(MSP \times 1000)$	
AMH	Ratio annual heat/moisture index $(MAT + 10)/(MAP \times 1000)$	
PAS	Precipitation as snowfall	
FFP	Frost-free period (number of consecutive frost-free days)	
NFFD	Number of frost-free days	
bFFP	Date of the beginning of the annual frost-free period	
eFFP	Date of the end of the annual frost-free period	

Source: Marchi et al., 2020

There are some metrics that result from combinations between different variables and that allow indicating specific processes or contexts. For example, TD represents the degree of continentality, and SHM, AMH and CMD are measures of the aridity. While SHM allows to distinguish between hot and dry years (high SHM values) and cool and wet years (low SHM values), AMH is indicative of the evapotranspirative demand (Sáenz-Romero et al., 2017) and

CMD relates to water deficit and irrigation demand (Stephenson, 1998; Narasimhan & Srinivasan, 2005; Bannayan et al., 2010; McDonald & Girvetz, 2013).

Due to the low spatial variability of these indicators, both at the MRR and the MRL scales, we produced summary tables with 5 descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, range, mean and standard deviation) for each of the available bioclimatic variables (36 indicators; Table 3) considering the above-mentioned RCP scenarios for 2050 and the normal period 1961-2020 based on the CRU-TS 4.05 dataset (Harris et al., 2020). The normalized differences, the percentual change and the absolute differences between the normal period and the RCP scenarios were determined at both scales, and the values at the MRL level were contextualized in relation to the MRR through standard scores.

Spatially explicit assessments of natural hazards were also considered in this stage of the exploratory data analysis to provide enough elements to the regional teams to support decision for the following analyses. Complementarily to the climate data, the Global Drought Hazard Frequency and Distribution v1 (1980-2000; 2.5 minute grid; Dilley et al., 2005) published by the World Bank was explored to identify regions that are already showing risks associated with drought. This dataset is based on the Weighted Anomaly of Standardized Precipitation (WASP), which assesses the precipitation deficit or surplus over a three-month temporal window weighted by the magnitude of the seasonal cyclic variation in rainfall. Drought events are identified when the magnitude of a monthly precipitation deficit is less than or equal to 50 percent of its long-term median value for three or more consecutive months. Additionally, we extracted the “Water Crowding Index” (WCI; Falkenmark, 1986, 2013; Rijsberman, 2006), a measure of the annual water resources (potentially available) per capita in a watershed, for 7 return periods (between 2 and 500 years).

The datasets produced by JRC-ESDAC concerning the soil loss by water erosion, both presently and by 2050 (Panagos et al., 2015b, 2021), were also considered in this exploratory data analysis, due to the high relevance that soil conservation assume in the present European context and which is clearly shown in the report EU Mission Board for Soil and Food Health (Veerman et al., 2020) and by the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” objectives leading to the transition towards healthy soils. Soil loss was computed, in these datasets, using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) formula (Renard et al., 1994, 1997):

$$E=R.K.C.LS.P,$$

where E : annual average soil loss ($t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$), R : rainfall erosivity factor ($MJ\ mm\ ha^{-1}\ h^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$), K : soil erodibility factor ($t\ ha\ h\ ha^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$), C : cover-management factor (dimensionless), LS : slope length and slope steepness factor (dimensionless), and P : support practices factor (dimensionless).

We also compared the spatial distribution of the R-factor (present estimations and by 2050; Panagos et al., 2015a, 2016; 2017; Ballabio et al. 2017; Bezak et al., 2020), which is a multi-annual average index that measures rainfall's kinetic energy and intensity to describe the effect of rainfall on soil erosion (Figure 3).

Figure 3 : Comparison of rainfall erosivity in Sierra Morena between present values and projections for 2050

Source: JRC-ESDAC

Still considering issues related to soil conservation, we also analysed 3 layers produced by the JRC-ESDAC regarding soil susceptibility to wind erosion: wind-erodible fraction of soil (%), soil loss potential due to wind erosion (Mg/ha.year), and land susceptibility to wind erosion (Borrelli et al., 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017).

The Flood Hazard Maps for 5 return periods (between 10 and 200 years) based on streamflow data from the European and Global Flood Awareness System (EFAS and GloFAS) and computed using two-dimensional hydrodynamic models were assessed to integrate risks related to runoff and water accumulation processes (Alfieri et al., 2014; Dottori et al., 2016a, b).

Considering the most recent episodes of wildfires in Europe that caused a high number of fatalities and losses in infrastructures and economic activities (e.g., Molina-Terrén et al., 2019; Ribeiro et al., 2022), the related factors that potentiated extreme fire behavior (e.g., Castellnou et al., 2018; Lagouvardos et al., 2019; Pinto et al., 2022), the changes in fire regimes already identified in several regions of Europe (e.g., Fernandes et al., 2014; Viedma et al., 2015), and the evolutionary trends of the meteorological fire hazard (Dupuy et al., 2020) and data from the Global Fire Atlas (Giglio et al., 2018; Andela et al., 2019) were considered.

Spatially explicit indicators that resulted from the combination of multiple disturbance factors, such as the combined forest management pressure by Kleeschulte et al. (2014) or the European map of forest disturbances by Senf & Seidl (2021), as well as projections of change in land use intensity

such as the risk of agricultural abandonment in 2030 by Perpiña-Castillo (2018, 2020, 2021) or in land systems in 2050 by Malek et al. (2018) and Malek & Verburg (2017), were also provided. Additionally, the map of crop types produced by d'Andrimont et al. (2021) was used to produce maps for the mountain regions to contextualise the regional estimations of productivity for the main crop types cultivated in Europe, based on the Agri4Cast Resources Portal (JRC). These estimates considered:

- Potential yield storage (the potential yield of the storage organs) and water limited yield storage (the potential yield of the water-limited storage organs);
- Projections for 2030 and 2050;
- Two RCP scenarios: RCP 4.5 (stabilisation) and 8.5 (generalized increase);
- Three different models: Hadley global circulation model, IPSL global circulation model, MIROC global circulation model;
- No CO₂ fertilisation.

To guarantee homogeneity and feasibility in the pan-European study, the list of susceptibility indicators provided was fixed. Within each region, each partner chose the most relevant to their vulnerability model, based on information from interviews and questionnaires (Figure 2).

4.1.3. Process of engagement for participatory activities

Due to the exceptional health pandemic situation in which these tasks started, there was a great diversity across regions in relation to engagement activities. Some regions had already carried out fieldwork to get to know the potential stakeholders involved in the project, others had already held a Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) meeting, and others had not yet been able to start.

To guarantee maximum participation and deliver project outcomes, different entry strategies have been used, depending on the situation described above:

- Contact through main or institutional actors in the territory. They generally facilitate first contact with stakeholder, especially if they have a lot of power or recognition, but it is better when they are not intermediaries and researchers contact stakeholders directly.
- Interesting people identified by desk-study (awards, competitions, news, social networks), and contacted directly.
- Contacts provided by third parties (prior permission). Colleagues from other areas, departments or projects, entities, etc.
- Prior knowledge of people (e.g., previous projects). Sometimes some partners had already worked in the case study areas and had some previous contacts.

Usually these strategies were combined, and finally complemented with a snowball sampling strategy, in order to reach actors that are more difficult to reach at first. Most cases have used mixed strategies that permit to engage up to 513 stakeholders across all MRL.

4.1.4. Interviews

The overall objective was to interview in each case study a set of stakeholders who could together give a broad view of the reality regarding the land use system (LUS) and the resource linked to the value chain, in an experiential, technical, managerial, or scientific way. The set of interviews sought to have a balance between the following profiles, searching for a relevant representation of background and experience within each group:

- Farmers/producers: either owner, tenant or manager with a direct decision capacity on the land management.
- Extension officers and advisors: technicians providing information/advice/innovation to farmer/producers but that do not own or manage land.
- Managers and other technical staff with knowledge about the LUS, not directly linked to agriculture extension but connected to the management of resources such as protected area managers, organisation executives and policy actors at different scales.
- Researchers.

Several strategies were used to engage these stakeholders. On the one hand, we took advantage of the process of creating the MAP per MRL or MRR (depending on the mountain region) to conduct informal interviews and select people who could be interesting for this task and could be motivated to participate. Using a snowball approach, we then identified further contacts referred by the initial list. During interviews and participatory work, all partners guarantee the fulfilment of the project Ethics guidelines and granted authorisation from their organisation ethics committee if needed.

Objectives

The specific objectives of the interviews were:

- Validate the reference variable. Identify the key resources of the land use system essential to support the value chain, as well as their attributes (productivity, quality, etc.).
- Inquire about the drivers of change to identify those having the greatest impact on the land use system and the reference variable. We started by asking for the initial list (Table 1), but then asked if there were any others that should be included. For each driver, the expected outcome was:
 - To identify the relevant components affecting the reference variable.
 - To understand the relationships between the drivers.
 - To identify the possible underlying causes of the driver (only for the endogenous driver).

At the end of this block of the interview, the initial mapping of the drivers and their relationships was shared and validated with the interviewees.

- Identify the adaptive capacity mechanisms linked to the drivers of change. The aim was to obtain an initial list of adaptive capacity mechanisms to build on in the workshop.

- Characterise personal profiles of the interviewees: age, level of education, experience in the land use system.
- Identify other stakeholders (snowball sampling method) in order to find representatives of the profiles not interviewed in the first round.

This information was extracted and recorded in an Excel template to facilitate post-processing.

Output:

Each team, after conducting the interviews and analysing the information collected, should have the necessary information to prepare the next steps of the research.

For the questionnaire:

- Choose and identify the final reference variable.
- Make a description of drivers indicating the relevant components to assess.

For the workshop:

- Prepare a draft list of adaptive capacity mechanisms. This required an analysis, selection, and reorganisation of the mechanisms.

4.1.5. Pre-Workshop questionnaire and synthesis

With the information gathered from the interviews, each team constructed a questionnaire that was distributed to all interviewees from the previous activity and any further relevant stakeholders identified in the meantime and expected to participate in the workshops.

Objectives

The aim of the questionnaire was to obtain the following information about the drivers of change:

- Feedback on the description and components of the drivers for the indicators. Getting feedback on whether they consider that the driver description represents well the key components for the MRL.
- Perception of past trend and future projection: quantitative individual assessment of the past trend (Table 4), and future projection (yes/no) for each of the drivers of change considering the components identified. Here, we aimed to identify the trend of the drivers in the MRL, regardless of whether it affects the reference variable or not.
- A ranking of the importance of drivers based on how they currently affect the reference variable based on quantitative individual assessment (Table 5). This score will serve on one hand, to discard drivers that have no relevance in the land use system and, on the other hand, to weight the importance of drivers in the vulnerability model.
- Each MRR team designed the questionnaire in google forms or other similar tool, based on the templates provided by the UCO team.

Table 4 : Categories for trend responses

Response	Code	Numeric score
It has declined sharply in the last 20 years	HD	-1
It has declined slightly in the last 20 years	MD	-0.5
Constant in the last 20 years	CO	0
It has increased slightly in the last 20 years	MI	0.5
It has increased sharply in the last 20 years	HI	1

Table 5: Ranking responses

Response	Code	Numeric score
Does not affect	VL	0
Not relevant	VL	1
Slightly relevant	L	2
Moderate relevant	M	3
Very important	H	4
Extremely important	VH	5

All the information collected was integrated and synthesised by each team to produce the following outputs for the workshops:

- A final results' matrix, with the components, trends and ranking values (in an excel template by each of the teams).
- A summary factsheet for each driver, providing its description, its components and the relevant underlying causes and relationships.
- The ranking of the drivers, including the relevant ones and excluding those considered not relevant to the research (low importance on the reference variable). The selected list of drivers to be presented in the next workshop in order of importance.
- Stakeholders' perception of the past trends and future projections.
- Selection of the relevant susceptibility maps and indicators to present at the workshop.

4.1.6. Vulnerability Workshop

A workshop was organised in each MRL with a well-balanced selection of participants derived of the previous activities. Due to COVID-19 situation, some workshops were held online, and others were physical meetings. The results from the previous activities were shown to the participants by the Moving regional team, and a discussion followed, with the Objectives listed below.

Objectives

- Identify the sensitivity for each driver of change (Table 1 **Error! Reference source not found.**).
- Develop and prioritise the adaptive capacity mechanisms.

Table 6 Sensitivity categories

Response	Code	Numeric score
Totally affects positively the reference variable. Improves overall to a large extent creating a large increase in profitability.	H+	-1
Severely affected positively the reference variable. Improves overall to a medium extent creating a moderate increase in profitability.	M+	-0.6
Partially affects positively the reference variable. Improve the reference variable occasionally in some years or generally but to a small extent.	L+	-0.3
Does not affect the reference variable: The farm is maintained as usual.	No	0
Partially affects negatively the reference variable: require minor changes in management practices.	L-	0.3
Severely affected negatively the reference variable: require large changes in management practices. Affecting profitability.	M-	0.6
Totally affects negatively the reference variable: will require a change in the land use system (e.g., species). The exploitation will not be profitable.	H-	1

The information collected was used to:

- Enter the sensitivity data per driver into the final spreadsheet matrix of results.
- Evaluate the workshop using the spreadsheet of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) tools.
- Develop a prioritised list of mechanisms to be used in the next step, an expert assessment of their feasibility and potential to reduce the impact of the drivers.

Numeric score	Economic viability	Technical viability	Environmental Benefit	Social acceptability	Current implementation	Who has to participate?
3	High (own resources)	High (own resources)	High (potential for biodiversity and / or ecosystem services)	High (broader positive impact to society and social support)	None	Producer
						Cooperative
						Professional organisations
2	Medium (need local support or small credit)	Medium (need local technical support)	Medium (does not affect biodiversity or services)	Medium (no positive impact or low social opposition)	Few farms	Researchers
						Regional government
					Several farms	Local government
1	Low (need for subsidies or great credit)	Low (need for external consulting)	Low (negatively impact biodiversity and / or services)	Low (medium to strong opposition by society)	Most farms	Central government
						EU

Table 7 Criteria for feasibility analysis of adaptation capacity mechanisms

4.1.7. Feasibility and potential impact reduction of adaptive capacity mechanisms

This analysis was the last step in building the vulnerability matrix. It was carried out by each of the regional teams as an informed expert assessment. In some cases, the teams gathered support of other stakeholders in specific workshops or interviews.

Objectives

- To obtain for each adaptive capacity mechanism, a feasibility score and reduction potential of the impact per driver on the reference variable by 2040.

The feasibility was assessed according to several criteria (economic, technical, environmental, and social) and considering two implementation levels: how widespread is currently the mechanism and which stakeholder groups are required for its implementation (Table 7). The assessment of impact reduction was done per driver using four distinct levels (Does not affect, Slight reduction, Moderate reduction, Complete reduction).

4.1.8. Vulnerability matrix calculation per region

Final vulnerability values per region were estimated based on the aggregation of all components of vulnerability (Figure 2: Workflow summaryFigure 2) for those drivers with the required information according to the following steps:

1. Estimate mean values of ranking, trend, and sensitivity values of all responses per driver at the component level in each region. The scoring of driver at component level allowed to separate key factors of the driver that could affect differently the system.
2. Impact per driver at the component level in each region estimated as the combination of the mean trend and mean sensitivity based on the rules established in (Table 8). In some special cases we had trend scores estimated for more than one component per driver but just one sensitivity value per driver. For these cases, overall impact was calculated using the maximum trend score. As impact is the combination of trend and sensitivity, the final impact score ranges from +1 (maximum value of negative impact) to -1 (maximum value of positive impact in the reference variable), and 0 indicates no relevant impact.
3. During the assessments (section 5.1.7), the experts were asked to score the potential reduction capacity of each adaptive mechanism to the negative impacts caused by the driver of change. Thus, to calculate vulnerability per driver at component level, its negative impact was reduced by the maximum reduction capacity identified per driver across all adaptive mechanisms listed per region. In practice, the impact per driver was multiplied by a correction coefficient where higher reduction capacity was assigned to a coefficient closer to zero: High reduction: 0; Moderate reduction: 0.6; Low reduction: 0.3; No reduction: 1. This reduction mechanism per driver was applied according to three different scenarios considering a different set of adaptive mechanisms based on their feasibility scores (see Table 7 for feasibility criteria):
 - a. All: considering all mechanisms.
 - b. Moderate feasibility: considering only mechanisms with average feasibility higher than 2 scores across all criteria
 - c. High feasibility: considering only mechanisms with average feasibility higher than 2.5 scores across all criteria.
4. Overall impact and vulnerability per region were estimated as the weighted mean of all drivers considering the importance given by the ranking component.

Table 8: Impact calculation based on the cases recorded

Trend	Sensitivity	Impact calculation	Rationality
Increase (positive score)	Negative effect (positive score)	Arithmetic mean	Both trend and sensitivity increase vulnerability
Increase (positive score)	Positive effect (negative score)	Arithmetic mean. Trend transformed as negative score	Both trend and sensitivity reduce vulnerability
Decrease (negative score)	Negative effect (positive score)	Arithmetic mean	Trend reduces vulnerability while sensitivity increases vulnerability. Both components counteract.

4.1.9. Comparison across regions

Each driver component per region was linked to a generic driver classification (Table 1) to compare the ranking, trends, and sensitivity across regions. When two or more components per region were linked to the same generic driver, the maximum value of each component was retained. This procedure allowed to retain the component contributing more to vulnerability per category and region. Overall impact and vulnerability levels across regions were also compared.

4.2. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map (T3.4)

The following methodology aimed to produce a *Spatial* Vulnerability Matrix for the Land Use Systems (LUS) supporting the focal Value Chain (VC) in each MRL, relying on the respective regional MOVING teams informed assessment of the findings collected in T3.3. The objective was to identify the spatial distribution of the vulnerability to the drivers selected in the MRL, so that information on adaptation mechanisms can be more targeted, in a later phase of the project.

In fact, the work developed in T3.3 was the stepping-stone for the production of the Spatial Vulnerability Matrices. In other words, each regional MOVING team built the information for the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix from the data collected and its own informed assessment, based on knowledge gathered in the different moments of interaction with local stakeholders and the narratives they expressed during the previous task.

Each Spatial Vulnerability Matrix expresses different levels of vulnerability of the selected land use system to drivers of change (related to climate or others) in relation to spatial explicit factors. Some of these Spatial Vulnerability Matrices allowed us to build Vulnerability Maps within the respective MRL.

4.2.1. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Each regional MOVING team responsible for a MRL build a Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for the Land Use System in a four-step process, as detailed below, and submitted it through the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix inputs template (Appendix II). For the purpose of illustration, each step is accompanied by the example of the Cordilheira Central MRL located in Serra da Estrela (Portugal), where the focal value chain selected was the PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) Serra da Estrela Cheese.

Step 1

Identification of the land use system in which the VC selected in each MRL depends on (see Point 4. Above in this Document for the clarification of the concepts and Deliverable 4.2: List of selected value chains and relationship building, Blackstock and Flanigan, 2021).

Cordilheira Central MRL example

PDO Serra da Estrela Cheese value chain, relies on the milk produced by two autochthonous sheep breeds that feed on a land use system of permanent pastures at highlands and lowlands.

Step 2

Identification of key drivers to which the land use system is vulnerable to (Vulnerability Drivers), based on the analysis of the information collected in T3.3. At this point, regional MOVING teams were asked to select the key drivers based on the ranking that resulted from the questionnaire applied to local actors (see Figure 2).

Cordilheira Central MRL example

In Cordilheira Central MRL, local actors' narratives often pointed out that permanent pastures are very vulnerable to land abandonment and wildfires.

On the one hand, due to demographic changes and a sharp decay in the number of producers, there is a decrease in grazing intensity, which results in shrub encroachment of prior pasture areas. Permanent pastures are invaded by *Calluna vulgaris* (heathlands), among others. After being covered by shrub, permanent pastures are hard to recover into pastures again, while the risk of fire increases. On the other hand, due to the high rate of forests in land cover and the increasingly severe summer drought, high severity fires are a constant threat to land use systems, including grazed areas, affected by contagion from areas covered by shrubland and forest, where fires often progress beyond the capacity for technological suppression.

In the case of Cordilheira Central MRL, there is an additional synergistic relationship between the two processes. The increased susceptibility of the landscape to fire increases with land abandonment, because the plant communities that colonise the former pastures are fire-prone and increase the spatial continuity of fuels available to be consumed by fire. Pastures, on the

other hand, were spaces where it was easier to fight fire, as they had a lower fuel load. These pastures were maintained by livestock grazing and pasture management using controlled fires in Winter and Spring (there is now a surplus of “bad” summer fires as a result of the deficit of “good” winter fires related to the collapse of the grazing system).

Step 3

Selection of two Spatially Explicit Factors that are decisive in the variation of the land use system's vulnerability to the drivers identified in Step 2, based on the analysis of the information collected in T3.3.

The teams were asked to select these two factors, based on the knowledge they have from their MRL and on the information collected from stakeholders along all WP3 analysis. The factors selected had to make sense and be particularly relevant within each MRL context and register spatial variation at the MRL scale. The selection of spatial explicit factors for each MRL intended to make the vulnerability mapping more adapted and relevant to each local context. Some examples of spatially explicit factors that could be selected are slope, elevation, distance to a specific land cover class, distance do roads or other infrastructures, distance to urban centres, size of forest patches (or of patches of other land covers) and tree cover density.

Once regional MOVING teams selected the spatially explicit factors, they also defined classes in which each of them could be unfolded.

Cordilheira Central MRL example

In Cordilheira Central MRL (Serra da Estrela), the narratives by local actors highlighted as spatially significant factors for the severity of fire and of land abandonment, both elevation and distance to forest and shrubland.

In fact, highland pastures are the first to be abandoned as lowland pastures are often enough to the sheep producers remaining in the area and are also more accessible. Besides, pastures at higher distances from forests and shrublands are seen as an advantage to avoid the risk of being consumed by wildfire.

The MOVING team responsible for this MRL defined two classes for elevation (≤ 1000 m and > 1000 m) and three classes for distance to forests and shrubland (≤ 250 m, 250 – 750 m and > 750 m). These classes were defined according to the characteristics of the MRL and assessment of the usefulness of the classes used in different existing maps of the region.

Step 4

Construction of a two-input Spatial Vulnerability Matrix where for each combination of classes of the Spatial Explicit Factors (Step 3) a level of vulnerability of the land use system to the vulnerability drivers (Step 2) is assigned, based on regional MOVING teams' own assessment informed by the participatory activities in T3.3. Five levels of vulnerability were considered: from very low vulnerability (1) to very high (5). This is the step where the informed assessment of the regional MOVING team was most relevant. It required processing all the information collected so far but showed to be easily completed, as the work developed so far for other tasks of WP3 lead the teams to a comprehensive knowledge of the MRL drivers and particularities.

Cordilheira Central MRL example

For Cordilheira Central MRL permanent pastures, the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix takes into account the drivers to which pasture area is vulnerable (Land abandonment and Wildfire) – two examples are given below.

Vulnerability Matrix		Distance to Forests and Shrublands		
		< 250m	250 - 750 m	≥ 750 m
Elevation	< 1000m	4	3	1
	≥ 1000 m	5	4	2

At higher elevations and closer to forests and shrublands vulnerability of permanent pastures to wildfire and land abandonment is higher.

At lower elevations and higher distances from forests and shrublands vulnerability of permanent pastures to wildfire and land abandonment is lower.

4.2.2. Vulnerability Map

Taking into account the spatial vulnerability matrices provided by the partners responsible for each MRL, vulnerability maps were built for selected cases, depending on the characteristics of the spatial vulnerability matrix produced and the available spatial datasets. As already foreseen in the Grant Agreement, this map was not produced for the entire set of MRL, as in some cases the relation between the value chain and the spatially explicit variability in the MRL is not straightforward, and therefore such a map would not represent an added value to the analysis.

The common approach was the creation of three auxiliary maps – 1 per each spatial explicit factor with the classes defined in each matrix and 1 with the limits of the land use system under analysis

- from which, using map algebra, the vulnerability map was built (see Figure 4 example). More specific methodology on Vulnerability Maps construction and assumptions, per MRL, can be consulted in Appendix II.

Figure 4 : Auxiliary and Vulnerability Maps for Cordilheira Central MRL (top left: Elevation map, top right: Distance to forest and shrubland map, bottom left: Permanent pastures area map, and bottom right: Vulnerability map)

5. Vulnerability Matrices across regions (T3.3)

5.1. Participation per region

Profile, age, and gender of stakeholders

MOVING aims to involve a diverse profile of stakeholders boosting diversity and representativeness as much as possible. For this task, the profiles prioritised were those with greater links and direct knowledge of the land use system: farmers and producers, extension officers and advisors, managers, other technical staff with knowledge about the land-use system and researchers. As we can see in Figure 5, the profile that has participated the most were farmers with the rest of the profiles being balanced among them. In terms of gender, we can see a predominance of men over women. Especially farmers have been men, due to the masculinisation of this type of tasks. In the rest of the profiles, although more balanced, there has also been a higher rate of male participation.

Figure 5. Participation plots according to profiles, gender, and age.

Regarding age, the presence of "young" female researchers (30-45) compared to older male researchers is noteworthy (Figure 5). Something similar happens in the case of farmers, with more women in a younger age group, which gives an idea of a greater incorporation of women into these professions. In the manager and extension officer profiles, the middle-aged group (40-60) stands out.

5.2. Importance, trends, and sensitivity of drivers across Europe

According to the perception of stakeholders, the most important drivers (i.e., higher value in the ranking) of vulnerability across the 23 regions were climatic drivers, particularly precipitation and temperature (Figure 6). The driver “Pest and invasive species” was also a relevant driver across the regions. Non-climatic drivers showed high variability in importance across regions, particularly for over-exploitation and land-use and land-cover change. Finally, wildfire showed the least mean relevance across all regions, although it is important to note that at least one region indicated this driver as extremely high relevant.

All drivers showed an increase in magnitude (i.e., mean score positive) during the last 20 years according to the perception of stakeholders across all 23 regions studied (Figure 6). Particularly, temperature showed the highest increase in magnitude while pollution showed the least increase. Climatic drivers showed in general higher increase in magnitude than other types. Some drivers showed high variability across regions indicating that the trend has high context-dependent effect. This pattern is particularly relevant for the “Pest and invasive species” driver where we have regions across all the gradient of options. The driver precipitation shows an overall increase in magnitude, which reflects the widespread perception that the precipitation regime is largely changing. This change in precipitation regime corresponds to an overall rainfall reduction across most of the regions.

In contrast to previous components of vulnerability, the top list of drivers with high sensitivity included both climatic and non-climatic drivers of change (Figure 7). Among them, demographic changes showed the highest sensitivity across all 23 regions. Interestingly, while temperature showed high relevance currently (high ranking score) it might show moderate sensitivity in the next 20 years, indicating that based on the perception of stakeholders it might not affect management practices in the medium-term. In contrast, other drivers such as precipitation changes (mostly reduction), showed high levels of importance for both current and future time spans. In several regions, stakeholders perceived that some drivers might affect positively the respective land-use system. This pattern occurred mainly with temperature, land-use and land-cover change and soil-physical degradation. Specifically, temperature might increase productivity in some regions with moderate temperature ranges (e.g., Alps) in contrast with already warm areas (e.g., Mediterranean mountains). Land-use and land-cover change might affect positively the reference variable if the driver tends to increase the area dedicated to land-use system (e.g., agroecological practices are widespread). Similar rationality is found for the positive effects of the soil-physical degradation driver suggesting positive feedback between the driver and the land-use system (e.g. organic farming promoting permanent grass cover).

Figure 6 : Boxplots summarizing the scores of Ranking (top) and Trends (bottom) of the vulnerability drivers across all 23 regions. The ranking score considers very low (0) to very high importance (5) while trend score shows high decrease (-1) to high increase (1). Sensitivity scores consider from high positive effect of the driver (-1) to high negative effect (1). For details in the score categories see the Methods section. For each vulnerability component, drivers are sorted by higher mean value from top to bottom.

Figure 7 : Boxplot summarizing the scores of Sensitivity for each driver of change across all 23 regions. Sensitivity scores consider from high positive effect of the driver (-1) to high negative effect (1). For details in the score categories see the Methods section. Drivers are sorted by higher mean value from top to bottom

5.3. Adaptive mechanisms

A total of 160 mechanisms of adaptation were suggested across all regions. Most mechanisms proposed showed high social and environmental feasibility, while technical and economic feasibility was mostly moderate (Figure 8). In general, these mechanisms were already implemented in few farms or communities across the MRL (~50%), although 30% of the mechanisms were novel in each region (Figure 8). Across drivers, non-climatic drivers were more effectively reduced by the adaptive mechanism (assuming full implementation), with the land-use and land-cover change driver as those with highest reduction capacity. In contrast, wildfire showed the least reduction capacity across all regions. The latter finding might be related to the low relevance of wildfires as a key driver of change (Figure 6) which might encourage the development of mechanisms targeting other more important drivers. Finally, very few mechanisms seem able to fully reduce the vulnerability of the drivers (Figure 8) suggesting that a well-balanced combination of mechanisms might be the best suitable approach.

Figure 8 : Summary of adaptive mechanisms across 23 mountain regions. Top left indicates the proportion of mechanisms in each feasibility level (L-Low, M-Medium and H-High) per criteria. Top right shows the proportions of mechanisms in each implementation level. Bottom plot indicates the proportion of mechanisms reducing the vulnerability across drivers of change, where complete indicates full reduction and none, absence of reduction.

Several mechanisms were highlighted as key to reduce the vulnerability of the system across most drivers in each region (Table 9). These mechanisms showed high diversity including integrative practices, dissemination, research and governance. Among all regions, the Betic region in Spain suggested several mechanisms with high reduction capacity. To see full list of mechanisms per region see Appendix I.

Table 9 : Top List of adaptive mechanisms with higher mean capacity of reducing vulnerability across all study cases (mean reduction capacity ≥ 1.8) including its mean feasibility (from 1 to 3) across economic, technical, social and environmental criteria.

MRL	Mechanism	Mean feasibility	Mean reduction
Swiss Alps MRL	Advanced soil practices - Further Sensibilisation on soil preservation and intercropping, goes together with climate mitigation strategies	3.0	2.0
Swiss Jura MRL	Better use of milk potential in function of the time of year.	2.8	2.0
Betic Systems MRL	Dissemination of the benefits associated with the ecosystemic services provided by the ecological mountain olive grove (environmental, economic and cultural).	2.5	2.0
Crete MRL	Research on the effects of climate change leading to predictions regarding its impacts on the different crops in the region	2.0	2.0
Betic Systems MRL	Specific informative actions on this model of agro-system, encouraging the change of model for the benefit of organic production in the mountain olive grove, as well as specific training actions aimed at offering added value to the practices that producers, service companies, cooperatives, etc. must carry out. Contributing to the creation of a professional sector that is trained and adapted to the management needs required by this particular agro-system.	2.3	1.9
Swiss Alps MRL	Water capacity - New water storage solutions for summer	1.5	1.8
Crete MRL	Adequacy of policies and regulations regarding agro-forestry land use systems	1.8	1.8
Crete MRL	Communal collaboration to transfer knowledge regarding carob cultivation and increasing awareness regarding responsive strategies and adaptation	2.3	1.8
Betic Systems MRL	Actions to raise awareness and disseminate good practices linked to organic mountain olive groves, generating added value for them, via price differentials based on ecosystem services and promoting specific quality labels within the framework of the European Union.	2.0	1.8
Betic Systems MRL	Increase in CAP aid for organic mountain olive groves, including specific modernisation plans and the allocation of aid complementary to agri-environmental aid for the most fragile olive groves (biodiversity, slopes, etc.).	3.0	1.8
Speyside MRL	Distillery water management	2.3	1.8

5.4. Vulnerability matrices

The vulnerability analysis yielded a wide range of impact and vulnerability scores across all 23 regions (Table 10). Six regions showed high impact level (>0.5) covering wide geographical area from West to East Mediterranean. Interestingly, few Mediterranean regions seem rather resistant to the drivers of change studied here (e.g., Betic and Crete). In general, regions covering alpine and central European ranges showed moderate to low impact.

Vulnerability scores account for the capacity of adaptive mechanisms to reduce the impact of the drivers. Assuming the implementation of all the adaptive mechanisms suggested per region (scenario A in Table 10), the vulnerability of the systems was greatly reduced (up to 0.5). In fact, after the reduction, the vulnerability across all regions was rather similar (Table 10). The different adaptation scenarios (i.e. applying only the adaptation mechanisms with medium or high feasibility) showed similar results in vulnerability (Table 10). This finding indicates that it is likely that with just the highly feasible mechanisms it is possible to greatly reduce the impact of the drivers of change studied here.

Table 10 : Overall impact and vulnerability per region. Values closer to 1 indicates higher impact and vulnerability. Three different adaptation scenarios are considered to estimate vulnerability: A. with all adaptation mechanisms applied, B. only applying mechanisms with medium feasibility and C. only applying mechanisms with high feasibility. See details of calculations in section 5.1.8

MRL	Impact	Vulnerability considering Scenarios of adaptation		
		Vulnerability all mechanisms (vulnALL)	Vulnerability Medium feasibility mechanisms (vulnMF)	Vulnerability High feasibility mechanisms (vulnHF)
Beydaglari	0.7	0.2	0.2	0.3
Stara Planina	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.2
Cordilheira Central	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.4
Sierra Morena	0.6	0.2	0.3	0.3
Central Apennines	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.3
South Carpatians	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.1
Drôme Valley	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.5
Jura	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2
Pyrenees	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.3
Crete	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1
Maleshevski mountains	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1
Slovak Carpathians	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.3
Austrian Alps	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.3
Transdanubian mountains	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1
Maciço Noroeste	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.2
Northern Apennines	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3
Eastern Alps	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.2
Speyside	0.3	0.1	0.1	*
Corsica	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Betic systems	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Šumava - Český les	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
Dinaric mountains	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
Swiss Alps	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0

*No mechanisms with high feasibility

5.5. Vulnerability Matrix per Mountain Reference Landscape

In this section, the calculated vulnerability matrices are presented for the 23 MRLs based on the scores of trends, ranking, sensitivity, and adaptation mechanisms collected from stakeholders. For each region, we provide two matrices. The first matrix shows the trend; the sensitivity (sensit); the mean reduction capacity of adaptation mechanisms considering: all mechanisms (reductALL), only medium feasible mechanisms (reductMF) and only high feasible mechanisms (reductHF); the impact (combining trend and sensitivity) and the vulnerability considering the three reduction scenarios (vulnALL, vulnMF and vulnHF) for each driver of change. Further explanation about this matrix is provided in Figure 9. The second matrix shows the weighted average of the same scores across all drivers considering the importance given by the ranking scores. Further details are included in the methods section 4.1.8.

Figure 9 : vulnerability matrix explained

01 - Austrian Alps. Austria

Mountain Reference Landscape: Austrian Alps MRL (region of Weiz)

Value Chain name: Lamb from the region of Weiz

Land-use system name: Extensive open range low land meadows and highland pastures

Name of the reference variable: Quality of pasture and linkage to the lamb production.

Figure 10. Summary table of values per driver for the Austrian Alps MRL (Austria)

The increased presence of wolf in the region seems to be of concern (pest & invasive species), that coupled with climatic drivers and soil physical degradation (partly due to climatic drivers), seem to be the drivers with the highest impact (Figure 10). Adaptive capacity is high in a scenario where all the proposed mechanisms are applied and of medium viability but decreases a lot in a scenario where only the most viable ones are applied (Table 11). This finding shows that adaptation to climate change and other difficulties is not an easy task, but it can be tackled even if this requires some effort.

Table 11 : Mean impact and vulnerability of the land use system for the Austria Alps MRL

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.4	0.1	0.1	0.3

02 - Stara Planina. Bulgaria

Mountain Reference Landscape: Stara Planina MRL (Western Balkan Mountains)

Value Chain name: Public Goods from High Nature Value (HNV) farmland

Land-use system name: “Medium intensity / natural forest + Agro-silvo-pastoral system + Extensive open rangeland” – according to van Asselen and Verburg (2012) this might be broadly defined as an example of a “Mosaic (semi-) natural system” consisting of “Grassland and forest”

Name of the reference variable: “Farmland biodiversity” – specifically the “*presence of priority habitats of European significance that are dependent upon the continuation of traditional agriculture*”.

Figure 11 : Summary table of values per driver for Stara Planina MRL (Bulgaria)

Depopulation, land abandonment, and drought are the main factors, with a very high impact factor (0.9 and 0.8 out of 1; Figure 11). Only one of the top three factors is climatic. Already at medium values we see temperature increase, soil erosion and intensive rainfall (erosion to a large extent comes from intense rainfall), the climatic values are more appreciated. The overall impact of the system is quite high (Table 12), considering that it is a medium value, but it seems that there is also a high adaptive capacity of highly feasible mechanisms, with less potential to reduce the impact on the climate drivers.

Table 12. Mean impact and vulnerability of the land use system for the Stara Planina MRL (Bulgaria)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.6	0.2	0.2	0.2

03 – Sumava - Cesky Les. Czechia

Mountain Reference Landscape: Šumava - Český les MRL

Value Chain name: Beef Production

Land-use system name: Extensive open rangeland

Name of the reference variable: Quality pasture for cattle

Figure 12 : Summary table of values per driver for Sumava- Cesky Les MRL (Czechia)

Although participants are aware of the high sensitivity that the reference variable (quality pasture for cattle) may have to some of the drivers such as drought, temperature, land degradation or extreme events, they do not currently see it as a potential problem, so the perceived vulnerability is low (Figure 12). Participants give more importance to how they are affected by regulations related to the National Park, Nature Protected Areas, or regulations of agricultural practices.

Table 13. Impact, adaptive capacity and vulnerability of the system for Sumava- Cesky Les MRL (Czechia)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1

04 - Corsica. France

Mountain Reference Landscape: Corsica MRL (Monte Renoso massif)

Value Chain name: PDO Chestnut flour

Land-use system name: High intensity plant forest (Agroforestry)

Name of the reference variable: Chestnut production.

Figure 13 : Summary table of values per driver for Corsica MRL (France)

The drivers with higher impact perceived by participants were pests, demographic changes, animal stray and drought (Figure 13). Interestingly some drivers showed a high positive influence in the reference variable, which resulted in a rather low overall vulnerability (Table 14)

Table 14. Impact, adaptive capacity, and vulnerability of the system for Corsica MRL

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.3	0	0	0

05 – Drôme Valley. France

Mountain Reference Landscape: Drôme Valley MRL

Value Chain name: Sheep meat locally produced and valorised

Land-use system name: Extensive open pastures

Name of the reference variable: the pastoral resource: grasslands and shrubbery availability on the pasture areas

Figure 14 : Summary table of values per driver for Drôme Valley MRL (France)

The factors that are perceived to be most influential are invasive species (with the wolf issue), climatic drivers (temperature, drought and extreme events) and demographic changes (Figure 14). There is little perceived adaptive capacity to these drivers. In contrast, in other case studies we have found mechanisms that can also influence the reduction of the impact of climate drivers, it may be interesting to see if they could be applicable to the context of the Drôme Valley.

Table 15. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Drôme Valley MRL (France)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.5	0.4	0.4	0.5

06 - Crete. Greece

Mountain Reference Landscape: Crete MRL (Rethymno)

Value Chain name: Central Rethymno Carob flour

Land-use system name: Agro-Silvo-Pastoral

Name of the reference variable: Carob Pod Production

Figure 15 : Summary table of values per driver for Crete MRL (Greece)

A combination of climatic (extreme events, spring drought) and social drivers of change (depopulation, abandonment and change of use) can affect the reference variable in a negative way (Figure 15). Undoubtedly, avoiding the abandonment of carob crops or the change to olive groves is closely linked to giving greater value to carob products, something which, together with the application of adaptation mechanisms, could greatly reduce the vulnerability of the system.

Table 16. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Crete MRL (Greece)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1

07 - Transdanubian Mountains. Hungary

Mountain Reference Landscape: Transdanubian Mountains MRL

Value Chain name: Agroecological knowledge - Cold Mountain Shelter knowledge economy

Land-use system name: Mosaic land use system

Name of the reference variable: the quantity of healthy food produced through mosaic land use in agro-ecological farming

Figure 16 : Summary table of values per driver for Transdanubian MRL (Hungary)

The combination of drivers with high negative impact (positive score) with two drivers of change that have a positive impact on the reference variable (negative scores), greatly reduces overall impact (Table 17). Despite this, we cannot downplay the high impact values of the other drivers, especially those related to gentrification, land degradation, and climate drivers (Figure 16). Adaptation mechanisms have a high feasibility to be applied, although the overall adaptive capacity to these drivers is medium (not complete). Here again, it is important to have drivers of change that improve the situation, in order to compensate for the above.

Table 17. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Transdanubian MRL (Hungary)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1

08 - Central Apennines. Italy

Mountain Reference Landscape: Central Apennines MRL

Value Chain name: Alto Molise dairy production. Caciocavallo cheese.

Land-use system name: Agro-silvo-pastoral system (largely relevant for the VC).

Name of the reference variable: Permanent grasslands and meadows.

Figure 17 : Summary table of values per driver for Central Apennines MRL (Italy)

As in many rural areas ageing and population decline is one of the major challenges, which require adaptation mechanisms. In this case, the perception of the participants is that they are not very optimistic about the feasibility and full effectiveness of the mechanisms. Climate drivers (drought, temperature, and late frost), wild animals such as boar, and fires are other threats. Interestingly, and contrary to other cases, a greater feasibility is seen in the application of measures against climate drivers than in drivers of change with a social component.

Table 18. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Central Apennines MRL (Italy)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.6	0.2	0.2	0.3

09 - Eastern Alps. Italy

Mountain Reference Landscape: Eastern Alps MRL

Value Chain name: Trento Doc Wine - Mountain viticulture in Alto Trentino

Land-use system name: Permanent cropland

Name of the reference variable: vineyard productivity and grape quality

Figure 18 : Summary table of values per driver for Eastern Alps MRL (Italy)

Extreme events, in particular spring frosts and heavy rainfall, is the factor with the greatest impact on vineyard productivity and grape quality (Figure 18). In fact, heavy rainfall also causes soil erosion and compaction (soil physical degradation). Adaptive mechanisms for these drivers have a medium/low viability and impact reduction capacity. Similar is the case for drought and pollution, although with a lower impact value. Other factors, such as pests and over-exploitation of resources, are perceived as more controllable. In contrast, the positive impact that temperature can have on high mountain viticulture stands out.

Table 19. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Eastern Alps MRL (Italy)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.4	0.1	0.1	0.2

10 - Northern Apennines. Italy

Mountain Reference Landscape: Northern Apennines MRL

Value Chain name: Chestnut flour

Land-use system name: High intensity plant forest / Agroforestry

Name of the reference variable: “chestnuts tree varieties” that influence the high quality of the chestnut flour but also the annual production (quantity) of chestnuts.

Figure 19 : Summary table of values per driver for Northern Apennines MRL (Italy)

In this case study, the vulnerability of the system has been assessed taking into account only three drivers, considered to be the most important (Figure 19). The two main drivers are linked to each other, as it is the same social dynamics that cause both depopulation and the loss of knowledge and practices. The perception of adaptive capacity is quite negative, with little or no capacity to reduce impacts, and few mechanisms with high feasibility. In the case of pests, the trend in recent years has already been positive and there is a potential to reduce the average impact, which makes expectations better.

Table 20. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Northern Apennines MRL (Italy)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3

11 - Maleshevski mountains. North Macedonia

Mountain Reference Landscape: Maleshevski mountains MRL

Value Chain name: Rural tourism

Land-use system name: Mosaic/landscape of Maleshevski region (predominant medium intensity /natural forest)

Name of the reference variable: Landscape of Maleshevija.

Figure 20 : Summary table of values per driver for Maleshevsky mountains MRL (North Macedonia)

Participants perceived a medium impact (between 0.4 and 0.6) of most drivers (Figure 20). Optimism about adaptive capacity mechanisms stands out positively, as a high feasibility and a medium reduction capacity is perceived, which would greatly improve the situation, in the face of an impact of these drivers of change. For pests, on the other hand, it seems that this is not currently an important factor, but it would potentially have a large impact and is still perceived to have less coping capacity than the other drivers.

Table 21. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Maleshevsky mountains MRL (North Macedonia)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1

12 - Cordilheira Central. Portugal

Mountain Reference Landscape: Cordilheira Central MRL (Serra da Estrela)

Value Chain name: Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese

Land-use system name: Extensive Open Rangeland (3), more specifically, highland and lowland pastures

Name of the reference variable: Pasture area

Figure 21 : Summary table of values per driver for Cordilheira Central MRL (Portugal)

In this case study, the sensitivity of each of the drivers is so high that the system is potentially highly threatened, although this sensitivity is compensated by a trend for some drivers to be lower (Figure 21). The adaptive capacity for the climatic drivers in this case does not seem to be effective, although it does seem to be medium effective and with high viability for the rest. The final result is a relatively high impact for the system (Table 22), which translates into a medium vulnerability, due to the decreasing capacity of the adaptation mechanisms.

Table 22. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Cordilheira Central MRL (Portugal)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.6	0.4	0.4	0.4

13 - Maciço Noroeste. Portugal

Mountain Reference Landscape: Maciço Noroeste MRL (Douro Superior)

Value Chain name: Dour Wine Value Chain

Land-use system name: Permanent cropland

Name of the reference variable: The vineyard productivity and grape quality

Figure 22 : Summary table of values per driver for Maciço Noroeste MRL (Portugal)

The high impact value for demographic changes stands out as one of the highest obtained in the case study, far ahead of the second one, which would be drought (Figure 22). The adaptive capacity mechanisms generally have a medium reduction capacity and high viability, except for demographic changes, overexploitation of resources and pest, where the mechanisms with the highest viability have a lower impact reduction capacity which means that in a scenario where only the most viable mechanisms are applied, the vulnerability would be 0.2 (Table 23), in contrast to 0.1 if all the mechanisms or the mechanisms with medium viability were applied.

Table 23. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Maciço Noroeste MRL (Portugal)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.4	0.1	0.1	0.2

14 - Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains. Romania

Mountain Reference Landscape: Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL (Piatra Craiului National Park)

Value Chain name: Certified Ecotourism

Land-use system name: Mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland

Name of the reference variable: “landscape composition” was considered more subjectively as the basis of the “highly appreciated natural beauty of the area”

Figure 23 : Summary table of values per driver for Southern Romanian Carpathians MRL

Chaotic building development, emigration and depopulation are drivers of change showing a very large potential impact on the system, although in turn, there seems to be a full capacity to reduce this impact with mechanisms with high feasibility (Figure 23). The rest of the drivers, both climate and social components, show a medium impact, which can be reduced in a medium way in the social components. On the other hand, the selected mechanisms do not have the capacity to reduce the climate drivers (Figure 23). In general, there is a high capacity to reduce the impact on the system, from an impact of 0.6 to 0.1 across all adaptation scenarios (Table 24).

Table 24. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Southern Romanian Carpathians MRL

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.6	0.1	0.1	0.1

15 - Dinaric Mountains. Serbia

Mountain Reference Landscape: Dinaric Mountains MRL. (Sjenica – Pester plateau)

Value Chain name: Sjenica lamb meat (PDO)

Land-use system name: Extensive open rangeland /Mosaic cropland (extensive) and grassland with few livestock/

Name of the reference variable: Productivity and quality of the pastures on the highlands.

Figure 24 : Summary table of values per driver for Dinaric Mountains MRL (Serbia)

At a general overview, it can be observed that very high impact values are not perceived, with only extreme events, pollution and demographic changes standing out, due to the fact that sensitivity in general is medium and is accompanied by medium/low trends (Figure 24). In addition, for some drivers such as demographic changes, soil physical degradation has a full impact reduction potential capacity, which also contributes to a low overall vulnerability of the system. On the other hand, the application of adaptation mechanisms would not be sufficient for extreme events and pollution to significantly reduce their impact, with possible consequences derived from this.

Table 25. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Dinaric Mountains MRL (Serbia)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1

16 - Slovak Carpathian Mountains. Slovakia

Study case: Slovak Carpathians MRL

Value Chain name: Bio-honey

Land-use system name: extensive grasslands (pastures and meadows) and forest

Name of the reference variable: Diversity of pollen- and nectar – producing plants and honeydew from trees.

Figure 25 : Summary table of values per driver for Slovak Carpathian mountains MRL (Czech Republic)

The drivers with the greatest impact, are the climatic drivers (Extreme events, temperature increase and fluctuation and drought), for which there is none or a low potential to reduce the impact of the drivers (Figure 25), which could be worrying for this value chain. For the rest of the drivers, with average impact values, a greater capacity for adaptation is perceived.

Table 26. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Slovak Carpathian mountains MRL

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.5	0.2	0.2	0.3

17 - Betic Systems. Spain

Mountain Reference Landscape: Betic Systems MRL (Subbetica Cordobesa)
Value Chain name: Organic Mountain olive oil
Land-use system name: Betic Systems
Name of the reference variable: The productivity of organic olives (in terms of quantity and quality)

Figure 26 : Summary table of values per driver for Betic systems MRL (Spain)

Climate drivers (drought, temperature and extreme events) and demographic changes (depopulation) are the drivers with the greatest potential impact on olive productivity (Figure 26). It should be noted that the average potential impact reduction capacity and high viability of the adaptation mechanisms is high. The negative values in sensitivity and trend for the drivers of physical soil degradation and contamination are due to the improvement of the soil and the absence of contamination due to the change from conventional to organic production.

Table 27. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Betic systems MRL (Spain)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1

18 - Sierra Morena. Spain

Mountain Reference Landscape: Sierra Morena MRL (Pozoblanco, Villanueva de Cordoba, and Cardeña)

Value Chain name: Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham

Land-use system name: Agro-silvo-pastoral system

Name of the reference variable: Production of grass and acorns

Figure 27 : Summary table of values per driver for Sierra Morena MRL (Spain)

Impact values are high for most drivers ranging from 0.5 to 0.8 (Figure 27). Drought and overexploitation (livestock load) are the biggest threats, closely followed by pests ("*Phytophthora cinnamomi*"), temperature and extreme events. Adaptive capacity is low for the climate drivers, and medium-low for the rest, depending on the feasibility of the measures. Strong support is needed to ensure that most adaptive mechanisms can be implemented.

Table 28. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Sierra Morena MRL (Spain)

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.6	0.2	0.3	0.3

19 - Spanish Pyrenees. Spain

Mountain Reference Landscape: Spanish Pyrenees MRL

Value Chain name: Mountain Wine Value Chain (Spanish Vignerons from pre-Pyrenean mountains)

Land-use system name: permanent cropland

Name of the reference variable: The vineyard productivity and grape quality

Figure 28 : Summary table of values per driver for Spanish Pyrenees MRL (Spain)

The drivers of change with the greatest impact are physical land degradation and pollution due to poor management, pests, climatic drivers (extreme events, temperature and drought), and demographic changes (Figure 28). Perhaps this last driver is underestimated, as some of the participants lived outside the MRL. Less adaptive capacity is observed for climatic drivers, for which the feasibility of adaptation mechanisms is lower. In contrast, for the other drivers, high feasibility and medium impact reduction potential of the adaptation mechanisms is observed. This difference in feasibility means that vulnerability changes depending on the feasibility scenario.

Table 29. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Spanish Pyrenees MRL

impact	vulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.5	0.1	0.2	0.3

20 – Swiss Alps. Switzerland

Mountain Reference Landscape: Swiss Alps MRL
Value Chain name: Mountain Grain value chain (Grisons Mountain Cereals)
Land-use system name: Cropland extensive
Name of the reference variable: "Cereal yields" in kg/ha

Figure 29 : Summary table of values per driver for Swiss Alps MRL (Switzerland)

Two drivers stand out with a medium impact, weather extremes and "weeds" (Pests, diseases, and invasive species) (Figure 29). Two drivers with a positive impact also stand out. Temperature, because an increase in temperature in the mountains will improve crop productivity, and physical soil degradation, because good management of cereals can improve the soil. In general, adaptive capacity mechanisms have a medium to full impact reduction potential, with high feasibility, except in the case of weeds, where the reduction capacity is low.

Table 30. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Swiss Alps MRL

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.2	0	0.1	0.1

21 - Swiss Jura. Switzerland

Mountain Reference Landscape: Swiss Jura MRL

Value Chain name: Tête de Moine PDO

Land-use system name: Extensive open rangeland

Name of the reference variable: Annual production of grass and fodder expressed in terms of quantity and species diversity.

Figure 30 : Summary table of values per driver for Swiss Jura MRL (Switzerland)

In this case study, to calculate the vulnerability, only the three most relevant drivers were selected according to the ranking scores. Those drivers were extreme events, temperature and decrease rain and snow precipitation. The impact of the three selected drivers is medium-high (0.4-0.6) (Figure 30), but there are mechanisms with high feasibility and moderate impact reduction capacity, which if applied would reduce the vulnerability of the system.

Table 31. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Swiss Jura MRL

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2

22 – Beydaglari. Turkey

Mountain Reference Landscape: Beydaglari MRL
Value Chain name: Greenhouse Tomato
Land-use system name: Intensive annual crop / irrigated
Name of the reference variable: Greenhouse Tomato Production

Figure 31 : Summary table of values per driver for Beydaglary MRL (Turkey)

There is a high impact risk for the coming years for many drivers, warning of the need for urgent action. Fortunately, there appear to be mechanisms with high feasibility that could be applied to reduce vulnerability. Although it will require very strong support, to be able to implement mechanisms with medium and low feasibility in some cases, as well as creativity to be able to develop new ones. Issues related to water scarcity, temperature rise, disease, pollution, and soil degradation seem to need special attention.

Table 32. Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Beydaglary MRL (Turkey)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.7	0.2	0.2	0.3

23 –Highlands and Islands. United Kingdom – Scotland

Mountain Reference Landscape: Speyside MRL

Value chain name: Speyside Malt Whisky

Land-use system name: Extensive Rangeland

Name of the reference variable: Water Quantity

Figure 32 Summary table of values per driver for Speyside MRL (United Kingdom)

Overall, the vulnerability of the system is not very high (Table 33). This pattern results from some drivers that have a low impact and compensate for other drivers with relatively high impact values such as extreme events, air and water temperature and over exploitation of water resources (Figure 32). When calculating the vulnerability, we observe that for some drivers a complete reduction of impact is possible. Likewise, there are no mechanisms with high feasibility (due to lack of economic viability), which will require a strong involvement of the administration in order to address these challenges.

Table 33 : . Impact and vulnerability of the land use system for Speyside MRL (UK)

Impact	VulnAll	vulnMF	vulnHF
0.3	0.1	0.1	NA

6. Spatial vulnerability matrix and maps across regions (T3.4)

6.1. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Map per Mountain Reference Landscape

In this section, the spatial vulnerability matrices submitted by regional MOVING teams are presented for the 23 MRLs. Additionally, vulnerability maps were built for selected cases, depending on the characteristics of the spatial vulnerability matrix produced and the available spatial datasets.

01 Austrian Alps MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Austrian Alps MRL, the focal value chain is lamb production. To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the regional MOVING team were aridity, temperature, and extreme weather and the two spatial explicit factors selected were slope and exposition (Table 34).

Table 34: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Austrian Alps MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Permanent pastures	In Weiz, milk and meat producing sheeps are fed on permanent pastures in the summer season from March/April to October/November. In case of extreme heat, stable keeping for single days during June and August is practiced in some few cases. During the period of stable keeping (in winter) the sheeps are fed with hay silage produced from permanent grassland and concentrated food (especially lambs) from croplands.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Aridity	Precipitation patterns have already changed and will continue to change. The overall amount over the year will be stable, however, in summers, there will be less rain events, which will become much stronger. Exposed (south facing) slopes will be dried out, contributing to soil erosion. In winter, there will be less snow which negatively impacts the necessary humidity of the soil in spring. Sheep keeping might be more sustainable than cattle.

Temperature	In Austria, likewise in Weiz, average mean temperatures increase by a factor between 1,5 to 2 compared to the global mean. Lack of precipitation and high temperatures have already led and will lead to water stress. Sheep don't feel comfortable grazing in the heat; thus, they graze increasingly in the evening and early morning. Stables will need to be air-conditioned. There will be the need for more heat resistant plants on pastures and grassland to ensure the quality of the feed.
Extreme weather	Extreme weather occurs in regard to drought periods and heavy rain events. These events plus strong winds lead to soil erosion. Compared to cattle grazing, sheep is associated with lower risks of causing soil erosion, which is seen as an opportunity (beside the facts, that sheep keeping is cheaper and more flexible in time).
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Slope	The steeper the slopes the more difficult it is to cultivate pasture and grassland. Sheep keeping is more appropriate for these pieces of land than cattle, since sheep can graze at steeper slopes. However, the risk of soil erosion and mud slides caused by the combination of less rain in summer, heavy rain punctually, higher temperatures and droughts increases at steeper slopes.
Exposition	This factor is most relevant in regard to heat. Especially south facing slopes dry out during summer, when exposed to the sun. Increased temperatures and drought periods combined with grazing animals (cattle more relevant than sheep) and weakened plants (poorly developed roots) decrease the stability of the soils. Heavy rain events cause soil erosion and mud slides.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures presented below (Figure 33). The classes for slope and exposition were defined based on interviews and expert consultation. At slopes up to 20% with North exposition the vulnerability of permanent pastures to aridity, temperature and extreme weather was considered low (level 2). Meanwhile, at bigger slopes with South exposition it was considered very higher (level 5).

Figure 33: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Permanent Pastures at Austrian Alps MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			<i>Slope (%)</i>		
			<i>[0-10]</i>	<i>]10-20]</i>	<i>]20-max]</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Exposition</i>	<i>North</i>	2	2	3
		<i>East-West</i>	3	3	4
		<i>South</i>	4	4	5

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the permanent pastures of Austrian Alps MRL, which is presented in Figure 34. The auxiliary maps used to build it (one for each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and one with the land use system area) can be consulted in Appendix II.

Vulnerability levels 5 (very high), 4 (high) and 3 (medium) occupy 29.46%, 32.54% and 28.45% of the permanent pastures area at MRL01, respectively (Table 35). Only 9.5% of the referred LUS is classified with a vulnerability level of 2 (low) and there are no areas considered of very low vulnerability (level 1).

Figure 34: Vulnerability Map for the Permanent Pastures of Austrian Alps MRL

Table 35. Percentage of Permanent Pastures area in each Vulnerability Level at Austrian Alps MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	0.00
2. Low	9.55
3. Medium	28.45
4. High	32.54
5. Very high	29.46

02 Stara Planina MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Stara Planina MRL, the focal value chain is public goods from High Nature Value farming, which rely on a mosaic (semi-) natural system (Table 36). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the regional MOVING team were land abandonment and demographic change (depopulation) and the two spatial explicit factors selected were Single Area Payment Scheme (SAPS), income support payments (CAP Pillar 1) and Agri-environment payments (CAP Pillar 2).

Table 36: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Stara Planina MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Mosaic (semi-) natural system	High Nature Value (HNV) Farmland with a high proportion of grazed semi-natural vegetation plus mosaic of low intensity cropping and natural landscape elements. There is a significant loss of important habitats due to land abandonment.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Land abandonment	Severe scrub encroachment and natural re-afforestation of HNV grasslands in the MRL due to under-grazing and abandonment of traditional hay-making is degrading valuable habitats (from the Habitats Directive: 6210, 6230, 6510 and 6520) and closing the mosaic landscape.
Demographic changes (depopulation)	The MRL suffered major depopulation during the 1970s and 1980s and this has increased again in recent years with a 40% decline in population between 2010 and 2020. Since it is mainly young people leaving the area, the remaining population is increasingly aged.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
SAPS income support payments (CAP Pillar 1)	Income support under SAPS has been an important factor encouraging the maintenance (avoidance of abandonment) of mowing / grazing on semi-natural

	grasslands. However, grasslands with more than 100 trees and/or scrubs per ha are not eligible for Pillar 1 SAPS support.
Agri-environment payments (CAP Pillar 2)	There have been two AECM schemes for encouraging the continued extensive management of HNV grasslands, but the impact of these measures depends upon specific eligibility criteria.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for the mosaic (semi-) natural system presented below (Figure 35). The classes for SAPS income support payments (CAP Pillar 1) and Agri-environment payments (CAP Pillar 2) were defined based on the Bulgarian "Land Parcel Identification System" (LPIS), more specifically, on the SAPS eligibility layer (for both cases) and on HNV eligibility layer (only for the later). At land which is eligible for SAPS and HNV support payments and, also, for SAPS income support payments, the vulnerability of mosaic (semi-) natural systems to land abandonment and demographic changes (depopulation) was considered very low (level 1). However, at land which is only eligible for SAPS support payments, it was considered very high (level 5).

Figure 35 Spatial Vulnerability Matrix Stara Planina MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1	
			SAPS income support payments (CAP Pillar 1)	
			<i>Eligible (< 100 trees and/or shrubs per ha)</i>	<i>Not eligible (> 100 trees and/or shrubs per ha)</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Agri-environment payments (CAP Pillar 2)	<i>Eligible for SAPS and HNV support payment</i>	1	2
		<i>Only eligible for HNV support payment</i>	3	3
		<i>Only eligible for SAPS support payment</i>	4	5

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

03 Sumava – Cesky Les MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Sumava – Cesky Les MRL, the focal value chain is beef production, which relies on a LUS of permanent pastures (Table 37) To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the regional MOVING team were precipitation and demographic changes and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation and distance to urban centres.

Table 37: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Sumava – Cesky Les MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Permanent pastures	Land in the Sumava region is used for agriculture (perennial grassland) and forestry. The climatic conditions and the slopes of the plots limit agricultural usage of the land. The altitude around 800 metres above sea level is considered as a crossing line between a production-oriented agriculture and the pure landscape maintenance.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	Continuous low rainfall with potential impact on vegetation, hydrological level (streams and aquifers) and soil. The amount of the spring and summer rains impacts on the amount of forage. Drought reduces availability of grass on pastures and availability of hay for winter season.
Demographic changes	Population decline or immigration in the region might produce changes in the management practices and land-use abandonment. There are not enough young people entering agriculture, so farms lack employees and family farms have difficulty with finding a successor.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation	Precipitation (lack of rainfalls) is a bigger problem for areas with lower altitudes within the MRL, where decrease of rainfalls is more common. It was explicitly stated that the areas with higher altitude are not so much affected.
Distance to urban centres	Population decline is a bigger problem mainly for areas remote from urban centres (more than 1 hour from the city with approx. 100 000 inhabitants).

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures presented below (Figure 36). At elevations above 800 m with a distance to urban centres up to 50 km the vulnerability of permanent pastures to precipitation and demographic changes was considered very low (level 1). In turn, at elevations up to 800 m with a distance to urban centres above 50 km it was considered high (level 4).

Figure 36: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix Permanent Pastures at Sumava - Cesky Les MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1	
			Elevation (m)	
			[0-800]]800-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Distance to urban centres (km)	[0-50]	3	1
]50-max]	4	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the permanent pastures of Sumava – Cesky Les MRL, which is presented in Figure 37. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II. About 3/4 of the permanent pastures area at Sumava – Cesky Les MRL was considered as having low vulnerability (level 2) and about 1/5 as having high vulnerability (level 4) (Table 38). There were no permanent pastures classified with a vulnerability level of 5 (very high).

Figure 37: Vulnerability Map for the Permanent Pastures of Sumava – Cesky Les MRL

Table 38: Percentage of Permanent Pastures area in each Vulnerability Level at Sumava – Cesky Les MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	4.23
2. Low	74.29
3. Medium	2.02
4. High	19.47
5. Very high	0.00

04 Corsica MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At chestnut flour, which relies on a LUS of high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) (Table 39). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were rainfall, pests, and animal stray and the two spatial explicit factors selected were rainfall and exposition.

Table 39: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Corsica MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Hight intensity plant forest (Agroforestry)	Chestnut orchards are mostly close to villages. These old orchards are threatened by overgrowth (brambles, ferns, thorns, arbutus or heather). The regular harvesting of chestnuts f or flour production is the only activity that entails maintenance or even management.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Rainfall	Rainfall expression is above all the drought which takes 2003 as the reference year. Since then, it has intensified with climate change with one significant episode every 3 years. Note that irrigation is prohibited by the PDO specifications. The effects of drought are multiple and antagonist: smaller fruit size but higher flour yield and sweetness). Stakeholders consider that the repetition of summer drought episodes (June-October) determines the vulnerability and lifespan of trees and production volumes.
Pests	Phytophthora and Cryphonectria diseases were the first obstacles to the revival of chestnut groves (1975). Fungi cause trees to die back more or less rapidly. The causes are climatic and linked to transmission by pigs (burrowing). Control are inoculation of endogenous mycorrhizae (Ink) and the use of hypo virulent strains. The recent period has seen the sudden appearance of fruits (2010-2020) of <i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i> causing a drastic and significant decrease in fruit production (50 to 100%). Biological control by <i>Torymus sinensis</i> contains the disease successfully and generates an effective local health system. <i>Balaninus</i> attacks the fruits, but those impacts are less important.
Animal stray	The wandering of animals especially cows and pigs impacts the reference variable through fruit predation, soil degradation (burrowing and trampling) and supporting structures for terraces. The solutions identified are coercive (public sanctions, prohibition of grazing) and organisational (common rules, customary uses of “u furestu”). The abundance of wild boars causes similar damage.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Rainfall	Episode of drought during the summer period (June-October, fertilisation of flowers and ripening of fruits).
Exposition	Exposure for an altitude of 600 meters.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) presented below (Figure 38). The classes for rainfall were defined based on Gamisans (2010). At areas with South exposition and rainfall between June and October of less than 700 mm the vulnerability of high intensity plant forest to rainfall, pests and animal stray was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at areas with North exposition and rainfall between June and October above 800 mm it was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 38: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for High Intensity Plant Forest (Agroforestry) at Corsica MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Rainfall from June to October (mm)		
			[0-700]]700-800]]800-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Exposition	South	5	4	2
		North	4	3	1

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

05 Drôme Valley MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Drôme Valley MRL, the focal value chain is sheep meat, which relies on a LUS of permanent pastures (Table 40). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were precipitation and temperature and the two spatial explicit factors selected were position combined with precipitation and elevation.

Table 40: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Drôme Valley MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Permanent pastures	The study area includes 13 municipalities in the southern part of the Vercors massif. This area is characterized by small-scale agriculture and by extensive grasslands. The study particularly focuses on the Gervanne and Ambel plateaux, which are the two most important permanent and public grasslands in the region.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	The dysregulation of the water regime by climate change affects the rainfall frequency and homogeneity. Following an altitudinal gradient, the phenomenon is less marked. Subjected to the Mediterranean climate, the southern region of the

	Vercors experiences less frequent and less evenly distributed rainfall throughout the year. This impact largely affects grass growth.
Temperature	Temperatures are generally rising over the MRL. Winters are mild and there are heat waves throughout the year. This disruption impacts the renewal cycles of the grass and slows down its growth, especially in south-facing areas.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Position/ Precipitation	Western and Southern Vercors were considered. In southern Vercors, about a third of the precipitation is subject to Mediterranean influences, resulting in rainfall that is less evenly distributed over the year and in smaller quantities.
Elevation	The impacts related to climate change and indicated by the drivers (precipitation, temperatures) assume a different severity depending on the altitude. The pastoral areas of the lower mountains and those facing south will be more affected by drought than the high plateaux. Vegetation diversity is also affected by this problem.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures presented below (Figure 39). The classes for position/precipitation were defined based on Misset (2014), Guillot (1968) and the Vercors Parc website and the classes for elevation were established based on expert assessment. At elevations up to 900 m in the Southern Vercors the vulnerability of permanent pastures to precipitation and temperature was considered high (level 4), while at elevations above 1100 m in the Western Vercors it was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 39: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Permanent Pastures at Drôme Valley MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1	
			<i>Position / Precipitation (mm)</i>	
			<i>Western Vercors / [900-1500]</i>	<i>Southern Vercors / [0-900]</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Elevation (m)</i>	<i>[0-600]</i>	3	4
		<i>]600-1100]</i>	2	3
		<i>]1100-max]</i>	1	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

06 Crete MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Crete MRL, the focal value chain is central Rethymno carob, which relies on a LUS of agroforestry (Table 41). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were demographic changes, land-use and land-cover change and precipitation and the spatial explicit factor selected was elevation.

Table 41: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factor selected for Crete MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Agroforestry	Carob tree is a multipurpose and pod producing species very well adapted to dry-farming conditions and important to the sustainability of agroforestry-ecosystems. Agro-pastoral land management, the co-existence of agriculture and animal husbandry enhances pod production, due to natural fertilisation and weeding. On the other hand, more intensive olive tree farming can complicate carob pod production (diseases, insects, fertilizers, and insecticides).
Vulnerability Drivers	
Demographic changes	Land/harvesting abandonment due to ageing population and farming occupation abandonment by the younger generation. Loss of knowledge regarding grafting and pruning due to demographic changes and decades of harvesting abandonment has impacted pod production.
Land-use and land-cover change	Land-use changes driven by profit margins led to the shift to the monoculture of olives. This shift was fuelled by EU subsidies for olive farming. The more intensive olive farming led to road construction and land fragmentation and the destruction of great numbers of carob trees. In the past years, these changes have led to harvesting abandonment. Moreover, the shift to the olive tree monoculture has increased the risk of pest invasions, diseases, and pollutants.
Precipitation	Carob pod production in the MRL occurs in non-irrigation orchards and depends on favourable rainfall conditions, which do not always exist in the region which is also characterized by great diversity in microclimate. Moderate drought during spring, summer, and autumn is common, with implications for yield, farmers income, and on a long-term basis for land use. Facing drought scenarios, farmers rely on carob in order to obtain a complementary revenue, as an alternative to more intensive and irrigation demanding farming, yet extreme drought conditions impacts yields differently depending on the particularities of the microclimate.
Spatial Explicit Factor	
Elevation	Traditionally carob pod production in high elevations was considered inefficient and unsustainable due to the sensitivity to frost. With the advent of climate change, in the past years pod production in carob groves in the higher elevations has increased. Nevertheless, according to the 1991 and 2016 census data villages in the MRL that are close to Rethymno (<10km) have maintained or even increased their population.

While villages that are further away from the city have shrunk in population. It is noteworthy that the semi-mountainous and not so much the mountainous villages at a distance of more than 10km from Rethymno depict the largest population declines (-42%). It is within these semi-mountainous villages that carob pods are cultivated.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for agroforestry presented below (Figure 40). The classes for elevation were defined based on research and expert opinion. At intermediate elevations (between 300 m and 600 m) the vulnerability of agroforestry areas to demographic changes, land-use and land-cover changes and precipitation was considered very low (level 1), while at lower elevations it was considered medium (level 3) and at higher elevations it was considered low (level 1).

Figure 40: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for agroforestry at Crete MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			
Spatial Explicit Factor	<i>Elevation (m)</i>	[0-300]	3
]300-600]	1
]600-max]	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of the vulnerability map for Crete MRL, which is presented in

Figure 41. However, the vulnerability map has an important limitation because vulnerability levels should be restricted to the agroforestry areas dedicated to carob production. In fact, there is no continuous carob tree forest in the area, and it was not possible to obtain an accurate map of the referred LUS. More specifically, at lower elevations [0-300 m] carob trees are practically displaced due to the much more profitable olive tree cultivation. At elevations higher than 600 m the climatic conditions are the least favourable, but this is changing due to the climatic change. The majority of carob tree orchards thrive in the semi-mountainous agro-silvo-pastoral areas, but they are developed in clusters and do not constitute a single cultivation area in the MRL. Therefore, the vulnerability map presented here should be interpreted carefully, since the vulnerability levels represented should only be taken into consideration for the areas where agroforestry areas dedicated to carob production are known to be present.

The auxiliary map used to build the vulnerability map – elevation considering the classes defined in the matrix – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Figure 41: Vulnerability Map at Crete MRL

07 Transdanubian Mountains MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Transdanubian MRL, the focal value chain is agroecological knowledge, which relies on a mosaic of land uses (Table 42) located at the *Cold Mountain Shelter* community. For the production of the spatial vulnerability matrix, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were precipitation, land-use change and soil physical degradation and the two spatial explicit factors selected were tree cover density and slope.

Table 42 Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Tansdanubian Mountains MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Mosaic of land uses	Cold Mountain Shelter is a small community of young, educated environmentally conscious lifestyle migrants. They produce food through permaculture, forest agriculture, contour farming, extensive animal husbandry, etc. Though, they main product is knowledge on sustainable livelihoods.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	The most important element in the “variability” of precipitation is that its distribution, quantity and intensity have become uneven and unpredictable both within one year and between years. Dry autumns and springs, winters without snowfall, with most of the precipitation falling in the form of summer showers accompanied by long periods of drought are typical. All this weakens extensive crops without irrigation, make them vulnerable and significantly reduce the quality and quantity of food produced. Badly timed rainfall causes further problems in orchards (lack of pollination, rot, disease).
Land-uses change	Agro-ecological, regenerative farming has been started in the area of the Cold Mountain Shelter by environmentally conscious urban families with high cultural capital, through mosaic land use, involving significant knowledge, innovation and labour. As a result, eroded soils are being restored, forested areas are being converted into cultivated land and productivity is being improved. Land-use change may temporarily reduce the value of the area from a conservation point of view, but in the long term it benefits the area.
Soil physical degradation	As a result of decades of poor management, there are weak soils in the area. Erosion by water and wind in exposed areas, especially due to sudden high rainfall, slow humus formation and thin, eroded topsoil result in difficulties in fertilisation. This results in significant soil degradation, erosion, poor water holding capacity, low nutrient content. Soil physical degradation is the most important factor the local producers are fighting with.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Tree cover density	Some of the area is still in intensive wine or arable production (ploughed, kept clean of cover). Other areas are different kinds of grassland, again others became more or less afforested/scrubbed. The denser the land cover is, the lesser is the danger of soil erosion resulting from downpours.
Slope	The steeper the slope is, the more danger is carried by downpours for soil erosion.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for the mosaic of land uses presented below (Figure 42). The classes for tree cover density and slope were established based on expert assessment. At slopes up to 10% with a tree cover density above 60% the vulnerability of the mosaic of land uses to precipitation, land use change and soil physical degradation was considered very low (level 1). On the contrary, at slopes above 20% with a tree cover density up to 10% it was considered very high (level 5).

Figure 42: MRL Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for the Mosaic of Land Uses at Transdanubian Mountains

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Tree cover density (%)		
			[0-10]]10-60]]60-100]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Slope (%)	[0-10]	3	2	1
]10-20]	4	3	2
]20-max]	5	4	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the mosaic of land uses of the Cold Mountain Shelter at Transdanubian Mountains MRL (and also for a bigger area which is of potential interest for the community), which is presented in Figure 43. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 for each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix – can be consulted in Appendix II.

At the mosaic of land uses of Cold Mountain Shelter most of the area was classified as having very low (level 1, 36.93%) or medium (level 3, 34.31%) vulnerability to the drivers presented in (Table 43). Land considered of high (level 4) and very high (level 5) of vulnerability occupies 9.95% and 4.73% of the area, respectively.

At the area of potential interest (which, as shown in Figure 43, includes the mosaic of land uses of Cold Mountain Shelter) most of the area was classified as having medium (level 3, 38.75%) and very low (level 1, 30.78%) vulnerability. Land with high (level 4) and very high (level 5) vulnerability occupies 12.20 and 2.90% of the area, respectively.

Figure 43: Vulnerability Map for the Agro-ecological Production Area (Mosaic of Land Uses) and Area of Potential Interest within the Transdanubian Mountains MRL

Table 43: Percentage of the Mosaic of Land Uses of *Cold Mountain Shelter* and of the Area of Potential Interest (which includes the former) area in each Vulnerability Level at Transdanubian Mountains MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)	Zone of potential interest area (%)
1. Very low	36.93	30.78
2. Low	14.08	15.36
3. Medium	34.31	38.75
4. High	9.95	12.20
5. Very high	4.73	2.90

08 Central Apennines MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Central Apennines MRL, the focal value chain is Alto-Molise dairy, which relies on an agro-silvo-pastoral system (Table 44). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the regional MOVING were precipitation, temperature and demographic changes and the spatial explicit factor selected was elevation.

Table 44: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factor selected for Central Apennines MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Agro-silvo-pastoral system	
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	It is one of the most relevant factors that affects "grassland resource". Rainfalls are increasingly intense and distribute in a not usual manner (long period of drought and short intense storm). Snowfalls are also lower, and snowpack is less persistent. This situation changes the hay mowing period.
Temperature	Grassland is suffering by the unusually and more frequent higher temperature in all seasons and it is becoming difficult to forecast temperature trends. For this, the area records relevant dry grassland and changing in the mowing period (anticipated or postponed). Temperature also affects hay quality & quantity. Sudden thermal changes also hit livestock health or fertility, and consequently, milk production.
Demographic changes	Despite some young people is engaged in managing or opening new farming and several dairies support/need breeder activities (specifically in Agnone), the area records depopulation, ageing of population and contraction in workforce turnover in agriculture / breeding businesses. Moreover, the immigrate workforce does not reduce the trend. It deeply affects "grassland resource" (increasing of uncultivated/unused land and territorial mismanagement, contraction of livestock & breeders, etc.).
Spatial Explicit Factor	
Elevation	Climate change impacts seem to be different also based on the altitude (severe in lower altitude and less severe on higher ones). For this reason, the reference variable and the VC can be affected in different way based on the altitude.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for the agro-silvo-pastoral system presented below (Figure 44). The classes for elevation were established based on expert assessment. At elevations up to 600 m the vulnerability of the LUS to precipitation, temperature and demographic changes was considered low (level 2), while at areas above 1000 m it was considered high (level 4).

Figure 44: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for the Agro-silvo-pastoral system at Central Apennines MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			
Spatial Explicit Factor	Elevation	[0-600]	2
]600-1000]	3
]1000-max]	4

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the agro-silvo-pastoral system at the Central Apennines MRL, which is presented in Figure 45. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 for the spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

In the agro-silvo-pastoral system at the Central Apennines MRL, vulnerability levels 3 (medium) and 4 (high) occupy 49.50% and 46.34% of the area, respectively (Table 45). Only 4.13% of the referred LUS was classified with a vulnerability level of 2 (low).

Figure 45: Vulnerability Map for Agro-silvo-pastoral System at Central Apennines MRL

Table 45: Percentage of Agro-silvo-pastoral System area in each Vulnerability Level at Central Apennines MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	0.00
2. Low	4.16
3. Medium	49.50
4. High	46.34
5. Very high	0.00

09 Eastern Alps MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Eastern Alps MRL, the focal value chain is Trento Doc wine, which relies on a LUS of vineyards (Table 46). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability driver considered by the respective regional MOVING team was temperature and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation and slope.

Table 46: Land use system, vulnerability driver and spatial explicit factors selected for Eastern Alps MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Vineyards	The MRL hosts specialized viticulture, often linked to family farming but progressively shifting towards larger and more specialized systems, even if organic and low impact management systems are gaining share.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Temperature	It refers to the increase in average temperatures, especially in the intermediate seasons (Spring and Autumn) with a potential (quite concrete) influence on the vegetative cycle of the vineyard and the cycles of pathogens and parasites. Increasing temperature allows grapes to grow at altitude, where ripening takes place more slowly with the development of aromas, while maintaining acidity. A general anticipation of the vegetative cycle makes evident the positive effect of planting vineyards in higher altitudes in order to have a later harvest. Increasing temperature can interfere with the severity of certain pathogens (e.g., downy mildew). The earlier development of vegetation in Spring increases the risk of frost damage.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation	The negative impact of increasing temperatures is more evident at lower altitudes in the valley. On higher altitudes, the temperature never reaches extreme parameters and vineyards located there avoid the risks related with this driver. Late frost tends to bring more damage in lower located vineyards, saving those in higher zones.

Slope	The inclination of the slope is also a factor which can determine the risk of frost damage: the risk is higher on flat land and lower in slopy areas.
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According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for vineyards presented below (Figure 46). The classes for elevation and slope were defined based on expert assessment. At slopes up to 10% with elevations up to 400 m the vulnerability of vineyards to temperature was considered very high (level 5). As slope and/or elevation increase the vulnerability decreases. In fact, the vulnerability level at slopes above 10% with elevations above 700 m was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 46: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Vineyards at Eastern Alps MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Elevation (m)		
			[0-400]]400-700]]700-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Slope (%)	[0-10]	5	3	2
]10-max]	4	2	1

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the vineyards of the Eastern Alps MRL, which is presented in Figure 47. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II. Vulnerability level 5 (very high) and 4 (high) occupy 46.55% and 25.68% of the vineyards area, respectively (Table 47). Additionally, 25.97% of the vineyards were considered of low vulnerability.

Figure 47: Vulnerability Map for the Vineyards at Eastern Alps MRL

Table 47: Percentage of Vineyards area in each Vulnerability Level at Eastern Alps MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	0.01
2. Low	25.97
3. Medium	1.79
4. High	25.68
5. Very high	46.55

10 Northern Apennines MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Northern Apennines MRL, the focal value chain is chestnut flour, which relies on a LUS of high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) (Table 48). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were lack of silvicultural practices, pest and demographic change and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation combined with exposition and distance from main roads or village.

Table 48: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Northern Apennines MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
High intensity plant forest (agroforestry)	The most common forest type is the one characterized by the presence of chestnut (64%). This is followed by stands with the presence of hornbeam (about 20%) and other typologies of forest. We need to consider that the VC is located in an abandoned agroforestry system.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Lack of silvicultural practices	Abandonment is the first component limiting forest management: absence of chestnut pruning, no cleaning of the undergrowth from other broad-leaved trees, no planting or grafting of new plants, and no targeted irrigation in specific periods.
Pests	Lack of coordinated control of existing pests. Poor crop management at farm level.
Demographic change	Historically, there has always been strong migrations towards abroad and towards the plains. In the past, however, the families were numerous, and it was always someone to whom to pass on the knowledge and carry out the management of the chestnut grove. Today, on the contrary, generational change seldomly took place in the local landscape context, while most of the people carry on this profession often come from cities.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation and Exposition	In the last years due to the climate change, and to the increase of temperature, the agroforestry has shown a good productivity in the chestnuts located on high level or on north exposition.
Distance from main roads or village	Abandonment is related to accessibility, and it increase with increasing distance from the main roads or village.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) presented below (Figure 48). The classes for elevation/exposition and distance from main roads or village were established based on expert assessment. At areas above 600 m of elevation with a maximum distance of 100 m from main roads or villages the vulnerability of high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) to lack of silvicultural practices, pests and demographic changes was considered very low (level 1). On the contrary, it was considered very high (level 5) at elevations up to 600m with South exposition that are at more than 100 m from main roads or villages.

Figure 48: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for High Intensity Plant Forest (Agroforestry) at Northern Apennines MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Elevation (m) and Exposition		
			[0-600] South exposition	[0-600] North exposition]600-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Distance from main roads or village (m)	[0-100]	4	2	1
]100-max]	5	3	4

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for 75.69% of the area of high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) of Northern Apennines MRL, which is presented on Figure 59. In the case of this MRL, not the whole area considered of high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) has a vulnerability level attributed to it, because for spatial explicit factor 1 (elevation combined with exposition) the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix do not cover all possibilities of exposition, namely they do not cover East and West expositions up to 600 m of elevation.

The auxiliary maps used to build the vulnerability map – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Regarding the 75,69% of the area of high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) that was classified for vulnerability within the Northern Apennines MRL, 64.29% was considered as highly vulnerable (level 4). Levels 3 (medium) and 5 (very high) represent 15.10% and 14.08% of the area, respectively (Table 49).

Table 49: Percentage of High Intensity Plant Forest (Agroforestry) area in each Vulnerability Level at Northern Apennines MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	3.29
2. Low	3.24
3. Medium	15.10
4. High	64.29
5. Very high	14.08

Figure 49: Vulnerability Map for the High Intensity Plant Forest (Agroforestry) at Northern Apennines MRL

11 Maleshevski Mountains MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Maleshevski Mountains MRL, the focal value chain is rural tourism, which relies on a mosaic landscape (Table 50). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix, the vulnerability drivers considered by the regional MOVING team were precipitation and temperature and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation and precipitation (Figure 49).

Table 50: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Maleshevski Mountains MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Mosaic landscape	The direction of stretching of the Maleshevo Mountains is southwest to north-northeast whose ridge is 32 km long and intersects the peaks of Jami Tepe (1801 m) and Chengino Kale (1748 m). The region of Malesevija covers 39.833 ha of which 85% are forests, and 6.081ha (15%) forest land. The forest floor is dominated by beech forests, pine forests and fir forests. Forest ecosystems cover 81.7% of the land, grass ecosystems cover 12.61% and mountainous shrubs cover 4.22 %.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	Rainfall regime has a direct impact on the growth and development of forest communities, wildfires, pests and diseases. The average annual rainfall in the projected area extends between the drier area Delchevo (570 mm) and the wetland Berovo (677 mm) which is located at a higher altitude (846 m). In the last ten years due to climate change, the study results show sufficiency of water which increases the frequency of droughts, pests, wide-range wildfires that are constantly present during the summer period.
Temperature	Macedonia has approximately 290 sunny days in the year. Malesevski mountains region is the coldest region in North Macedonia. The lower mountainous parts that are located at an altitude of (1000 m – 1600 m) have an average annual temperature of 10 degrees. In the winter period, temperatures reach -30 degrees. In summer period the maximum temperatures can reach 38 degrees. In combination with low precipitations, high temperatures during the summer period cause soil aridness and as a consequence the forests are vulnerable to pests, diseases and wide-range wildfires.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation	According to the climate models used, with the increase of the altitude, the precipitation increases on average 15-25 mm for every 100 m higher altitude. At high altitudes, fires and pests are less likely to occur due to low temperatures, heavy rainfall and rarely tree density on altitudes around 2000m, where highland pastures dominate. Inaccessibility of the terrain minimizes the anthropogenic factor as well.

	Wide-range wildfires begin to spread from the bottom to the top. If the wind is ally during the process of wildfire-spreading, the inaccessibility of the terrain makes it difficult to react and prevent fast. Pests and diseases are also unlikely to appear at high altitudes.
Precipitation	The region of Maleshevija is well known for collecting non-timber forest products and their processing to create natural-local products. The lack of balanced rainfall regime affects the greener economic outcome of the forests due to the deficiency of water in the last ten years. The soil is dry, and the processes of soil degradation appear due to the frequent wildfires and low tree and shrub density. In the highest altitudes around the mountain peaks, the average annual rainfall regime reaches 850 mm.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for mosaic landscape presented below (Figure 50). The classes for elevation and precipitation were defined based on a study for Valorisation of the natural values of the Maleshevski mountains. When precipitation is at the lower class ([0-500]) the vulnerability of the mosaic landscape was considered high (level 4). As the precipitation increases, the vulnerability decreases and was considered low (level 2) at the higher precipitation class ([650-max]).

Figure 50: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Mosaic Landscape at Maleshevski Mountains MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1	
			Elevation (m)	
			[0-1500]]1500-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Precipitation (mm)	[0-500]	4	4
]500-650]	3	3
]650-max]	2	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the mosaic landscape of Maleshevski Mountains MRL, which is presented on Figure 51.

The whole Maleshevski Mountains MRL was considered a mosaic landscape, so the vulnerability levels in the vulnerability matrix (Figure 50) were applied in the entire MRL area. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Most of the Mosaic landscape/Maleshevski Mountains MRL area (98.81%) was classified with a vulnerability level of 3 (medium) (Table 51).

Figure 51: Vulnerability Map for the Mosaic Landscape of Maleshevski Mountains MRL

Table 51: Percentage of Mosaic landscape area in each Vulnerability Level at Maleshevski Mountains MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	0.00
2. Low	0.11
3. Medium	98.81
4. High	1.08
5. Very high	0.00

12 Cordilheira Central MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Cordilheira Central MRL, the focal value chain is PDO Serra da Estrela cheese, which relies on a LUS of permanent pastures (Table 52). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were wildfire and land abandonment and the two spatial explicit factors selected were distance to forests and shrublands and elevation.

Table 52: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Codilheira Central MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Permanent pastures	Permanent Pasture is the more detailed land use class (within the more general Land Use System - Extensive Open Rangeland) that feeds Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese Value Chain. In Serra da Estrela, milk-producing sheep feed on permanent pastures at high lands and lowlands. These pastures are being abandoned over the years due to lack of renewal of shepherds' generations.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Wildfire	Due to the high rate of forests in land cover and the increasingly severe summer drought, high severity fires are a constant threat to land use systems, including grazed areas, which are affected by contagion from areas covered by shrubland and forest, where fires often progress beyond the capacity for technological suppression.
Land abandonment	Land abandonment, due to demographic changes and a sharp decay in the number of producers, is reflected in this case in the decrease in grazing intensity, which results in the shrub encroachment of prior pasture areas. In Serra da Estrela, there is an invasion of protected pastures under the Natura 2000 Network (habitat 6230) by <i>Calluna vulgaris</i> (heathlands). After being covered by shrub, permanent pastures are hard to recover into pastures again, while the risk of fire increases.
In this case, there is a relationship between the two processes. The increased susceptibility of the landscape to fire increases with land abandonment because these communities, that colonize the former pastures, are fire-prone and increase the spatial continuity of fuels available to be consumed by fire. Pastures, on the other hand, were spaces where it was easier to fight fire, as they had a lower fuel load. These pastures were maintained by animals and winter fire use (there is now a surplus of bad summer fires as a result of the deficit of good winter fires related to the collapse of the grazing system).	
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Distance to forests and shrublands	Pastures higher distances from forests and shrublands are seen as an advantage to avoid the risk of being consumed by wildfire.

Elevation	Highland pastures are the first to be abandoned as lowland pastures are often enough to the sheep producers remaining in the area and also more accessible. Pastures abandonment results in shrub encroachment which increases the risk of wildfire.
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According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures presented below (Figure 52). The classes for distance to forests and shrublands and elevation were established based on expert assessment. At elevations above 1000 m with distances to forests and shrublands up to 250 m, the vulnerability of pastures to wildfire and land abandonment was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at elevations up to 1000 m with a distance from forests and shrublands above 750 m, it was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 52: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Permanent Pastures at Cordilheira Central MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			<i>Distance to forests and shrublands</i>		
			<i>[0-250]</i>	<i>]250-750]</i>	<i>]750-max]</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Elevation (m)</i>	<i>[0-1000]</i>	4	3	1
		<i>]1000-max]</i>	5	4	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the permanent pastures of Cordilheira Central MRL, which is presented in Figure 53.

The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

About 2/3 of the permanent pastures within Cordilheira Central MRL were classified with a vulnerability level of 4 (high) 67.50%, (Table 53). Vulnerability Level 3 (medium), 1 (very low) and 5 (very high) occupy 15.59%, 11.20% and 5.71% of the permanent pastures area, respectively.

Table 53: Percentage of Permanent Pastures area in each Vulnerability Level at Cordilheira Central MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	11.20
2. Low	0.00
3. Medium	15.59
4. High	67.50
5. Very high	5.71

Figure 53: Vulnerability Map for the Permanent Pastures of Cordilheira Central MRL

13 Maciço Noroeste MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Maciço Noroeste MRL, the focal value chain is Douro Wine, which relies on a LUS of vineyards (Table 54). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were changes in temperature and demographic changes and the two spatial explicit factors selected were internet connection quality and distance to schools and health centres.

Table 54: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Maciço Noroeste MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Vineyards	The Douro Superior includes in its total surface of vineyard (250 000 ha) two Designation of Origin (DO) Douro wine and Port wine. In the higher part of the area, agriculture is not intensive and there are vast areas non cultivated. Main crops are vineyard, olive groves, chestnuts, or almonds.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Changes in temperature	Refers to the increase in average temperatures, with an influence on the vegetative cycle of the vine and the cycles of pathogens and parasites. The increase in temperature allows the grapes to grow at altitude, where maturation occurs more slowly with the development of aromas, while maintaining acidity. A general anticipation of the vegetative cycle makes evident the positive effect of planting vines at higher altitudes in order to have a later harvest. The increase in temperature may interfere with the severity of certain pathogens (e.g., downy and powdery mildew). Earlier development of vegetation in spring increases the risk of frost damage.
Demographic changes	"Demographic change" refers to the depopulation of rural areas in the mountain region (low birth rate and increased emigration), ageing of the population and the abandonment of young people for lack of qualified job opportunities. The problem exists and is growing exponentially.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Internet connection quality	The availability of internet is a strategic asset that allow/not allow residents to keep on working in the area. Especially for qualified jobs, there is the option to live here and partial smart working (with companies elsewhere). Nowadays internet availability is very partial.
Distance to schools and health centres	The distance to schools and health centres are two determining factors in attracting people to live and work in the region.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for vineyards presented below (Figure 54). In areas without internet connection and with a distance to schools and health centres above 15 km, the vulnerability of vineyards to the drivers presented in Table 54 was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at areas with a good internet connection and, also, with a distance to schools and health centres up to 5 km, it was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 54: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Vineyards at Maciço Noroeste MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			<i>Internet connection quality</i>		
			<i>Not available</i>	<i>Bad</i>	<i>Good</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Distance to schools and health centres (km)</i>	<i>[0-5]</i>	4	3	1
		<i>]5-15]</i>	4	3	2
		<i>]15-max]</i>	5	4	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

14 Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL, the focal value chain is certified ecotourism, which relies on a mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland (Table 55). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were changes in land use and land cover, demographic changes and over exploitation of resources (forest) and the two spatial explicit factors selected were size of nearby urban centres and traveling time from nearby urban centres.

Table 55: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland	In Piatra Craiului - Zărnești region, certified ecotourism is most dependent on the mosaic landscape composed of forest and extensive semi-natural grassland. This mosaic landscape is affected by the changes in land use and changes in land cover.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Changes in land use and land cover	The main threat to Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL land use systems are the changes in land use and land cover. The main causes of these changes are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over-exploitation of forest and other local resources; - Abandonment of less accessible grasslands in the mountains and decline in traditional farming; - Chaotic development of leisure, recreation and tourism activities; - Poorly planned/controlled construction of tourist accommodation and holiday homes.
Demographic changes	Demographic changes are the second most important threat to the land use systems. Demographic changes are reflected in the depopulation of the local people, out-migration, especially during summer, and conflicts between the local people and business operators, and local people and tourists.
Over exploitation of resources (forest)	Over-exploitation of forest is reflected in the improper forest management in the area, which results in illegal exploitation of wood in the Piatra Craiului National Park and Natura 2000 sites.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Size of nearby urban centres	As mentioned in Southern Romanian Carpathians Policy Brief, one of the decisive factors in the variation of the system's vulnerability is the increasing number of visitors in the Piata Craiului National Park which puts pressure upon the local environment. The majority of the national tourists are coming from nearby urban centres, notably Brașov (553,000 population (National Institute of

	<p>Statistics, indicator POP105A) and Bucharest (1,800,000 population (National Institute of Statistics, indicator POP105A)). The on-going increase in the population of these urban centres ('growth poles') is putting further pressure upon the National Park.</p> <p>According to expert opinion, the two main urban centres from where the tourists come to visit the Piatra Craiului National Park are the urban 'growth' poles of Braşov (30 km travel distance) and Bucharest (180 km travel distance) (Benedek, J., 2016).</p>
<p>Traveling time from nearby urban centres</p>	<p>The visitor pressure on the National Park is related to the travelling time from nearby urban centres – which in turn is the product of distance and the speed of travel due to the quality of the transport infrastructure (roads and railways). Historically the transport infrastructure in Romania has been very poor but is improving rapidly. For example, the visitor pressure on Piatra Craiului National Park is currently constrained by the poor road infrastructure when travelling from Bucharest (Prahova Valley, from Bucharest to Piatra Craiului National Park). However, there are well-advanced plans to improve the infrastructure, and this will significantly reduce travelling time and potentially facilitate the movement of much larger numbers of tourists (including day trips) which will put the National Park under increasing pressure and negatively affect the region.</p>

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for the mosaic landscape presented below (Figure 55). The classes for size of nearby urban centres and travelling time from nearby urban centres were defined based on expert assessment. Mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland was classified with a vulnerability level of 5 (very high) when the size of nearby urban centres is above 750,000 inhabitants and the traveling time from nearby urban centres is up to 3 hours. On the contrary, it was classified with a vulnerability level of 1 (very low) when the size of nearby urban centres is up to 250,000 inhabitants and the traveling time is above 1 hour.

Figure 55: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Mosaic Landscape at Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Size of nearby urban centres (population)		
			<i>]0-250,000]</i>	<i>]250,000-750,000]</i>	<i>]750,000-max]</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Traveling time from nearby urban centres (h)</i>	<i>[0-1]</i>	2	4	5
		<i>]1-3]</i>	1	3	5
		<i>]3-max]</i>	1	4	4

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

15 Dinaric Mountains MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Dinaric Mountains MRL, the focal value chain is PDO Sienica lamb, which relies on a mosaic of cropland (extensive) and grassland with few livestock (Table 56). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were precipitation, temperature, and extreme weather events and the two spatial explicit factors selected were mean precipitation in Spring and Summer and distance to villages and water sources.

Table 56: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Dinaric Mountains MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Mosaic cropland (extensive) and grassland with few livestock	Pešter is situated within the Dinaric Mountains MRR in the municipality of Sjenica with some extensions to Novi Pazar and Tutin. The plateau is a large field/highland surrounded by high mountains. Altitudes of the plateau are between 900 and 1200 meters. Soil is mostly karst intermingled with pastures. Pasture management takes place through extensive grazing. The economy of the area relies primarily on animal breeding, mainly sheep. Pešter is famous for its dairy products, especially the Sjenica cheese, as well as lamb and prosciutto. The plateau is sparsely populated. Pešter is characteristic for its microclimate, which is particularly harsh in the winter months. Lowest temperatures during Winter time can go up to -35°C. Daily temperatures during summer have very wide amplitude – day temperatures can go up to 30°C, while night temperatures can be even around 0°C.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	The water supply through precipitation is one of a few top factors that influence the productivity and the quality of the pastures. The overall intensifying trend is a sum of increased variabilities in precipitation which result in more dry periods during the warmer/Summer season, and the increased overall quantity of rainfall are opposite. The months of May and June see the most rainfall which is strongly needed rain for grass production, while July and August are the driest. Due to precipitation shortage, 50% of the animal feed failed in the previous season.
Temperature	Temperature variability and climatic factors have always been an important feature of climate in Sjenica. Being one of the harshest regional specificities, the climate of the region is extreme mountainous and continental, with particular winter extremes. Nowadays there is a trend of earlier summer season (earlier by 10 days) and equally same (10 days) of later cold weather. The winters are not that harsh (the far minus up to minus 40 is typical for this region) while each summer there are tropical days (over 30 degrees); Overall, the average increase of temperature in the last 40 years has been around 1.5 degrees.

Extreme weather events	Spring hail, heat waves and storms are some of the extremes that note increased frequency. Still, the extreme events, though overall more present, are not that emphasized as one of the drivers affecting the variable. Winds that are contributing to soil erosion are also occasionally putting strong pressures on the production system. In addition to this, late Spring frosts can be seen as extreme events, since the vegetation is starting earlier due to the temperature increment, causing damage on the earlier grown grass and lower quantity and quality of grass at the beginning of grazing season.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Mean precipitation in Spring and Summer	Temporal mismatches in the distribution of precipitation in spring time may lead to water shortage, impeding the growth of grass, affecting its harvest and forcing to bring in fodder and water or to bring sheep where water is. This also applies to the summer months where due to high temperatures and waters shortages, water has to be brought in or the sheep need to be moved closer to water sources. These factors might have effects on land abandonment and can lead to land use change (April/May and June).
Distance to villages and water sources	Due to the lack of water sources because of spring time lack of precipitation and because of summer drought, sheep need to be moved closer to water sources, such as wells or water catchment areas, or water needs to be brought in. In periods of high temperatures, sheep also need shade and cooling which they find near trees, shrubs and other vegetation.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for mosaic cropland (extensive) and grassland with few livestock presented below (Figure 56). The classes for mean precipitation in Spring and Summer and distance to villages and water sources were established based on expert assessment. At areas where distance to villages and water sources is up to 3 km and with mean precipitation in Spring and Summer above 90 mm the vulnerability was considered very low (level 1). On the contrary, at areas where distance to villages and water sources is above 5 km and mean annual precipitation in Spring and Summer is up to 70 mm it was considered very high (level 5).

Figure 56: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Mosaic Cropland (extensive) and Grassland with Few Livestock at Dinaric Mountains MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			<i>Mean precipitation in Spring and Summer (mm)</i>		
			<i>[0-70]</i>	<i>[70-90]</i>	<i>[90-max]</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Distance to villages and water sources (km)</i>	<i>[0-3]</i>	3	2	1
		<i>]3-5]</i>	4	3	2
		<i>]5-max]</i>	5	4	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

16 Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL, the focal value chain is bio-honey, which relies on forests and grasslands (Table 57). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were land use changes, drought, and temperature fluctuations and the two spatial explicit factors selected were land cover types and distance from infrastructure.

Table 57: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Forests and grasslands	For bee pasture a landscape mosaic including grasslands (pastureland and meadows) and forests is the best. This combination of land-use systems allows bees to survive the whole year round.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Land use changes	"Land use changes" mean abandonment or management changes on grasslands. The abandonment of pastures and meadows starts the process of natural succession with changing plant composition, eventually leading to less diversity for bee pasture. Management changes occur mainly on meadows where the mulching is substituting mowing. The mulching physically destroys plants from their roots and as well as damages the pasturing bees.
Drought	"Drought" is a factor that describes precipitation-free periods that cause plants, soil, and air to dryness. Drought weakens plants, including their roots and their ability to draw nutrients from the soil. It also causes the predominance of drought-tolerant species and the eventual introduction of non-native species from warmer areas and the disappearance of some native nectar-bearing and pollen-bearing plants. The result is a less favourable species composition for bee grazing.
Temperature fluctuations	"Temperature fluctuations" mean irregular deviations from the average temperature in each season. The temperature fluctuations affect the time, length and frequency of flowering of plants. As a result, nectar and pollen production is damaged. Especially during winter, the month of February is often warmer than March. In autumn, the warm November associated with the flowering of some introduced plant species may disrupt the annual cycle of bees.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Land cover types	The land covers with higher diversity of pollen and nectar plants are better for bees' pasture.
Distance from infrastructure	The higher a distance from infrastructure, the less the environment is polluted, which is favourable for bio-quality production.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for forests and grasslands presented below (Figure 57). The classes for land cover types groups and distance from the infrastructure were defined based on expert assessment. At land cover classes of pastures, complex cultivation patterns and natural grasslands that are at distances from infrastructures above 1.5 km the vulnerability to land use changes, drought and temperature fluctuations was considered very low (level 1). At areas of industrial and commercial units, vulnerability was considered very high (level 5).

Figure 57 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Forests and Grasslands at Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1				
			Land cover types (CORINE land cover 2018 – level 3)				
			231, 242, 321	312, 313	311, 324	112, 211, 243	121
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Distance from the infrastructure (km)	[0-1.5]	2	3	4	4	5
]1.5-3]	1	2	3	4	5
]3-max]	1	2	3	3	5

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

(CORINE land cover 2018 – level 3 classes in order of appearance in the table: 231 – Pastures, 242 – Complex cultivation patterns, 321 – Natural grasslands, 312 – Coniferous forest, 313 – Mixed forest, 311 – Broad leaved-forest, 324 – Transitional woodland-shrub, 112 – Discontinuous urban fabric, 211 – Non-irrigated arable land, 243 – Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation, 121 – Industrial and commercial units)

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL, which is presented in Figure 58. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix – can be consulted in Appendix II. Taking into account the nature of the spatial explicit factor 1 and the fact that a) beekeepers can locate bee colonies practically anywhere where they have access and think it is good for bees, b) beekeepers can even sometimes migrate along a year with their bee colonies according to available pasture for the bees and c) the radius in which bees fly is usually between 3 km and 10 km from their hive location, the vulnerability map for this MRL covers its entire area.

More than half of the Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL area (55.58%) was classified with vulnerability level 2 (low) (Table 58). The areas classified with vulnerability levels 3 (medium) and 4 (high) occupy 27.72% and 14.17% of the MRL, respectively.

Figure 58: Vulnerability Map for the Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL

Table 58: Percentage of Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL area classified in each Vulnerability Level

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	2.29
2. Low	55.58
3. Medium	27.72
4. High	14.17
5. Very high	0.24

17 Betic Systems MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Betic Systems MRL, the focal value chain is organic mountain olive oil, which relies on a LUS of organic olive groves (Table 59). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were reduction and change of precipitation regime and socio-demographic changes and the two spatial explicit factors selected were slope and elevation.

Table 59 : Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Betic Systems MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Organic olive groves	In the Betic Systems, the traditional non-mechanisable olive grove is an important social and economic asset, a landscape shaper, which is facing various problems that threaten its sustainability. In recent decades, organic production has emerged as a strategy that can help to reduce its vulnerability and make it more resilient to climate change and other drives of change.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Reduction and change of precipitation regime	The reduction, but above all the change in the rainfall pattern, which is scarcer and later in the autumn season, has a negative effect on the fruit ripening process, reducing the quantity and quality of production, which has a negative impact on the loss-making economic balance of this agro-system.
Socio-demographic changes	The loss of the active population together with the lack of generational renewal hinders the continuity of the traditional management of these olive groves as well as the availability of labour and therefore the very survival of the cultivation system.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Slope	Slopes are a critical factor in the management of highland olive groves. Above 20% in particular, olive grove management becomes more difficult, and critically so when the slopes are steeper than 30%. In such cases, mechanisation is not very effective.
Elevation	The influence of altitude is not so clear-cut, but it is evident that the higher the altitude, the more complicated accessibility becomes, the longer the journey times, and there is a certain abandonment of olive grove plots above 600-700 m in the municipality of Zuheros. On the other hand, reduced rainfall or extreme heat events may be better supported by olive groves located at higher altitudes.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for organic olive groves presented below (Figure 59). At elevations above 600 m with slopes over 20% the vulnerability of organic olive groves to reduction and changes in precipitation regime and socio-demographic changes was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at elevations up to 600 m with slopes up to 10% the vulnerability was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 59 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Organic Olive Groves at Betic Systems MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Slope (%)		
			[0-10]]10-20]]20-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Elevation (m)	[0-600]	1	3	4
]600-max]	2	4	5

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map at Betic Systems MRL, which is presented in Figure 60. However, the vulnerability map has an important limitation because vulnerability levels should be restricted to the areas of organic olive groves and not to all types of olive groves present in the MRL, as presented in Figure 60. In fact, a spatial dataset with the limits of organic olive groves, which represent about 5% to 10% of all olive groves in the MRL, was not available. Therefore, the vulnerability map presented here should be interpreted carefully, since vulnerability levels represented should only be taken into consideration for the areas where organic olive groves are known to be present.

The auxiliary maps used to build the vulnerability map – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the olive groves area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Figure 60: Vulnerability Map for the Organic Olive Groves of Betic Systems MRL

18 Sierra Morena MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Sierra Morena MRL, the focal value chain is Los Pedroches PDO Iberian ham (*jamón ibérico*), which relies on an agro-silvo-pastoral system called *dehesa* (Table 60). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were precipitation, extreme events and pest and diseases and the two spatial explicit factors selected were precipitation and tree cover density.

Table 60 : Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Sierra Morena MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Dehesa	<p>The <i>dehesa</i> is an agro-silvo-pastoral system where the historical relationship of human beings with their environment has created an open forest landscape where <i>Quercus</i> species (usually holm oaks, but also cork oaks, and gall oaks) coexist with crops or pastures.</p> <p>The MRL is located in the region of Los Pedroches (Cordoba, Spain), covering more specifically the three municipalities of Villanueva de Cordoba, Pozoblanco, and Cardeña. From a geological point of view, this area has a constant presence of plutonic rocks (granodiorites and granites), which usually outcrop igneous bodies, although quartzite and slate are abundant to the north and south of the sector. As a result, erosion is low, which does not, however, imply good soil quality.</p>
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	Drought causes water stress and weakening of the trees. Autumn rains are very important as this is when the acorns gain weight. Also, for the pasture, as it helps it to germinate. Drought in spring causes less flower setting, less flower production and therefore less acorn production. It also causes the pastures to be of poorer quality. There is a gradient between the Pozoblanco area with less rainfall and Venta del Charco (Cardeña) with more rainfall. This driver will be more relevant in the arid areas of the MRL.
Extreme events	Although there were several components described in this driver such as late frosts, heat waves and hails, here we concentrate on heat waves that can cause acorn abortion (unripe acorns fall off). Heat waves importance might have a synergistic effect with reduction of precipitation, particularly in arid areas.
Pest and diseases	<p>This driver is expressed in this case study as pests and diseases that cause weakening and death of trees. The two main agents considered are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>: It is favoured by the weakening of trees caused by drought (in places like Cardeña, with higher rainfall and the same soil it does not affect so much). - <i>Cerambix</i> spp.: Attacks dead wood, e.g., by bad pods or old trees. It is more common and widespread in old oaks, represented mostly in low tree cover areas.

Spatial Explicit Factors	
Precipitation	This factor is directly related to the three drivers mentioned as drought, heat waves and diseases will impact more in areas with lower rainfall (under more stress). Categories have been calculated based on the full gradient of rainfall of the MRL (looking at the map). The lower limit is close to the holm oak tolerance (>450-500)
Tree cover density	Drought and pest/diseases increase mortality and thus reduce tree density. The dehesa system is based on an open forest type with moderate tree cover. Areas with very low density have the risk of becoming pasture and with too much density of becoming close forest. In these two contrasting situations the provision of acorns and pasture together is compromised. Thus, we are looking at a non-linear relation between tree density and vulnerability.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for the dehesas of Sierra Morena MRL presented below (Figure 61). The classes for mean annual precipitation and tree cover density were defined based on expert assessment. The vulnerability of dehesas, to the drivers identified above, was considered very high (level 5) for areas with tree cover densities up to 20% where mean annual precipitation is up to 600 mm. On the contrary, dehesas were classified as having very low vulnerability (level 1) when tree cover density is between 20% and 40% and mean annual precipitation is above 700 mm.

Figure 61: Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Dehesa at Sierra Morena MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Mean annual precipitation (mm)		
]0-600]]600-700]]700-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Tree cover density (%)]0-20]	5	4	3
]20-40]	3	2	1
]40-100]	3	2	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the dehesas of Sierra Morena MRL, which is presented in Figure 62. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

About half of the dehesas in MRL19 were classified with a vulnerability level of 2 (low) 49.14%, (Table 61). Vulnerability level 3 (medium) and 1 (very low) occupy 20.98% and 16.33% of the dehesa MRL area, respectively. Higher levels of vulnerability are those which represent less area, namely, levels 4 (high) and 5 (very high) classify 8.46% and 5.09% of the dehesas MRL extent, respectively.

Figure 62: Vulnerability Map for the Dehesas of Sierra Morena MRL

Table 61: Percentage of Dehesa area in each Vulnerability Level at Sierra Morena MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	16.33
2. Low	49.14
3. Medium	20.98
4. High	8.46
5. Very high	5.09

19 Spanish Pyrenees MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Spanish Pyrenees MRL, the focal value chain is mountain wine, which relies on a LUS of vineyards (Table 62). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were temperature and extreme events and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation and slope.

Table 62 : Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Spanish Pyrenees MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Vineyards	The area is quite depopulated and agriculture lost its relevance, nevertheless, in more recent years, there has been a recovery of old vineyards and planting of new ones, based on local varieties and ecological management methods.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Temperature	It refers to the increase in average temperatures, especially in the intermediate seasons (spring and autumn) with a potential (but also already concrete) influence on the vegetative cycle of the vineyard and the cycles of pathogens and parasites. Increasing temperature allows grapes to grow at altitude, where ripening takes place more slowly with the development of aromas, while maintaining acidity. A general anticipation of the vegetative cycle makes evident the positive effect of planting vineyards in higher altitudes in order to have a later harvest. Increasing temperature can interfere with the severity of certain pathogens (e.g., downy mildew). The earlier development of vegetation in spring increases the risk of frost damage.
Extreme events	It refers to rainstorms, hail and late frost. All 3 phenomena are increasing in terms of frequency and damage the grape production in different moments of the year.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation	The negative impact of increasing temperatures is more evident on lower altitudes in the valley. On higher altitudes the temperature never reaches extreme parameters and vineyards located there avoid the risks related with this driver. Late frost tends to bring more damage in lower located vineyards, saving those in higher zones.
Slope	The inclination of the slope is also a factor which can determine the risk of frost damage: the risk is higher on flat land and lower in hilly areas.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for vineyards at Spanish Pyrenees MRL presented below (Figure 63). The classes for elevation and slope were established based on expert assessment. At elevations up to 500 m with slopes above 10%, the vulnerability of vineyards to temperature and extreme events was considered very high (level 5).

As elevation and slope decrease, the vulnerability was also considered to decrease, reaching the minimum level (1 - very low) at elevations above 800 m with slopes up to 10%.

Figure 63 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Vineyards at Spanish Pyrenees MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Elevation (m)		
			[0-500]]50-800]]800-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Slope (%)	[0-10]	4	2	1
]10-max]	5	3	2

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map at Spanish Pyrenees MRL, which is presented in Figure 64. However, the vulnerability map has an important limitation because vulnerability levels should be restricted to the areas of vineyards. In fact, it was not possible to obtain a spatial dataset with the limits of vineyards. Therefore, the vulnerability map presented here should be interpreted carefully, since vulnerability levels represented should only be taken into consideration for the areas where vineyards are known to be present. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Figure 64: Vulnerability Map for the Vineyards of Spanish Pyrenees MRL

20 Swiss Alps MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Swiss Alps MRL, the focal value chain is mountain grain, which relies on a LUS extensive cropland (Table 63). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were precipitation, extreme events/weather extremes and temperature and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation and precipitation in summer.

Table 63 : Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Swiss Alps MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Extensive cropland	Organic cereal production in the mountain zone was considered. It is done in a mixed system where the main land use system is actually pasture, for milk or beef. Cropland is marginal.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	The timing of rain (or snow and hail) is much more important for yield than the amount. Too much or too little rainfall during the main growth phase of cereal crops has a major impact. Producers perceive the total amount of rainfall as more or less unchanged, but the intensity and regularity of rain has changed drastically, making it difficult to rely on empirical values for yield planning. Heavy rain or drought are more common, but unpredictable and the main problem.
Extreme events/Weather extremes	The extreme weather events relevant to yields mainly concern precipitation: Heavy rain or drought, snow too early or too late, but also frost. Here, too, the timing is crucial; events in winter have no influence on yield. The intensity and irregularity of the weather is the main problem. This driver and the driver of precipitation have often been understood together.
Temperature	Average temperatures in the main growth phase are most important for yields, while long periods of extreme temperatures have the greatest impact on yields. In their most extreme form, these are drought and frost. Temperature is not yet seen as a major problem for yield, more growing days are welcomed, and heat waves are not yet a problem.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation	This factor is mainly related to temperature and related weather extremes. So far areas at higher altitudes have experienced lower temperatures overall but are now experiencing bigger changes.
Summer precipitation	Drivers related to precipitation are very variable depending in which valley etc. a farm is located, some places are protected from wind by a mountain range, others are completely exposed. The effect of too little or too much precipitation is very complex and depends on slope, soil type, elevation, season, etc. It is very difficult to generalize.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for extensive cropland presented below (Figure 65). The classes for elevation were defined based on farmers' positions and the classes for precipitation in Summer were established based on expert assessment. At elevations up to 900 m with too little precipitation in summer and at elevations above 1200 m with too much precipitation in summer, the vulnerability of extensive cropland to precipitation, extreme events/weather extremes and temperature was considered very high (level 5). Extensive croplands were classified with a very low (level 1) vulnerability level in areas with elevations up to 900 m and, with at the same time, optimal amount of precipitation in summer.

Figure 65 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Extensive Cropland at Swiss Alps MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			<i>Elevation (m)</i>		
			<i>[0-900]</i>	<i>]900-1200]</i>	<i>]1200-max]</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Precipitation in summer (mid-June to mid-September)</i>	<i>Too much</i>	3	3	5
		<i>Optimal amount</i>	1	2	3
		<i>Too little</i>	5	4	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

21 Swiss Jura MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Swiss Jura MRL, the focal value chain is Tête de Moine PDO cheese, which relies on a LUS of permanent pastures (Table 64). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were precipitation, temperature and extreme events and the two spatial explicit factors selected were elevation and tree cover density.

Table 64 : Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Swiss Jura MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Permanent pastures	The geographical area defined by the Tête de Moine PDO cheese specification is essentially made up of pastures (from 415 m to 1606 m). These areas are divided into communal wooded pastures; permanent communal grazed meadows; permanent private grazed pastures; temporary meadows mown for fodder.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Precipitation	The rainfall regime is impacted by climate change (more frequent anticyclones). Snow is also less abundant. Following an altitudinal gradient, the phenomenon is less marked. But everywhere the lack of rainfall has a direct impact on grass growth.
Temperature	The average temperature tends to increase. There are more sunny days, especially in summer, which can lead to a slowdown in grass growth (evapotranspiration), in a context of shallow, calcareous (karstic) soils.
Extreme events	Droughts are the most relevant driver. Droughts can lead to significant forage losses. These phenomena seem to be more frequent and prolonged. Hail is also an extreme problematic event as it can negatively affect the quality of the forage.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Elevation	The summering pastures areas ("estivages") are interesting in dry years. Their higher altitude relieves the pressure on lowland pastures which are subject to heat waves and a halt in grass production in summer. For example, in the summer of 2003 and spring of 2011, droughts caused a 40% decrease in annual yield on pastures in the lowlands of the Jura. Finally, droughts make it increasingly difficult to establish and maintain the botanical balance of temporary grasslands, notably on lowlands (< 600 m).
Tree cover density	<p>The fine mosaic structure of wooded pastures significantly reduces the effect of drought on forage production. The conservation of a semi-open landscape with trees would allow farmers to mitigate the negative effects of climate change on forage production and stabilise yields. Assuming an increase in the frequency of dry years, wooded pastures have the potential to reduce the economic risk associated with large fluctuations in the amount of available grass, which would force farmers to buy supplementary fodder.</p> <p>Description of the classes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-wooded pasture: intensive to semi-intensive pasture, almost without trees and generally without shrubs. Tree cover density $\leq 1\%$. - Lightly wooded pasture, with fine texture: intensive to extensive wooded pasture. Mostly isolated trees. Tree cover density between 1% and 20%. - Very wooded, coarse-textured pasture: semi-intensive to extensive wooded pasture, with trees grouped in groves separated by a network of "chambers" (grazed meadows, thin lawns). Tree cover density between 20% and 70%. - Grazed woodland: generally, very extensive, almost devoid of grazed meadows and rough grassland. Tree cover density $\geq 70\%$.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures presented below (Figure 66). The classes for elevation were defined based on Mosimann et al. (2017) and Meisser et al. (2016). Tree cover density were defined based on Buttler et al. (2012) and Barbezat and Boquet (2008). At elevations up to 600 m with a tree cover density up to 1% the vulnerability of permanent pastures to the drivers identified above was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at elevations above 950 m with a tree cover density above 70% it was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 66 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Permanent Pastures at Swiss Jura MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Elevation (m)		
			[0-600]]600-950]]950-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Tree cover density (%)]70-100]	2	2	1
]20-70]	3	2	2
]1-20]	4	3	2
		[0-1]	5	4	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the permanent pastures of Swiss Jura MRL, which is presented in Figure 67. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Most permanent pasture area was classified with a vulnerability level of 3 (medium) 57.55%, (Table 65). Vulnerability levels 4 (high) and 2 (low) occupy 21.60% and 13.11% of the permanent pastures area, respectively.

Figure 67: Vulnerability Map for the Permanent Pastures of Swiss Jura MRL

Table 65: Percentage of Permanent Pastures area in each Vulnerability Level at Swiss Jura MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	6.31
2. Low	13.11
3. Medium	57.55
4. High	21.60
5. Very high	1.43

22 Beydaglari MRL - Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

At Beydaglari MRL, the focal value chain is greenhouse tomato, which relies on a LUS of intensive/irrigated annual crop (Table 66). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this LUS, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were over-exploitation of resources and precipitation and the two spatial explicit factors selected were slope and precipitation.

Table 66 : Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Beydaglari MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Intensive and irrigated annual crop	In recent years, highland greenhouse vegetable production has increased in the region. This expansion affects overexploitation of water and land resources. This threatens sustainable production.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Over-exploitation of resources	Overextraction of groundwater. Groundwater level is decreasing due to unconscious use of groundwater.
Precipitation	It was emphasized that the decrease in precipitation creates a problem in accessing the water required for irrigation. The problem of access to irrigation water causes a decrease in tomato yield.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Slope	Drought effects occurs first in the area which has higher slopes.
Precipitation	Drought increased due to decreased precipitation. Therefore, problems arose in accessing sufficient irrigation water.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for intensive/irrigated annual crop of tomato presented below (Figure 68). The classes for slope were defined based on expert assessment. At slopes above 20% with a precipitation up to 500 mm the vulnerability level of the LUS was considered very high (level 5). On the contrary, at slopes up to 10% with a precipitation above 500 mm, it was considered very low (level 1).

Figure 68 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Intensive/Irrigated Annual Crop of Tomato at Beydaglari MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			Slope (%)		
			[0-10]]10-20]]20-max]
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	Precipitation (mm)	[0-500]	3	4	5
]500-max]	1	2	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The previous spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for intensive/irrigated annual crop of tomato at Beydaglari MRL, which is presented in Figure 69. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II.

Vulnerability level 1 (very low) and 3 (medium) occupy 87.91% and 9.07% of the intensive/irrigated annual crop of tomato at Beydaglari MRL, respectively (Table 67).

Figure 69: Vulnerability Map for Intensive/Irrigated Annual Crop of Tomato at Beydaglari MRL

Table 67: Percentage of Intensive/Irrigated Annual Crop of Tomato area in each Vulnerability Level at Beydaglari MRL

Vulnerability level	LUS area (%)
1. Very low	87.91
2. Low	2.52
3. Medium	9.07
4. High	0.49
5. Very high	0.01

23 Speyside MRL – Spatial Vulnerability Matrix and Vulnerability Map

A. Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

For the Speyside MRL, the focal value chain is Speyside malt whisky, which relies on the quality and quantity of water available, which in turn is an outcome of a mainly extensive rangeland LUS (Table 68). To produce the spatial vulnerability matrix for this focal value chain, the vulnerability drivers considered by the respective regional MOVING team were rainfall per sub-catchment and water demand per sub-catchment and the two spatial explicit factors selected were water supply per sub-catchment and water demand per sub-catchment.

Table 68: Land use system, vulnerability drivers and spatial explicit factors selected for Speyside MRL spatial vulnerability matrix production

Land Use System	
Extensive rangelands	Distilleries use water from ground and surface waters that are influenced by all land uses in the associated sub-catchment.
Vulnerability Drivers	
Rainfall per sub-catchment	Input to the water supply - few transfers to other catchments - locally significant. Spatial variation is substantial SW (high) to NE (low) and sub-catchments can be small. Distilleries link to single sub-catchments.
Water demand per sub-catchment	As a proxy for the water used by distilling (process and cooling) the alcohol production volumes are used. This means the water use per litre of production is assumed to be the same and we will not take account of other demands in the sub-catchment. It is therefore indicative.
Spatial Explicit Factors	
Water supply per sub-catchment	Blue water inputs to the sub-catchments (rainfall x area) to give an order of magnitude estimate of surface water resources available. Ground water is used but natural transfers between surface water are unquantified.
Water demand per sub-catchment	Demand for surface waters for distilleries. Further analysis to get full vulnerability would also consider other users – households, agriculture etc.

According to these, the regional MOVING team built the spatial vulnerability matrix for extensive rangelands presented below (Figure 70). When water supply per sub-catchment is high and demand is low vulnerability was considered very low (level 1). On the contrary, when water supply per sub-catchment is low and water demand is high, it was considered very high (level 5).

Figure 70 : Spatial Vulnerability Matrix for Extensive Rangelands of Speyside MRL

Spatial Vulnerability Matrix			Spatial Explicit Factor 1		
			<i>Water supply per sub-catchment</i>		
			<i>Low</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>High</i>
Spatial Explicit Factor 2	<i>Water demand per sub-catchment</i>	<i>Low</i>	3	2	1
		<i>Medium</i>	4	3	2
		<i>High</i>	5	4	3

Vulnerability levels: 1 – very low, 2 – low, 3 – medium, 4- high, 5 – very high.

B. Vulnerability Map

The spatial vulnerability matrix allowed the construction of a vulnerability map for the Speyside MRL sub-catchments where the water is used for distilling processes, this is presented in Figure 71. The auxiliary maps used to build it – 1 per each spatial explicit factor, with the classes defined in the matrix, and 1 with the land use system area – can be consulted in Appendix II. The map highlights both where single distilleries may be making more substantial demands on more limited water resources (via combinations of catchment size and rainfall) but also where concentrations distilleries or a series of distilleries across a catchment may in aggregate have greater vulnerability (potentially requiring more coordination/cooperation in future water use). The analysis while based on average conditions could be extended to individual years in the historic record where there were known to be issues of supply and to use these rainfall levels as benchmarks for analysis for future climate scenarios.

Figure 71: Vulnerability Map for Speyside MRL

7. Conclusions

The main objective of WP3 – Development of visual science-society-policy interface tools in MOVING is to provide an in-depth understanding of the drivers and effects of changes in mountain areas, and provide susceptibility and vulnerability data and interface tools, ready to be used by citizens and experts in the reference regions. Thus, the work delivered in this WP will be a key input for the rest of the project, particularly for WP4 and WP6. Specifically, this Deliverable reports the key findings related to susceptibility and vulnerability of the 23 mountain regions considered in the project, summarizing the work carried out in T3.2, T3.3 and T3.4.

This Deliverable gathers the results of an extensive and detailed participatory work and provides relevant and novel insights into the vulnerability of mountain regions in Europe. The methodology implemented considered a wide range of tools (survey, interviews, workshops, GIS, mapping, and desk study) that were applied in a short period of time and in parallel to the creation of the MAPs. On top of this complexity, the peak of fieldwork and participatory activities overlapped with the COVID-19 restrictions all over Europe. This context was a clear challenge for the project implementation across 23 regions in Europe. However, the excellent work of partners and the active engagement of task leaders facilitated the completion of the mentioned tasks and ultimately the obtention of relevant insights for the project. For each MRL, existing information was mobilised, and stakeholders' knowledge was collected and organised. The combination of both sources of data provides a very detailed picture of the processes ongoing in the MRLs under analysis. This approach includes processes which occur at a global scale, such as climate change, and analyses the way they directly affect the MRLs under study. But also, other processes which are expressed locally as wildfires and invasive species and processes of a socio-economic nature, such as depopulation and land abandonment or changes in land use systems, which affect in particular each MRL.

The vulnerability matrices developed for the 23 MRL is the most comprehensive analysis of vulnerability of mountain land-use systems in Europe done up to today. Through active engagement of more than 500 stakeholders across mountain regions in Europe, MOVING has managed to obtain the perception of farmers, managers, extension officers and researchers on the relevance of drivers of change, shaping the vulnerability of the systems. We found similarities across European mountains with some drivers such as temperature scoring high in the ranking of most case studies and demographic changes as a key driver affecting the sensitivity of most MRLs. Interestingly, the stakeholders did not perceive pollution and wildfire as relevant drivers. Stakeholders did not perceive that adaptative mechanisms could be significant to reduce these impacts. Conversely, non-climatic drivers were perceived to be more effectively reduced by the mechanisms of adaptation suggested by participants (assuming full implementation). Specifically, the driver "land-use and land-cover change" showed the strongest reduction capacity based on the mechanisms listed.

The Spatial Vulnerability Matrix as well as the resulting maps work as a synthesis of the vulnerability analysis undertaken on beforehand with data sources and stakeholders' consultation. What results have made clear is that the drivers of change, which mostly affect and

will affect in the near future the MRLs and the resource basis for the value chains selected, are specific for each MRL. Furthermore, in many cases vulnerability derives from a combination of different types of drivers, natural and socio-economic, global and local, and often, these drivers reinforce each other. And as such, being able to understand in detail the estimated impacts of climate change in their specific regions have been relevant for the stakeholders involved and made them aware of the challenges their regions would face in a short and medium time frame. It has also boosted a renewed awareness for the other drivers of change and their interplay with the climate change drivers.

7.1. Learning and challenges from the participatory process

The results reported in this deliverable are the outcome of an intensive participatory process carried out across the 23 regions included in the project. Some of the main learnings and challenges listed by the partners in each region after implementing the full participatory methodology are:

- The understanding of the scientific terms used in this project, the spatial information provided by the team, as well as all the indicators produced using large-scale databases, were not always easy to understand by all the stakeholders. The role of the MOVING team in each MRL has been crucial here. A key learnt lesson from this WP is that processing and transferring technical knowledge, in formats such as indicators and maps, requires resources and time to make it explicit for a wide range of stakeholders. But the full implementation of our transdisciplinary methodology showed that cross-fertilisation of information and knowledge sources results in more substantial and contextualised knowledge that can help to address current and future challenges.
- Another outcome of the methodology implemented in WP3 was the interaction and increased share of knowledge among stakeholders. By gathering different actors related to the management of endogenous resources and to the mountain VC selected, MOVING has contributed to engage stakeholders in a dialogue, which otherwise would probably not have been fostered. In some cases, stakeholders knew well each other, but in other cases, there were stakeholders from the same MRL who had not met before the MOVING project organised participatory discussions. We consider this novel interaction as a positive and relevant outcome, not only for the MOVING local MAP along the project itself but also for the benefit of a shared discussion and vision for the future of each of the MRLs considered.
- Due to COVID-19 restrictions partners had experienced frequent problems in accessing stakeholders. Thus, some workshops or interviews had to be done online. The online work requested more facilitation and more time and resources to be developed. Once restrictions were released, the teams valued very positively being able to move from on-line to face-to-face format, because the bonds and conversations that are generated can be deeper.
- The methodology proposed to construct the vulnerability matrix per region was built in close collaboration with all partners in order to acknowledge the complexities of each study

case. Bearing in mind the information that had to be collected per region and the need of cross-comparison certain flexibility was accepted across regions. Most common changes included modifications in the calendar of activities to avoid intense workload periods for farmers (e.g. harvesting periods), or combination of activities (e.g. questionnaire with workshops).

- During the participatory process, the relevance of gathering knowledge directly from the stakeholders was evident due to their practical and experience-based understanding of the system. However, some participants felt not knowledgeable enough to answer, particularly if the group included participants of other profiles that traditionally hold the technical knowledge (i.e. research and technicians). Facilitators from the regional teams encouraged wide participation across the distinct profiles, actively listening to them and recognising the value of their knowledge and opinions.
- A great challenge in this WP has been to produce a relevant and novel academic work and at the same time to make the outcomes useful for the mountain areas and local stakeholders. Through active participation and listening, the project has tried to meet both criteria. If this linkage is not achieved, the stakeholders do not see the usefulness of the project, while if it is achieved, very interesting synergies and engagement can be generated. We foresee that this work will continue in the next WP and in the dissemination of the activities summarised in this deliverable.

7.2. Perspectives for linking the spatial and the value chain analysis

With the knowledge processed and produced in the T3.1., T3.2., T3.3. and T3.4. for each MRL there is now a rather complete set of insight into how the MRL area is changing, why it is changing, the relevance of different drivers in the near future, the ones that might lead to more radical changes, and finally which ones could be faced through active adaptation mechanisms by the stakeholders.

This is a strong basis to assess which challenges would be faced by the value chain selected in the near future in each MRL, specifically in the production phase. The outcomes highlight how the whole value chain would be affected, if the conditions for the crop, forest or livestock production change in the MRL due to the drivers affecting the land use system and the system's vulnerability to such changes.

Finally, the results of WP3 will make it possible to assess how the changes in the value chain may affect, reinforcing or minimising the effects of the drivers of change identified. The adaption mechanisms analysed in WP3, are particularly relevant to inform this feedback across scales. In WP4, when discussing with value chain actors how the value chain is working and which threats and opportunities it is facing in the future, the knowledge from WP3 will be integrated in the evidence basis for the discussion. Hopefully, this evidence will bring insights which are new and enlightening for the stakeholders. The methodological challenge is to integrate both types of data

and evidence, from the value chain to the land use system and from the land use system to the value chain. We foresee that the WP3 & WP4 integrations will lead to enhance the resilience and sustainability analysis of the European mountain regions.

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9. Appendix I (T3.3): Region reports of Participatory Vulnerability Analysis.

The vulnerability analysis reports of the regions include the following content:

- Context: Study case, Value Chain name, Land-use system name and description, and name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain.
- Drivers' description and components
- Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Legend to the infographics and vulnerability matrix

01 - Austrian Alps MRL. Austria

Context

Study case: Sheep farming in the region of Weiz

Value Chain name: Lamb from the region of Weiz

Land-use system name: Extensive open range low land meadows and highland pastures

Photo 72. Flock of grazing sheep in Almenland

Source: S. Karner

Photo 73. Ewes to lamb in stall in Gnaas

Source: D. Steinwender

Figure 74 Land use system map of the region of Weiz

Source: MOVING Project (WP3) according to Asselen and Verburg (2012)

Short Description land-use system

The Berglandregion Weiz is characterised by alpine semi-open pasture landscape (low mountain range region). The main area of the mountainous region is used for forestry, and the proportion of arable land is subordinate. Around a third of the use is made up of grassland cultivation, the use for alpine pastures (according to the land use cadastre around 2040 hectares) takes up 6% of the area. Pasturing is historically dominated by cattle in this area, but sheep are becoming increasingly popular in that region. Most of the 185 alpine pastures are single alpine pastures (158), 10 communal alpine pastures and 17 agricultural communities.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain:

Quality of pasture and linkage to the lamb production. The reference variable for the vulnerability analysis is “quality of pasture and grassland”. We started with a focus on the pasture land, but during the interviews it turned out that grassland for the production of winter feed (grass silage, hay, hay silage) or as temporary meadows is of high importance as well. The reference variable was chosen as it represents the main forage resources and the most relevant cost factor in sheep farming (50-60% of production costs). The sheep are in the pastures from spring to autumn, and low pasture quality in terms of quantity and quality (e.g. reduced nutritional value, less protein and energy content of the grass due to lignification of grasses) negatively impacts the yield. Pasture grass is the cheapest feed per unit of protein. The winter feed is produced by all sheep farmers in that region on their own farms. If this cannot be done in sufficient quantity and in good quality, feed has to be bought in, which constitutes a considerable additional cost factor. This is only done in exceptional cases because that additional costs for feed would make the business not profitable anymore.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 69 Driver description and components for Austrian Alps MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. Change in precipitation pattern in the region is characterized by less but heavier rainfall and longer dry periods in summer, as well as increasing rainfall in winter instead of snow. This fact has a negative effect on the water balance (bodies of water and groundwater reservoirs), as well as the soil and vegetation of the pasture and grass land areas. Particularly in combination with heat waves, longer dry spells do not only reduce the grazing forage yield (quantity), but also have negative impacts on the quality of pasture areas, especially in sun-exposed and south-facing locations.
Temperature	The increase in mean temperature, seasonal or annual (changes in average, maximum and minimum temperatures included), causes a prolonged growing season. This increases the productivity of pastures and grass land. On the other hand, a prolonged vegetation period has negative effects on the quality of the grazing land due to overuse and a shortened plant regeneration period. Due to a longer vegetation period, plant pests might spread better, which has a negative effect on the quality of the pasture plants; disease-transmitting insects and (endo) parasites can spread better, which has a negative impact on animal health. E.g., midges as carriers of bluetongue disease or causes of skin eczema.
Extreme events	Extreme events consider changes in intensity, frequency, or timing for the following components: heat waves, heavy rain, (thunder) storms, hail and frost periods. The occurrence of heat waves has a negative effect on the quality of pasture areas, especially exposed south-facing slopes, and on winter feed. Heavy rain events coming along with storms (and hail) cause damage to the soil (loss of humus, landslides, mudslides) and plants. This poses a problem for the stability of the pasture areas and the network of paths.
Wildfire	On the one hand, wildfires could result in more open rangeland, but as there is not much need of increasing these areas, wildfires represent a threat for the farms in that region. That's because many sheep farms operate forestry as well.
Pollution	Pollution is basically not a problem on pastures and alpine meadows in Weiz. However, some people fertilise their pastures to increase the yield by mowing.
Pests, diseases and invasive species	Invasive species: The spread of invasive plant species, which also enter higher altitudes, is due to the vulnerability of native plants because of the rise in temperature and drought (not drought or heat-adapted). As sheep are very sensitive regarding their forage base, it depends on the breed which neophytes they tolerate. The breeds of the Weizer sheep farmers are rather sensitive and would thus not have an ideal forage base.

	<p>Pest: Another problem is the spread of parasites. These thrive especially well when it is humid. Sheep are susceptible to endoparasites such as gastrointestinal lungworm, liver fluke (via the dwarf mud snail as host), which thrive primarily in moist places. The Bluetongue disease is transmitted by gnats (a type of mosquito) that occur at higher altitudes when the temperatures are rising.</p>
<p>Over-exploitation of resources</p>	<p>Overgrazing: Basically, overuse is not a problem in the Weizer Bergland. The livestock density on pastures is low, and there is rather an under-use problem of many pastures leading to weediness, bush encroachment, and forestation of pastures.</p> <p>Overuse water: At certain places there is water scarcity in summer, when there are long dry periods (drought), causing the groundwater level to drop. Here, some farms already have water problems (in higher locations). With the decline in snow cover and soil humidity, this could also become a problem in the spring.</p>
<p>Demographic changes</p>	<p>Like in other rural areas, there is a decrease in population due to emigration and a drop in the birth rate, but this does not seem to impact sheep farming in that region. Due to the small-scale structure of agriculture and its high proportion of sideline work, many farms have been able to survive. Sheep farming is still a niche, but continuously growing. For young generations taking over farms, a shift from cattle to sheep husbandry is attractive: less investment in infrastructure, easier for physically "weaker" people (often women), sheep can be kept more flexibly in terms of time (but to the same extent) as cattle (comparison only possible if the same usage, e.g., keeping dairy sheep with dairy cows), which makes their keeping on a side-line job base attractive. Therefore, there are also newcomers and lateral entrants opting for sheep.</p>
<p>Soil physical degradation</p>	<p>Heavy rain events coming along with storms (and hail) cause damage to the soil (loss of humus, landslides, mudslides) and plants. This poses a problem for the stability of the pasture areas and the network of paths.</p> <p>Sheep are clearly better than the traditional cattle husbandry due to their weight, stepping and grazing behaviour - they stimulate stronger rooting of the plants and biodiversity. Cattle are much heavier, eat the grass only roughly and trample over the entire area, which leads to soil compaction. At the same time, the stepping of cattle causes grass swards, which in turn leads to erosion. This effect is intensified by drought as a result of heat and little precipitation. The use of tractors for mowing has the same effect due to soil compaction. Some meadows are even so fertilised that they are mown up to 5 times a year - normal is 2 to 3 times.</p>
<p>Land-use and land-cover change</p>	<p>Land use changes: Caused by the switch of cattle farms to indoor stock farming, and by the abandonment of farms, land use changes in the Weizer Bergland are characterized by a reduction in grazed areas and an increase of fallow land.</p> <p>Change to sheep: Caused by the switch from cattle to sheep farming</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 75 Infographic of results Austrian Alps MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: Precipitation was considered as the most important driver in regard to the quantity and quality of forage yield from pastures and grassland. There was only one respondent, who had ranked it very low (no explanation why available), while all other ranked it very relevant. For none of the drivers the given answers were strikingly controversial.

As wolves are not yet relevant in the case study area (there are only some golden jackals, which are not protected, thus hunted), we did not explicitly address that topic in the questionnaire. Moreover, the number of sheep attacked by wolves is very low throughout Austria (approx. 14% of the sheep that die in average on alpine pastures). However, the topic was still addressed by participants during the workshop: on the one hand it is discussed very emotionally (involving unsolvable conflicts of interest between husbandry and wildlife conservation), on the other hand it might have severe implications on pasture farming: some participants envisaged a considerable decrease of sheep pasturing going along with an increase of wolves as protection measures cannot be implemented reasonably. Consequently, sheep farmers, will only graze their sheep in “safe” areas or close to their farms, but not in remote mountainous places anymore.

About Trends: Regarding *drought*, an increase of *average temperature*, *extreme events* and *physical soil degradation* most respondents agreed on an increase in the past, and they think that this trend will continue in future.

The assessment of *land use changes* in plain areas, which might impact the future development of sheep farming in mountains indirectly by causing competitive disadvantages, was of high variances, thus results are not very meaningful. However, we had connected this topic to agro photo voltaic (combined with grazing areas), which is an issue of growing relevance, but highly contested. Further discussions on that issue will be carried in next phases of the project

Regarding *wildfires* respondents had difficulties in assessing the future projection, half of them were not able to answer the question.

About Sensitivity: The number of responses to the online survey to assess the sensitivity during the workshop was very low, thus the validity of the results might be limited. Workshop participants ascribed the highest sensitivity to wildfires but referred more to the fact that for many of the sheep farmers in the mountainous areas' forestry is another important source of income. *Temperature increase*, *extreme events*, and *physical soil degradation* was equally high ranked followed by *demographic change*, *precipitation*, *overuse*, and *Pests & invasive species*. Pollution and land use change was not ranked of that high sensitivity. The quite high ranking of demographic change was surprising.

List of adaptive mechanisms

These were the main mechanisms discussed at the workshop. In addition, in general, the fact that most sheep farms are managed on a part-time basis represents a challenge in terms of professionalisation or specific vocational training. This was also confirmed in the discussions during the workshop.

- **Agroforestry:** this was a new measure, which was raised only during the workshop (not in previous interviews). Silvopasture is considered as having good potential for improving the micro-climate of pastures with positive effects on the soil, plants, and sheep. Either trees might be planted in the pastures, or forest areas might be thinned, and pasture plants establish, eventually by seeding adapted plant varieties. Most farmers (as well in the study region as throughout Austria) are not aware about this farming practice (lack of traditional knowledge), thus the acceptance might be quite low. There is a pilot region close to the study area, where first experiments of agro-forestry are set up, but on plain land, and not focussing on silvopasture.
- **Building-up humus measures:** a healthy soil is seen as one of the most important resources, thus measures for soil recreation should be fostered. Some few farmers are already engaged in dealing with that topic, but there is need for awareness raising and vocational training of farmers. Expert consultants supporting farmers, and incentives in terms of financial support are considered to speed up related actions. Close to the study area, there is an initiative, which includes humus building-up measures as well. A cooperation with this region might be reasonable.
- **Cooperative feeding management.** Sustainable (joint) forage management / strategic feed resource planning - traditional knowledge is no longer sufficient regarding winter forage reserves (e.g., in the case of lignification of grass); feed may also have to be procured strategically (good mixture of straw and concentrated feed); experts should give advice on how to manage the pasture and grassland areas more efficiently; setting up cooperative structures for joint storage of winter feed (e.g., decentralised haylofts). The original suggestion (interview) of organising it in a cooperative manner, was discussed during the workshop with scepticism regarding the willingness of farmers to cooperate. However, apart from that hurdle, the measure was judged as very valuable.
- **Optimising grassland and pasture management:** Use of heat resistant grass varieties for the cultivation of winter forage. Optimal intensity of cultivation: The stronger the management of grassland, the stronger the development of roots, and thus the stability against erosion during extreme weather. Support would be needed from experts for individual consultations, and programs organising and funding vocational trainings.
- **Shift from cattle to sheep farming.** More farms shifting from cattle to sheep farming in order to prevent soil erosion, and to foster biodiversity on the pastures. This measure was

assessed as an already ongoing trend, which will continue in future. Sheep farming became particularly attractive due to the successful marketing of lamb and dairy products through the sheep farmers' cooperative, also for part time farming and women. Still, it is also a matter of general attitude towards sheep farming, which is traditionally considered as less prestigious compared to cattle farming. However, this image is changing within the younger generation.

- A new business model might be offered by **'rent a sheep'** services, for which the demand is increasing in order to get fallow land cultivated. However, it is also linked to the necessity of regularly transporting the animals from one place to another, which is associated with too much effort for most farmers. Some few already practice it successfully.
- **Goats to fight the encroachment of pastures:** Goats eat perennials and all sorts of plants much more efficient than sheep. They could therefore be used for the 'regeneration' of encroached alpine pastures. This measure is considered to be effective and easy to be implemented on an individual farm level in case necessary.
- **Reactivation of old farms (5 - 10 hectares):** The reactivation of old farms could create jobs as well as contribute to the preservation of the alpine pastures and meadows. Sheep offer attractive potential for newcomers as well. However, a reactivation is considered much more difficult than the **conservation of farms**. In most cases high investment is needed, and it is also often done by newcomers, who have no or little farming experience – plus a kind of "romantic" instead of a realistic idea about what it means to successfully run a farm.
- **Agro photovoltaic** is increasingly becoming an issue of interest for farmers in plain areas, which is highly contested in terms of using high quality agricultural land for electricity instead of food production. In the current practice there is no real double-use, and the agri-part is often neglected as energy production is generating the main revenue. While the focus at the given point of time lies on plain areas (due to the necessary infrastructure given there), the installation of agro-PV systems on pastures in mountainous areas is seen as more sustainable, and an attractive option. On one hand, the systems would protect the soil and animals from too much sun and extreme weather, on the other hand, additional income could be generated.
- **The use of wool**, which is now for nearly all farmers only a by-product and does not generate any revenue, could be optimised, and linked to broader climate protection measure. As a regional resource it might be used as bio-based fertiliser, growing substrate for vertical greening of buildings or as insulation material. There is quite much scepticism, if such measures would economically pay-off as the necessary infrastructure would need to be set up in the region, and there are concerns if these products could then be offered at affordable prices.

02 - Stara Planina. Bulgaria

Context

Mountain Reference Landscape: Western Stara Planina (Western Balkan Mountains)

Value Chain name: Public Goods from High Nature Value (HNV) farmland

Land-use system name: “Medium intensity / natural forest + Agro-silvo-pastoral system + Extensive open rangeland” – according to van Asselen and Verburg (2012) this might be broadly defined as an example of a “Mosaic (semi-) natural system” consisting of “Grassland and forest”

Photo 76. Horses grazing on semi-natural grasslands (HNV Farmland Type 1) in the municipality of Berkovitsa (MON02), Stara Planina

Source: HGGKoen de Rijk

Photo 77. Small cultivated plots alongside semi-natural grasslands and forest (HNV Farmland Type 2) in the municipality of Berkovitsa (MON02), Western Stara Planina

Source: HGGKoen de Rijk

Photo 78. Abandoned semi-natural grasslands in the municipality of Berkovitsa (MON02), Stara Planina

Photo 79. Under-utilised / abandoned semi-natural grasslands in the municipality of Berkovitsa (MON02), Stara Planina.

Figure 80 Map of the land use system (“Medium intensity / natural forest + Agro-silvo-pastoral system + Extensive open rangeland”) within the Western Stara Planina MRL

Source: MOVING Project (WP3) according to Asselen and Verburg (2012)

Short Description land-use system

In accordance with the understanding that there are areas in Europe where the prevailing farming system “...supports or is associated with either a high species and habitat diversity, or the presence of species of European, and/or national, and/or regional conservation concern or both” (European Commission, 2020), we describe the land-use system under study as “High Nature Value Farmland” (HNVF).

The HNVF existing in the Western Stara Planina is a mix of Types 1 (Farmland with a high proportion of semi-natural vegetation) and 2 (Farmland with a mosaic of low intensity agriculture and natural and structural elements) (Stefanova and Kazakova, 2012). See Figures 1 and 2.

The relative proportions of these two HNVF types in the Western Stara Planina vary primarily with altitude.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable selected was “farmland biodiversity” – specifically the “presence of priority habitats of European significance that are dependent upon the continuation of traditional agriculture”. The four main semi-natural vegetation habitats (as defined by Annex 1 of Council Directive 92/43/EEC) considered to be associated with the reference variable in the Western Stara Planina are 6210 (Semi-natural dry grasslands and scrubland facies on calcareous substrates*), 6230 (Species-rich *Nardus* grasslands on siliceous substrates in mountain areas), 6510 (Lowland hay meadows) and 6520 (Mountain hay meadows).

Farmland biodiversity is one of several “non-commodity outputs of agriculture” (so-called public goods) which are valued by society, but which are not directly marketable. Nonetheless, they can be marketed indirectly

(e.g., via product labelling schemes) as well as supported with effective policy interventions that are targeted at maintaining and/or enhancing their delivery (*'public money for public goods'*).

* Very important for orchids (a total of 11 orchid species with conservation significance have been found in the Western Stara Planina)

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 70 Driver description and components Stara Planina

Drivers	Description and Components
Precipitation	<p>The increasing incidence and intensity of drought is believed to be impacting upon biodiversity of the HNV grasslands in (at least) three ways by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reducing their floral diversity due to the local loss / extinction of those plant species of conservation significance that are least drought resistant 2. Potentially reducing the faunal diversity of semi-natural grasslands by reducing habitat quality (e.g., feeding sources for butterflies) 3. Causing the over-grazing (and associated loss of plant species) of those pastures occurring on soils which retain moisture for longer and therefore stay greener for longer
Temperature	<p>Increasing temperatures are understood to influence the distribution of valuable plant species in semi-natural grasslands, but it remains contentious how exactly.</p> <p>Concern was expressed by the stakeholders those rising temperatures could lead to the loss of cold-adapted plants, especially in the higher altitude alpine pastures (so-called 'mountaintop extinction'). However, it was also noted that there are many micro-climates in the complex topography of the Western Stara Planina mountains which are likely to provide 'refuge' to vulnerable species, at least in the short- to medium-term.</p> <p>More concerning is the potential interaction between rising (summer?) temperatures and the increasing incidence and intensity of drought.</p>
Extreme events	<p>Intensive rainfall. Changing patterns of rainfall are being observed with increasing incidence of very intensive rainfall – this is causing localised (often severe) soil erosion, especially adjacent to streams; in areas where sloping soils are already degraded, and where there is existing gully erosion due to heavy traffic from livestock or vehicles.</p> <p>These extreme rainfall events are also manifesting as an increased flood hazard, especially at lower altitudes.</p>
Wildfire	<p>In view of discussions amongst the stakeholders regarding the increasing incidence and intensity of drought, it was inevitable that concerns were also expressed about the risk of wildfires – especially those started accidentally by local farmers.</p> <p>There is a long-standing tradition of burning dry grass in the spring in order to promote fresh growth. The practice is prohibited, but control and enforcement are limited. From time-to-time these fires get out of control and there are a significant number of burned areas within the MRL.</p>
Pollution	<p>Point source water pollution from the poor storage and management of livestock manure and slurry was identified as a problem, but no indicators are available to substantiate. The problem is associated especially with smaller farms that do not have the necessary resources to invest in the improvement / upgrading of their manure storage facilities.</p>

Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Not identified as an important driver
Over-exploitation of resources	Not identified as an important driver
Demographic changes (depopulation)	<p>Demographic changes (depopulation). The Western Stara Planina has suffered major depopulation since the 1960s. People left the mountain municipalities of Georgi Damyanovo (MON14), Chiproviti (MON36) and Godech (SFO09) especially during the 1970s and 1980s when Bulgaria’s centralised economy was rapidly industrialising and there was large-scale movement of population from rural to urban areas.</p> <p>Unfortunately, the rate of depopulation has increased again in recent years with a 40% decline in the total population of the MRL between 2010 and 2020. Since it is mainly young people leaving the area, the remaining population is increasingly aged.</p>
Soil physical degradation	<p>Soil erosion. As noted above, the increasing incidence of very intensive rainfall is perceived as increasing the risk of soil erosion. This is most obvious on sloping cultivated land, but also in the semi-natural grasslands – especially adjacent to mountain streams; in locations where the grasslands have been previously degraded by over-grazing (or in some cases, fire), or where there are existing (eroded) gullies which collect and channel surface run-off during heavy rainfall.</p>
Land-use and land-cover change	<p>Land abandonment. The collapse of communism in the late 1980s triggered a complex process of re-privatising Bulgarian agriculture, including the restitution of farmland to its previous owners. This was hugely disruptive and there was a massive decline in the number of grazing animals accompanied by a huge increase in the abandonment of grasslands used for grazing and haymaking, plus small plots of cultivated land – especially in the more remote mountain areas.</p> <p>Although livestock numbers have stabilised and increased again in recent years, the continuing depopulation of the region means that abandonment and under-use of grasslands remains an issue because farmers do not have the available workforce (e.g., shepherds) to maintain their traditional management practices.</p> <p>This has led to severe scrub encroachment and natural re-afforestation of almost one-third of the semi-natural grasslands in the MRL (see <i>Figures 3 and 4 in the opening section of the report</i>).</p> <p>The loss of large area of semi-natural grassland grasslands, plus the ‘closure’ of the mosaic landscapes, has led to an alarming degradation of important wildlife habitats as well as the loss of specific species of conservation value. In other words, the supply of public goods from the HNV farmland has declined significantly and is at risk of further decline.</p> <p>This problem continues to be exacerbated by a range of other factors that will be explored in WP4.</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 81 Infographic of results Stara Planina

Comments on the results

About Ranking: The drivers that were considered most important were the non-climate-related drivers of (5) Demographic changes (depopulation) and (7) Land abandonment – these are considered to be affecting the supply of public goods from HNV farmland in the MRL most significantly

Although currently perceived to be of lesser importance at the moment, the drivers of (1) Precipitation (increasing incidence and intensity of drought) and (2) Temperature (increasing temperatures, including interaction with drought) were acknowledged as having the potential for significant impact upon the supply of public goods, but require much more scientific investigation. It was pointed out for example that precipitation (annual or seasonal rainfall) does not directly reflect soil water content which is the most factor important for plant development during the growing season of many plant species.

About Trends: As already explained, all the drivers were perceived as having increased over the last 10-20 years – with the exception of (4) Wildfires (*started accidentally by local farmers*).

It was agreed that all the drivers are likely to continue increasing in the coming years, although there are opportunities for the non-climate-related drivers of (5) Demographic changes (*depopulation*) and (7) Land abandonment to be directly addressed with well-targeted policy interventions

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Increased eligibility of semi-natural grasslands for CAP Pillar 1 payments** – the existing system of income support payments under Pillar 1 of the CAP is biased against extensive farming, including the exclusion (due to various criteria) of large areas of vegetation used for grazing in mountain areas. EU and national guidelines are needed to improve the definition of permanent grasslands/pastures to ensure the full eligibility in the new CAP of all areas that are effectively grazed or produce fodder (e.g. eco-schemes to support HNV farming systems and semi-natural pastures). This is an EU-wide issue and not specific to the Western Stara Planina.
- **Improved targeting of CAP Pillar 2 payments** – there are multiple opportunities for CAP Pillar 2 payments to be better targeted at the support of HNV farming, including adjusting the overall budget balance in favour of Pillar 2, designing and implementing more appropriate results-based incentive schemes for traditional land management and investment in locally-led HNV farmland conservation projects. This should be accompanied by adjustments in the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF) of the new CAP to improve the characterisation and monitoring of HNV farming systems/territories and the evaluation of CAP measures. Again, this is an EU-wide issue and not specific to the Western Stara Planina.
- **Stronger advisory and innovation support services for HNV farmers** – all forms of sustainable agriculture are “knowledge-intensive” and benefit from the existence of well-

functioning Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKISs). This includes relevant research, education and training, general and specialist advisors, innovation support services, formal and informal knowledge exchange networks etc. In the new CAP, all EU Member States are required to take strategic actions to strengthen their national AKIS to ensure both the production and flow of knowledge and innovative solutions to farmers' needs. If appropriately targeted this has great potential to benefit HNV farmers.

- **Improved governance of common grazing** – common grazing is a traditional practice in Bulgaria and the majority of grasslands in the Western Stara Planina are public (municipal or state) grasslands that were historically used for common grazing. Due to the need to have a legal right to claim CAP support payments, these common grasslands are now allocated for individual use and their use is regulated in a written form agreed by the local municipality. Considerable potential exists to improve these agreements, both for maintaining the biodiversity value of the grasslands (notably regarding the management of Natura 2000 areas) and benefitting the farmers via compensatory payments.
- **Greater support for new entrants / young farmers** – as the number of HNV farms declines greater effort could be made to help new entrants and/or young farmers to start new ones. Numerous opportunities exist including CAP funding for the installation of young farmers, adjusting the rules for the allocation of and access to municipal grasslands, incentivising land sales/rental of HNV farmland etc.
- **Regional/local branding and marketing schemes** – a regional brand for the Western Stara Planina has been discussed for some time but requires dedicated actions, skills and improved cooperation amongst local actors. With the right strategic vision and necessary coordination this could be achieved via the available policy support mechanisms (see above and below). The simplification and streamlining of legislation and controls for direct marketing of farm products would also be highly beneficial for local HNV farmers.
- **More multi-funded (and community-led) local development** – HNV farmers in the Western Stara Planina are predominantly small-scale and do not exist in isolation but as communities. Well-facilitated and multi-funded local development is a very powerful tool for improving the quality of life of HNV farmers and their families thereby helping to address the problems of outmigration and rural depopulation. There are LEADER Local Actions Groups (LAGs) established and working in the region, however, none of them has built their Local Development Strategies upon the HNV characteristics of their local territories.

03 – Sumava - Cesky Les. Czechia

Context

Study case: Šumava - Český les

Value Chain name: Beef Production

Land-use system name: Extensive open rangeland

Photo 82. Sumava pastures

Source: Jakub Husák

Figure 83 Crops map in Sumava - Cesky Les MRL

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *d'Andrimont et al 2018*

Short Description land-use system

The geographical area comprises of three municipalities located in a mountain region. Settlement is located around 800 metres above sea level. This altitude is considered a crossing line between a production-oriented agriculture and the pure landscape maintenance. Land in the region is used for agriculture (perennial grassland) and forestry. Agricultural usage of the land is limited by climatic conditions and slope of the plots. The geographical area includes Natural Landscape Protected Area and National Park. Regulation focused on preserving nature values significantly impacts on agriculture and forestry.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable is **quality pasture for cattle** that lies in the heart of the beef production. Quality of the pasture is associated with enough grass for the pasture (as well as production of hay for winter season) that presumes adequate density, health and diversity of plants. Qualitative features of the pasture are directly affected by climatic factors in the region.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 71 Driver description and components in Sumava - Cesky Les MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Continuous low rainfall with potential impact to vegetation, hydrological level (streams and aquifers) and soil. The amount of the spring and summer rains impacts on amount of forage. Drought reduces availability of grass on pastures and availability of hay for winter season.
Temperature	Increase in mean temperature, seasonal or annual. High temperature in summer months in combination with reduced precipitation multiplies negative effect on vegetation growth.
Extreme events	Changes in intensity, frequency, or timing for extreme heat and storms. Extreme heat reduces vegetation on pasture. <i>Mentioned partly during the interview, but not used for the further discussion and evaluation: negative impacts on animal welfare.</i>
Wildfire	Changes in intensity and frequency of wildfires, which reduce diversity of vegetation on pastures.
Land-use and land-cover change	Overgrowth of pastures of trees and shrubs. <i>Mentioned partly during the interview, but not used for further discussion and evaluation: agricultural land in mountain areas (except the National Park and the Nature Protected Areas) are under pressure due to high demand for land that can be used for residence (tourist infrastructure).</i>
Soil physical degradation	Loss of organic of the soil, due to insufficient fertilisation of pastures and loss of organic matter due to grazing and mowing grass.
Over-exploitation of resources	Overgrazing due to more cattle on pastures. <i>Mentioned partly during the interview, but not used for further discussion and evaluation: high concentration of animals on a limited plot during winter destroys land</i>
Pests, diseases and invasive species	Changes in the intensity and frequency of pasture damaged by voles, mice and wild boars. <i>Mentioned partly during the interview, but not used for further discussion and evaluation: there are a few invasive plant species (such as <i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i> or <i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>) recognized in Sumava mountains</i>
Pollution	Contamination of soil by heavy metals. <i>Mentioned partly during the interview, but not used for further discussion and evaluation: contamination of land through cattle excrement that may include residues of veterinary medication</i>

Demographic changes

population decline or immigration in the region might produce changes in management practices and land-use abandonment. There are not enough young people entering agriculture, so farms lack employees and family farms have difficulty with finding a successor.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 84 Infographic of results in Sumava - Cesky Les MRL

Comments on the results

About Ranking: Analysis suggests that there are three groups of drivers:

1. Relatively important: precipitation, temperature, extreme events, demographic changes
2. Relatively unimportant: land-use change, soil degradation, over-exploitation, invasive species
3. Less relevant: pollution, wildfire

The group of important drivers consists of those that bring visible impacts on current agriculture in given region, relatively unimportant drivers are limited by other circumstances, namely institutional regulations associated with the National Park, Nature Protected Areas or regulations of agricultural practices. Their impacts are thus negligible wildfire and pollution (due to regulations) is not viewed as relevant drivers that would impact on agriculture in the region.

About trends: Stakeholders acknowledge a small increase in relation to the issue of precipitation, temperature, and extreme events. They also expect that this trend will very likely to continue. The evaluation of the less important drivers was somehow mixed, since the drivers and their effects in the region was not visible enough. The impact induced by human activities in agriculture was not considered so important, because the locality is quite strictly protected by existing institutional framework. At this moment, it does not seem that this would change in the future, and thus the future trend is expected to remain stable.

About sensitivity: Stakeholders participating in the study generally acknowledge that current agriculture is sensitive to ongoing climate change. Main emphasis is put on the issue of low precipitation and high temperature, which farmers experienced in the previous couple years. At the same time, stakeholders pointed out that more sensitive to these changes are intensive farms in low altitude locations (reduction of yields with the same costs, lack of water for animals, lack of forage for animals). Agriculture in mountain areas, and particularly extensive cattle farms located in altitude above 800 metres, were not seen as sensitive to these changes.

List of adaptive mechanisms

The list of adaptive capacity mechanism is sorted from the most important to less important based on workshop (prioritisation of mechanism) and interviews.

- **Change of agrotechnical procedures** refers mainly to implementation of suitable grass mixture to resow pastures also in Šumava National Park (where it is currently prohibited) and allow pasture mowing at different terms (not all pastures and meadows in one term) to allow blooming and resowing of plants that are present at meadows. It needs to change legislation at national level and farmers' awareness of the benefits. So, this is achievable in the medium term.

- **Changes of subsidies schemes** towards support of small farms and processing the products which could improve the quality of pastures in indirect way (diversification of farmers and their better relation to the soil). It is also achievable in the medium term. Landscape management needs to be financially supported since the farmers produce positive externalities. From their point of view, the subsidy schemes in the Czech Republic have been more favourable for large-scale farmers. Czech Republic has got the largest farm size in the EU (the average is 133 hectares of the utilised agricultural area). Direct payments to farmers are based on the farm size, therefore the large-scale farms benefit from this policy approach. There has been an intense discussion to **change this approach in favour of small farms**. The stakeholders in the workshop generally agreed on shifting the support towards small-scale farming.
- **Education and promotion of agriculture** could have a long-term indirect impact. It should attract young people to agriculture in mountain areas, which suffer from depopulation and to improve their relation to the soil. This has been mentioned as a cross-cutting topic for entire agriculture. Remoteness of mountain areas only magnifies the given problem.
- **Modernisation and innovation in agriculture and generally rural development** is dependent on policy and subsidy support. It could be easily achievable from the technological perspectives (technology is available) but change in financial support is a matter of the medium term. Most of the stakeholders pointed out that the shift in **financial support needs to be in harmony with the changed mindset of farmers to implement methods that are more in compliance with nature**. The agricultural practices in national park obviously go in that direction, however, stakeholders in the workshop mentioned that the “good farmers” should be more appraised for their effort. Stakeholders pointed out that the minimal standards for farmers are not very demanding and give a lot of room of practices that are not sustainable in a long term. Despite that, such practices still allow farmers to draw agricultural subsidies. Stakeholders mentioned that farmers who are more ambitious in achieving sustainable goals should benefit more from the policy support. At the same time the rural development policy – focused on innovations – should be coupled with changes in agriculture. However, the ideas of stakeholders mentioned during the workshop were quite general and did not include more specific ideas.

04 - Corsica. France

Context

Study case: Corsica - Monte Renoso massif

Value Chain name: PDO Chestnut flour

Land-use system name: High intensity plant forest (Agroforestry)

Photo 85. Typical chestnut grove

Photo 86. The village of Bocognano and its chestnut grove

Source: Sorba J.M., 2021

Photo 87: Site visit of the Moving group in progress

Photo 88: Workshop on participatory vulnerability analysis,

Source: Sorba J.M., 2021

Photo 89. Plant multiplication plots, Bocognano

Source: Martinetti, 2022

Photo 90. Young chestnut plant with protection tube

Source: Regional Syndicate for the defence and promotion of the quality of Corsican Chestnut Flour

Figure 91 Localisation: Rinosu Massif and villages

Source: Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière (Screen capture July 28, 2021)

Short Description land-use system

The land-use system concerns three village territories located in the middle valley. The chestnut groves are mainly located near the villages of Bocognano, Ghisoni, Noceta and Venaco (pop. about 1000, 20/km²) at a latitude of 500 to 1000 m (supra mediterranean, 700-800mm/year). It is in a green setting made up of forests dominated by beeches, quercus (*pubescens*, *ilex*) and scrub. The influence chestnut grove on the peri-village area constitutes an economic resource (PDO flour and tourism), a lever against abandonment and a barrier against fires. These are old orchards (from the 17th to the 19th century) of which only 10 to 15% are harvested mainly transformed into flour in nearby mills.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain:

Chestnut production. The reference variable is the annual production of chestnuts expressed in terms of quantity and characteristics of the fruits (pomological and organoleptic criteria PDO). Downstream, it is linked to PDO flour by pedoclimatic and varietal conditions and therefore processing (harvesting, sorting, drying, husking, grinding). The whole is fixed in the rules of the PDO specifications. Upstream, annual production expresses the health of environments, trees, and orchards.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 72 Driver description and components in Corsica

Driver	Description and Components
Demographic changes:	The chestnut grove is the 5th forest species in Corsica, but only 2,600 ha are managed out of the estimated 30,000 ha. The factors that affect production volumes are linked to the rural decline that began after the Second World War and accelerated since the 1960s. The success of the recovery at the end of the 1970s came up against the demographic weakness of the villages and the age of orchards that had become vulnerable to diseases and pedoclimatic factors. For all players in the value chain, population density is the primary impact factor of the reference variable (2 to 5 inhabitants in the area per km ² , INSEE, 2018).
Pests and invasive species	Pest. Phytophthora and Cryphonectria diseases were the first obstacles to the revival of chestnut groves (1975). Fungi cause trees to die back more or less rapidly. The causes are climatic and linked to transmission by pigs (burrowing). Control are inoculation of endogenous mycorrhizae (Ink) and the use of hypo virulent strains. The recent period has seen the sudden appearance of fruits (2010-2020) of Dryocosmus kuriphilus causing a drastic and significant decrease in fruit production (50 to 100%). Biological control by Torymus sinensis contains the disease successfully and generates an effective local health system. Balaninus attacks the fruits, but whose impacts are less important.
Pests and invasive species	Animal stray rewilding. The wandering of animals especially cows and pigs impacts the reference variable through fruit predation, soil degradation (burrowing and trampling) and supporting structures for terraces. The solutions identified are coercive (public sanctions, prohibition of grazing) and organisational (common rules, customary uses of "u forestu"). The abundance of wild boars causes similar damage.
Precipitation	Drought. Its expression is above all the drought, which takes 2003 as the reference year. Since then, it has intensified with climate change with one significant episode every 3 years. An experiment is underway to retain moisture by seedling a lawn also serving as green manure (clover) or even installing rainwater reserves and weather stations. Note that irrigation is prohibited by the PDO specifications. The effects of drought are multiple and antagonist: smaller fruit size but higher flour yield and sweetness).
Temperature	Coupled with precipitation, it is the cause of increasingly frequent drought episodes. Note that very high temperatures (reference, year 2015) reduce pollination (dry pollen), fertility and the quantity of chestnuts. Few or no direct solutions apart from planting trees at a higher altitude (supramediterranean and mountainous floors), planting adapted varieties and cultural practices limiting evapotranspiration.
Soil physical Degradation	The soil concentrates all the impacts (climatic, animal wandering, reservoir of pathogens and predators). Its structure, fauna and flora are increasingly deteriorating due to the violence of the rains (soil beating), overgrazing and human intervention. Preserving chestnut grove soils involves sowing lawns, limiting the passage of machinery, avoiding burning, and grinding plant material to improve the humus content and soil fertility (Training of farmers in soil protection, awareness of vulnerability and implementation of protective cultivation practices). Some actors question the positive effect of grazing on soil fertility (digging and manure).

Precipitation	Altitude and vegetation Due to global warming and the decrease in rainfall, the altitude of old orchards and their exposure to adret (even a minority) constitute an obstacle to fruit production and affect the sustainability of orchards. The solutions would be to irrigate the trees (ban by the PDO), to sow lawns and to plant varieties adapted to drought and / or to a higher altitude.
Land Use and Land Cover Change	The decline in agro-pastoral activities is accompanied by a freeing up of space favorable to little or no mastery of pastoralism, particularly of pigs and cows which tend to become wild. The spatial influence of this degraded pastoralism favors the overgrowth of environments and orchards. However, in recent years, often at the initiative of town halls, several initiatives have been noted to clean up orchards and protect them from the effects of abandonment and the decline in human activities (see fires).
Extreme Events	Are grouped here the extraordinary climatic events which often associate torrential rains, winds and lightning. They cause damage of unpredictable magnitude. The wind in particular causes the fall of unopened buds which make harvesting difficult. Corsican chestnut groves usually have an excellent dehiscence, which promotes the release of the fruit.
Wildfires	Rare in the past, the frequency of winter fires is increasing due to drought, increased temperatures and thickets (<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> , <i>Rubus</i> and <i>Erica arborea</i>) in the perivillage areas where chestnut groves are often found. They are made vulnerable even as they participate in the protection of villages.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 92 Infographic of results in Corsica

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: The demographic driver comes first for all the interviews carried out (16). Pest comes in second place, it incorporates a large part of the other drivers (2, 3, 5 and 6 rainfalls, temperature, soil.). Driver 4 “Animal stray and rewilding herd” is a source of reduced chestnut production (erosion, disease, and predation).

About trends: The actors are aware of climate change and its impact on the Mediterranean chestnut grove, which fears drought.

But they are helpless in terms of prospective and operational solutions (technical packages). One possible strategy is to take advantage of the mountainous character of Corsica. Renovation is no longer the only means of revival: planting projects are growing due to a desire to establish orchards at a higher altitude. A reflection is underway to think of the different ways of renewing old orchards: plants, grafting, autoregeneration and the installation of a nursery, central or decentralized etc.

About sensitivity: The last 30 years have been marked by a first flourishing period (1995-2010) of tree renovation, linked to the PDO certification of flour. The gall wasp period (2011-2020) at the origin of a strong loss of production, (20 to 80%) revealed the vulnerabilities of the activity (aging of the orchard and the castanéiculturists, diseases, drought, insufficiency of equipment).

The success of biological control (Taurimus), the price of PDO flour (18 to 20 euros) and the new interest for the chestnut tree (landscape, nurturing, educational, etc.) encourages the plantation of new orchards adapted (drought, soil, diseases, etc.). Organisation (rules of access to the resource, control of stray animals) and production of plants are the new challenge for the next 20 years.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Replacement old Orchard by varieties adapted (drought)**

The age of orchards and abandonment are perceived as the source of disease and reduced production. The replanting project aims to replace dead or diseased trees and to plant new plots on sites less exposed to the effects of climate change (shade, irrigation, and altitude). This means producing healthy plants in nurseries, multiplying them in mountain areas and distributing them. The setting up of a decentralized multi-site nursery is under study and gives rise to many debates (location, varieties, governance, and objectives). Planting is an innovation because the revival has so far consisted of renovating old trees (pruning, make-up removal, etc.).

- **Biological disease control**

The biological fight against the gall wasp (with its natural predator, Torymus) has shown the attachment of producers to organic management of orchards (in AB for a large part of

the volume). It has mobilized many producers and volunteers on the island to raise funds to finance release campaigns and plant observation. The partnership health system can be reactivated for other pathogens.

- **Irrigation, water reserves, soil retention**

Climate change calls into question the ban on irrigation mentioned in the specifications of the AOP. The producers wish to irrigate the new trees by setting up hillside reserves (by gravity) or by sprinkling. The protection of soils and the improvement of their fertility (maintenance of water retention capacity) are increasingly discussed.

- **Management rules customary law of the commons**

The customary law which governed the different uses of the chestnut grove has almost disappeared in favor of the sole right of ownership (private or communal). The project of the actors is to restore this right or to draw inspiration from it to secure the plantations against degradation linked to stray animals, theft or competition between uses. A management of the common good type is under study (control of resources, governance, and rules of use).

- **Soil protection**

Heavy rainfall, declining fertility, erosion led producers to use new means: grassing, sheep grazing, litter etc.

- **Clearing of chestnut groves**

A small part of the chestnut grove is in production. Most of the surfaces are sometimes overgrown by high scrub. Gyrobroyage techniques are essential to allow harvesting and the protection of trees against fires.

- **Cultural practices**

Cultivation practices are still poorly regulated and would require technical advice adapted to chestnut cultivation (agronomy, pedology, tillage). As well as techniques such as complementarity between symbiotic species (mycorrhization of strains attenuated against anchor disease) or even edible mushrooms.

- **Incentives for setting up in chestnut farming**

There are no public policies dedicated to the recovery according to specific directions of the recovery. Public aid is allocated under the castanéiculturists' status as farmers. Several orientations are envisaged: renovation, planting, nurseries, and varietal trials against drought, irrigation trials.

The weakening of the cynip explains the choice of actors in favour of biological control to deal with diseases. The first issue in the value chain is the renewal of very old trees. The projects today associate planting with simple renovation: the planting of new trees adapted to climate change (drought) raises questions of research (resistant varieties), of experimentation in plots, of organisation (nurseries), of choice technical (irrigation), development actions (water retention, brush clearing) and land availability (use of old village outbuildings). The establishment of a nursery appears to be a strategic fulcrum for responding to the array of uncertainties linked to rural abandonment and climate change. The players are led to rethink the location of the orchards (800 m minimum) and to design new driving methods. Training and advice are seen as determining factors in supporting producers in the transition (cultivation practices and soil protection). These devices appear insufficient today. Due to the successive crises, the objective of installing new producers is little asserted. It involves opening the value chain to new players, particularly municipalities, and to new uses, which may raise questions of coexistence between activities (flour and other methods of recovery).

05 – Drôme Valley. France

Context

Study case: Drôme Valley, France

Value Chain name: Sheep meat locally produced and valorised

Land-use system name: Extensive open pastures

Photo 93. Sheeps grazing in Font d'urle, Vercors massif

Photo 94. Climb to the mountain pasture from Saint Julien en Quint to Font d'Urle

Source: CCVD

Figure 95 Municipalities, Vegetation and Natural parc in the MRL

Source: CCVD

Short Description land-use system

The geographical area of the study includes 13 municipalities (Beaufort-sur-Gervanne, Cobonne, Eygluy-Escoulin, Gigors & Lozeron, Montclar-sur-Gervanne, Omblèze, Plan de Baix, Suze, Le Chaffal, Saint Julien en Quint, Bouvante, Léoncel). The mountain region is located at the opening of the Drôme valley, on the north side, which coincides with the beginning of the south-west part of the Vercors massif. The land-use system goes from lower mountain regions hosting the farms to the higher alpine pastures and plateaux of Ambel and Gervanne.

This area has been defined by the CCVD and its main partners involved in the value chain (FDO, ADEM) because there are:

- many farmers and other stakeholders involved in the dynamics of Pastoral landscape management.
- few problems and threats known since few years (predation, drought, climate change, landscape closure)
- farmer's resistance facing territorial issues
- stakeholder organisations requesting support to deal with the issues and support to adapt to climate change

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable for this study is the pastoral resource: grasslands and shrubbery availability on the pasture areas. Pastoral resource is the most important resource for all kind of extensive pastoral breeding. The quantity and the quality of the resource affect the wellness of the herd and the value of final products. Specifically for this value chain, the valorisation is completed and territorially integrated if all the resources of the breeding come from the local area. Part of the producers sell their products (lamb and sheep meat, wool) under the label *Parc régional du Vercors* which demands that the livestock must be fed with local fodder or cereals, or with grassland from the pastures in the parc area.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 73 Driver description and components in Drôme Valley

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. The region is experiencing a decrease in precipitation and a general disruption of rainfall episodes: heavy rainfall alternates with long periods of drought. The dry period extends from late spring to early fall, while the periods at the beginning and end of the year are characterized by heavy rainfall. Low rainfall affects grass and brush growth and quality especially in lower mountain.
Temperature	Temperatures are generally rising over the MRL. Winters are mild and there are heat waves throughout the year. This disruption impacts the renewal cycles of the grass and slows down its growth, especially in south-facing areas.
Extreme events	Dry spells are becoming more common due to rising temperatures and low rainfall. This has led to an increase in gusty winds and the number of days with strong winds that dry out the air and soil. Moreover, late freezes in early spring are a risk to crop and grassland development.
Wildfire	Firewoods. There are no serious episodes to report. However, the risk of fire is increasingly high due to the drought and the closing of the environment (vegetation density).
Pollution	This factor is not very relevant in the context of the value chain at this time. The only element that could become a problem is water pollution by herd manure in case of heavy loading on a surface.
Pests, diseases and invasive species	In times of drought, insects such as locusts and grasshoppers feed on the grass in the meadows. But it is a minor and localized impact. Even if it is not directly linked to climate change, the presence of the wolf represents a new and very important issue for the breeders and their herds. Livestock is relocated to areas close to the farm for safety reasons, putting pressure on the meadows (indirect risk of overgrazing).
Over-exploitation of resources	Due to the drought and high temperatures, the slow renewal of grasslands and the reduction of grazing areas by the closure of environments, the risk of overgrazing is higher.
Demographic changes	Rural areas in the MRL are increasingly frequented by people who are unfamiliar with the codes of grazing environments (tourists, new inhabitants). The tourist attraction of the region and the large number of hikers sometimes make it difficult to manage the pastures: lack of knowledge of the behavior to adopt with the grazing animals, respect for the passage areas and problems related to the presence of guard dogs.

Soil physical degradation	This factor is not very relevant in the context of the value chain at this time. Soils degrade only on surfaces exposed to drought and/or erosion. It is a very punctual phenomenon only visible the long of herds pathways.
Land-use and land-cover change	Mountain environments in MRL are closing due to a decrease in the maintenance of the landscape by livestock. Some areas are experiencing reforestation. Vegetation takes the place on the meadows or prevents the access to other more distant surfaces.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 96 Infographic of results for Drôme Valley

Comments on the results about ranking, trends and sensitivity

About Ranking: Based on the results of the interviews, questionnaire responses, and discussion with MAP members, the drivers that were assessed as having the greatest impact on the value chain were: precipitation, temperature, and invasive species (wolf).

Dry weather during the summer season has been extended to late spring and early autumn. According to some actors, the annual quantity of water has not changed, but the episodes of rainfall are more localized, but also more violent. This deregulation is a complex issue for the organisation of the mountain pastures, where the renewal of plant species is slowed down.

Temperatures also play a pivotal role in the renewal process. Warmer temperatures are recorded in the high pastures affecting grass growing.

Even if it is not considered as an invasive species, but more as a harmful element, the wolf is the most important issue for the value chain at the moment. Its presence in the region is increasing and it is getting closer and closer to the valley. Many breeders want to stop their activity because of the difficulty of managing such a phenomenon. Divisions are created within the society, the protectors of the wild fauna on one side and the breeders and hunters on the other.

Finally, "Extreme events" were not considered as driver directly impacting the value chain. Drought was understood because of the lack of rainfall, so the "precipitation" factor was considered at the origin of the problem.

About trends: The temperature observations made at the Montélimar (western Drôme) station between 1970 and 2011 do not show a significant increase in the occurrence of very hot days, during which the maximum temperature reaches or exceeds 35°C. The year 2003 appears to be quite isolated, with almost 30 very hot days recorded. The trend is clearer for the medium and especially the long-term forecasts, during which 40 or even 50 very hot days per year could be recorded on a frequent basis. It is in the long term that the hot summers could become really frequent and long, with an average of more than ten days of very hot weather forecast for all the lowland areas, and up to 15 or even 20 days in the extreme south-east of the department.

These very high temperatures could be accompanied by more frequent summer droughts and longer, amplifying the drying action on the vegetation.

Partly under the influence of the Mediterranean, the Drôme department is already subject to the constraints associated with summer drought, and stationary observations in Montélimar show a strong period of water stress in July-August. In the medium and long term, even if the trend of an increase in the number of consecutive dry days does not seem to be significant, the period of water stress, while increasing in intensity, could extend beyond the current period. Extrapolated from a publication of Philippe et al. 2012.

From what came out of the interviews the interpretations are the similar. For the moment, the problems linked to climate change are still slightly perceptible. The risk on grass growth is mostly identified in the long term and remains for the moment quite localized. However, there is a growing

concern about the availability of water for grazing livestock on the mountain pastures in summer period. This has led to a recent focus on technical tools for water transport and storage.

About sensitivity: The perception of the impact of climate change is not very alarming among most of the actors interviewed. Some of them feel that in the long term the impacts will be visible and are aware of the risks. For this reason they want to be informed about possible solutions and implement adaptation mechanisms now.

The wolf in this period largely occupies the minds of the farmers, the farmers' unions, and the direction departementale des territoires (who implement the measures of protection of the wolf). It is a theme to which also the citizens are very sensitive and which at this moment, despite everything, passes before the impact of the climate change.

Last year from the 1st of January to this time on February 6 sheep died, this year for the same period the number is of 51.

Recent articles about wolves attacks in Drôme Valley (3 different attacks)

- 14.02.2022 <https://www.20minutes.fr/planete/3235479-20220214-Drôme-un-troupeau-de-moutons-tue-les-attaques-de-loups-se-multiplient>
- 7.02.2022 <https://www.ledauphine.com/faits-divers-justice/2022/02/07/dix-brebis-tuees-a-crest-une-nouvelle-attaque-du-loup>
- 16.01.2022 <https://www.ledauphine.com/economie/2022/01/16/le-loup-sevit-dans-la-plaine-dromoise-cet-animal-n-a-pas-peur-et-se-permet-petit-a-petit-d-aller-plus-loin>

List of adaptive mechanisms

Adaptation mechanisms do not have a direct influence on reducing the impact of climate drivers (drought, temperature and extreme events). However, they can play a role in adaptation and mitigation of associated consequences of climate change mitigation (such as forest fires), as well as other drivers through changes in grazing practices, which are directly related to landscape maintenance and resource use.

- **Reduction of livestock loading in mountain pasture defining a precise grazing schedule**

This requires an effort of communication and sharing of space between producers. Due to the longer dry season, the organisation of "parcels" and grazing calendars seems to be a practical solution that can be easily worked out by everyone. The Federation Departementale Ovine (FDO) could play a coordinating role in setting up the calendars, the frequency of passage and define with the farmers the number of animals allowed in the alpine pastures per passage.

- **Develop undergrowth pasture, agro-sylvo-pastoralism and eco-pastoralism**

The objective of these practices is to exploit as much of the available space as possible with bilateral benefits.

Undergrowth grazing, on the one hand, provides diversified food and shade, and on the other hand it allows the maintenance of wooded areas (management of closed environments, less risk of fire).

Regarding the wolf problem, grazing in controlled areas (orchards, fields in rotation...) would ensure the protection of the herd.

In organisational terms, it is a question of creating synergies between different agricultural activities which can prove to be opportunities to create closed cycle systems, therefore of sustainable agriculture.

- **"Report sur pied": management of the equilibrium between grazing and stoked fodder**
- The « Report sur pied » it is a breeding technique to manage the balance between grazing and stored forage, which applies in all systems using diversified vegetation.

Grassland production is not regular or predictable depending on the temperature, moisture and plant conditions of the plot. The idea is to let the grass accumulate without harvesting or grazing it in order to keep the biomass produced for later.

It is a mechanism that concerns the breeders and perhaps organisations that can support the breeders in the process. The main goal is to manage in a more intelligent way the available resource and to adapt the consumption according to the season and the weather conditions.

06 - Crete. Greece

Context

Study case: Carob Production in Rethymno- Crete

Value Chain name: Carob flour

Land-use system name: Agro-Silvo-Pastoral

Photo 97. Carob trees in a new plantation

Photo 98. Wild Carob trees in Rethymno

Source: UOC/PERIFEREIA

Figure 99 MOVING Land Systems in Crete

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Malek & Verburg, 2017*

Figure 100 Land Systems in Crete MRL

Source: Map of land uses (Region of Crete). General Directorate of Forests and Forest Environment.

http://mapsportal.yopen.gr/layers/geonode:kriti_dis

Short Description of land-use system

The MRR of Central Rethymno is a hilly mountainous area between the two major massifs of Crete: White Mountains and Psiloritis (Mount Ida), with steep slopes, mainly covered with shrubby vegetation, oaks, kermes oaks, carob trees (in shrubby vegetation as well as in meadows) and olive trees. Numerous small villages (with less than 500 residents) are scattered around the region

The dominant land use systems are permanent, extensive and agro-silvo-pastoral, and they are deeply connected to the way of life of the inhabitants. The area has a high level of vulnerability mainly because of the ageing and declining population and the hitherto implemented rural development policies, which have led to land and activity abandonment. The emerging climate change seems to exacerbate the situation. A characteristic example of abandonment is the exploitation of carob trees that were traditionally cultivated and harvested for their beans in the area.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain:

Carob Pod Production and linkage to the value chain of carob flour. Carob harvesting traditionally yielded and continues to yield a supplementary revenue for farmers. The legumes or pods are collected by using a traditional process involving rods. The harvesting of legumes takes place in late summer to early autumn and was often-times a collective communal process. The carob harvest has an overlap with the grape harvest; thus, the price of the product can be crucial regarding prioritisation.

Nowadays, the carob legumes are processed for both human and animal consumption in modern mills with patented techniques for processing the ripe, dried, or toasted legumes into flour, chips, powder, coffee, tea, molasses type syrup, and beauty products. These high reputation and quality by-products are in turn used in a long, but rather narrow value chain of baked goods, condiments, treats, and other food items. Due to the nutritional value, lower calories, fat, and processed sugar the by-products have been used in the nutraceutical

industries and are a part of the sustainable food movement. The higher value carob seeds are extracted, exported and processed in Italy and other countries and are ultimately utilized in gastronomy.

We aim to focus on the value chain of carob flour because it is mainly developed in the area and affects the socio-economic environment.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 74 Driver description and components in Crete MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Decrease in rainfall in spring. Carob pod/bean production depends on favourable natural rainfall cycles in early autumn and spring. Carob trees grow in the arid and drought prone MRL but pod production can be negatively affected by very low rainfall in September and the late spring months. The driver was included due to the evolving climate change. To keep it simple, the adopted description was <i>"Understanding precipitation as significant changes in rainfall from autumn to mid-spring (favourable rainfall). Changes in this period have negative effects on the hydrological level (streams and aquifers), soil and vegetation. Sufficient rainfall in this period is important for carob germination, flower set, and pod production. Therefore, changes in this rainfall period can negatively affect carob trees, as well as other crops. Specifically, in this study we will focus on the prolonged reduction of precipitation during Springtime."</i>
Temperature	Trees and pod growth endure temperature range from -5 to 50 degrees Celsius. Adult trees suffer damages when temperatures fall below -4°C and there is frost, and young trees are even more sensitive. In contrast, high temperatures up to 50°C, are well tolerated in carob. In Crete and in the land use system there is low vulnerability to low temperatures. Low susceptibility and sensitivity of carob trees high temperatures- but sensitivity to temperatures below -5°C. The driver was included due to the evolving climate change. The adopted description was: <i>"Understanding Temperature as the increase of temperatures on average over the year. This results in milder winters and warmer summers, which positively affect the vegetation, flowering, and fruiting of the carob trees. An increase in mean temperature over the year is likely to have a positive effect on the production of carob pods."</i>
Extreme events	Extreme southerly winds break down trees and dislodge the carob pods/beans impacting production. The MRL is prone to such weather conditions, and they have become more prominent. Frost and temperatures below 5°C damage pods and trees but this are a very rare occurrence in the MRL. Additionally, in the last 10 years the MRL experienced rapid rainfalls in winter. The driver was included due to the evolving climate change. The adopted description was: <i>"Extreme events" means changes in the intensity, frequency, or timing of extreme weather events. For the carob growing area in Rethymno, we focus on rapid rainfall in winter and heat waves in combination with strong southerly winds and prolonged hot conditions starting in spring that negatively affect carob trees"</i> .
Wildfire	Agro-pastoral land management system is associated with the prevention of wildfires. Wildfires are not prevalent on Crete and carob trees burn less slowly than all other trees. The driver was included in case a future threat would be indicated by the participants, but it did not work.
Land-use and land-	Land-use changes are driven by profit margins (led to the shift to the monoculture of olives), EU subsidies for olive farming, road construction and land fragmentation, carob harvesting abandonment/ uprooting and timbering to firewood. The adopted description

cover change	was: <i>"Understanding "Land-use and land-cover change" as abandonment of carob crops, uprooting of carob trees to produce firewood and land-use change mainly for olive cultivation. "</i>
Soil physical degradation	Carob grows under different edaphic conditions. The trees grow and produce pods in marginal and calcareous soils. Soil properties in the area are sufficient for pod production in the MRL. The agro-pastoral land management system impacts positively via weed reduction and natural fertilisation. The driver was included in case the perception of a group of participants would be different. The adopted description was <i>"Understanding Soil Physical Degradation as loss of organic matter due to erosion, poor tillage, or excessive compaction. In the case of carob trees there is no natural degradation, as carob trees have marginal nutrient requirements and pasture land-use coexists. Carob cultivation is suitable for soils that have been degraded by other crops and could be used to upgrade them."</i>
Over-exploitation of resources	Carob pod production does not exploit the natural resources since it is a dry and organic farming crop. Carob trees have a positive impact on resources since their long rooting systems aid in preventing soil erosion. The driver was included in case the perception of a group of participants would be different. The adopted description was: <i>"Understanding SOIL PHYSICAL DEGRADATION as loss of organic matter due to erosion, poor tillage, or excessive compaction. In the case of carob trees there is no natural degradation, but other neighbouring crops and land-use systems may affect the soil."</i>
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Mealybugs, soft and armored scales and mites damage pod production. Rodents destroy tree bark causing damage to trees and pod production. Production may be impacted much more if pests and more invasive species infiltrate. The danger of invasive species was mainly underlined by researchers and publications related to problems in carob productions in Sicily and south Italy. That was the main reason that the particular driver was included. The adopted description was: <i>"Understanding PESTS, DISEASES and INVASIVE SPECIES as spread of rodents, new diseases and species that have invaded Crete and affect carob trees and / or their pods"</i>
Pollution	Unknown if pollution impacts production of carob pods. Airborne pesticides may impact production, especially to certain areas of the MRL that aerial spraying for olive trees carried out in the past. The driver was not self-evident and included in order that we check the extension and the possible impact of such types of "indirect" pollution. The adopted description was: <i>"Understanding POLLUTION as the systematic degradation of natural resources due to intentional or unintentional human intervention. In the carob growing areas of Rethymnon, the pollution can be caused by aerial spraying, use of pesticides and / or elimination of processing products and production of other products (oil production or dairy production). Pollution can adversely affect carob pod production."</i>
Demographic changes	Land/harvesting abandonment due to ageing and declining population in mountainous and semi-mountainous areas, away from the urban centers (>10km). Farming occupation abandonment by younger generation. Loss of knowledge regarding grafting and pruning due to demographic changes and decades of harvesting abandonment has impacted pod production. The driver was self-evident for the MRL. The adopted description was: <i>"Understanding DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGES as the population aging and decline and the decline of agricultural activities in the mountainous areas of Rethymnon. In addition, demographic changes have caused a reduction in the number of carob cultivators and a loss of significant knowledge for the development, collection and production of carob."</i>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 101 Infographic of results in Crete MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends and sensitivity

About Ranking: According to the participants, the most dominant driver of change for the carob production in the MRL is the demographic changes that have affected and continue to affect it, along with the land-use change that have taken place, mainly in favour of the olive-tree cultivation. The climate change drivers follow, although most of the participants do not seem to have a clear perception of their importance. Mainly the scientific community raised the driver of the pests and invasive species, and it was evaluated mainly as a future threat.

About trends: The demographic changes, the land-use change and the temperature have been indicated as the drivers with a sharp increase in the last 20 years. Wildfires are considered non-existent in the MRL. Over exploitation and soil physical degradation have remained more or less constant, whereas pollution has exhibited a slight increase, which, according to the stakeholders, has not affected the carob production.

According to the stakeholders' perception, climate change related drivers (precipitation, temperature, extreme events and invasive species) seem to continue in the same trend as in the past 20 years. The only change of trend is foreseen for the land use, mainly because of the climate change and the anticipated turn to more resilient crops like carob.

About sensitivity: The actual or potential degree to which carob pod production in the MRL is modified or impacted by disturbances and therefore sensitive to climatic parameters such as precipitation and temperature is very difficult to predict due to the very diverse micro-climatic and edaphic conditions even in neighbouring orchards. The marked "on-off" pattern in carob pod production is apparently not related to climatic conditions according to the participants, making sensitivity indicators difficult to pinpoint rendering predictions next to impossible. The dearth in research regarding the productivity of the local carob cultivars accentuates the complexity. Nevertheless, it is a crucial issue for the local carob industry.

List of adaptive mechanisms

The participants identified the three most prevalent drivers of change affecting carob pod production in the land use systems of the MRL of Rethymno. These are: demographic changes, changes in land use and climate change through extreme events. The resulting recommendations that were verified by the participants, and the mechanisms that were formed from them, are as follows:

- Mechanism 1: Research

Academic research on carob species / cultivars has been identified as a mechanism of great importance by both participants and research (Kyrtzis et al., 2021) The academic community underlined that the dearth in knowledge of the Cretan species/cultivars of carob, vulnerabilities, and processing capacities, as well as their impact in natural preservation, in human health and in the economic life limits carobs' contribution to social and economic capital (Antonioni et al., 2021). One main parameter of research is how the different cultivars adapt to climate change, particularly in Crete's diverse climatic and edaphic conditions. Researchers from the University of Crete and

other research centres in Greece have already started coordinated efforts on the study of carob its cultivars and propagation difficulties. Such academic knowledge on carob is crucial. Knowledge on the adaptive capacity of carob trees and pod production may be impacted favourably from the line research that has just begun.

Two directions have been indicated within this mechanism. The first (1.1) is underway, whereas the second (1.2) has been proposed by the experts and should be taken into consideration.

- Mechanism 1.1: Research on different species of carob trees, the available cultivars, their reproductive capacities, and their enemies
- Mechanism 1.2: Research on the effects climate change leading to predictions regarding its impacts on the different crops in the region
- Mechanism 2: Policies

According to the experts an intrinsic weakness of public policy is that different planning decisions and actions occur from authorities at separate levels of governance. Regarding carob, a contradiction was identified between the policy of central government and the regional authorities. A major problem for the cultivation of carob is the regulations for agroforestry land use systems, which permit very constrained exploitation of trees – including carob trees. At the same time, the Region of Crete has a keen interest in the promotion of the cultivation of carob trees all over the island, particularly in semi-mountainous and mountainous areas, large parts of which have recently been characterized as forests.

The need for a holistic and comprehensive plan within the MRR has been recognized in order to overcome policy incompatibilities. Since prefectural agricultural directorates apply agricultural and environmental policies, a systematic support scheme for the cultivation of carob must be developed and put into effect. Toward these ends, local authorities should be equipped with trained human capital and resources to support and monitor carob cultivation and pod production.

Training is of paramount importance for the local communities. Due to demographic changes, knowledge on carob cultivation has dwindled and not passed on. Moreover, new knowledge is being produced and must be disseminated to farmers.

Finally, the experts delineated four different directions for actions leading to policy development, barrier removal and movement forward that can bolster the adaptive capacity and sustainability of carob pod production:

- Mechanism 2.1: Development of a holistic plan with measures to avoid abandonment and promotion of population retention in the region
- Mechanism 2.2: Development of systems of support from agricultural directorates
- Mechanism 2.3: Formal Education and Training for farmers
- Mechanism 2.4: Adequacy of policies and regulations regarding agroforestry land use systems
- Mechanism 3: Knowledge Exchange/ Acquisition

During the interviews and the workshop of T3.3 the need of information, of knowledge exchange amongst the farmers and direct communication between farmers and researchers for transfer of knowledge was underlined. The building of a community of practice to brace and reinforce the afore mentioned could support and improve communication as well as function as a steward for future planning particularly towards overseeing the development and adaptation of responsive strategies.

This last mechanism was considered separately in order to demonstrate and underline the importance of communication and collaboration amongst all CoP participants and the runoff and continuance of MOVING's mission.

- Mechanism 3.1: Communal Collaboration to transfer knowledge regarding carob cultivation and increasing awareness regarding responsive strategies and adaptation

07 - Transdanubian Mountains. Hungary

Context

Study case: Transdanubian Mountains Hungary

Value Chain name: Agroecological knowledge - Cold Mountain Shelter knowledge economy

Land-use system name: Mosaic land use system

Photo 102. Land use system in Cold Mountain Shelter

Photo 103. Land use system in Cold Mountain Shelter

Source: Rural BT

Figure 104 Map of the land use system based on crops Transdanubian Mountains

Source: MOVING project (WP3)

Short Description land-use system

Cold Mountain Shelter is a small community of young, educated environmentally conscious lifestyle migrants, creating, living and spreading knowledge on sustainable livelihoods. They produce food through permaculture, forest agriculture, contour farming, extensive animal husbandry, etc. Though, their main product is knowledge on sustainable livelihoods. They organise courses, events, exhibitions in permaculture, sustainable water management, construction and community building. Through a nation-wide association of lifestyle migrants (All-goes-together Association) they are creating an online knowledge platform to share environmental- and community friendly technology (both innovative and traditional) organise a yearly festival and help to develop local and regional nodes of environmentally conscious communities.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable is **the quantity of healthy food produced through mosaic land use in agro-ecological farming in and around the Cold Mountain Shelter area**. The production process is partly creating the basis for the creation of knowledge and to produce healthy food, partly consumed by the members of the local community partly processed and sold to people, coming to their courses (thus buying the knowledge too).

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Figure 105 Driver description and components in Transdanubian Mountains

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	<p>Changes in precipitation regime. The most important element in the "variability" of precipitation is that its distribution, quantity and intensity have become uneven and unpredictable both within one year and between years. Dry autumns and springs, winters without snowfall, with most of the precipitation falling in the form of summer showers accompanied by long periods of drought are typical.</p> <p>All this weakens extensive crops without irrigation, make them vulnerable and significantly reduce the quality and quantity of food produced. Badly timed rainfall causes further problems in orchards (lack of pollination, rot, disease).</p>
Temperature	<p>Temperature variability is characterised by increasing heat content and hectic, highly variable temperature conditions. Long, hot summers with persistent heat waves, mild winters and occasional short periods of severe cold have become common. The seasons are shifting, with spring practically disappearing.</p> <p>Mild winters do not kill off pests, and in addition, vegetation starts too early, with late frosts and prolonged warm spells causing damage to gardens and orchards. However, a longer growing season can also be beneficial in intensive crops.</p>
Extreme events	<p>Changes in extreme weather events are characterised by increased frequency and severity of prolonged periods of drought, heat waves, hailstorms, thunderstorms, torrential downpours, micro-floods, late frosts. These can result in significant water and wind erosion, and summer heat waves coupled with drought can significantly reduce the quantity and quality of food produced from extensive farming. Spring frosts and storms severely damage orchards.</p>
Land-use and land-cover change	<p>Land use intensive and holiday. In the abandoned parts of the hillside, many plots of land are changing hands, land cover and cultivation. Some areas are being turned into holiday homes, cleared and developed for housing. In other areas, agricultural entrepreneurs plant vineyards and other intensive standing crops. As a result, vegetation cover is reduced and urban pressure (buildings, roads, litter, other pollution) increases. Gardens in holiday homes are generally not cultivated (grass desert). Intensive cultivation often continues old bad practices, causing further soil degradation and pollution. New plantings (deep tilling, repeated soil rotation) significantly increase the risk of erosion.</p>
Land-use and land-cover change	<p>Land use Agro-ecological production. Agro-ecological, regenerative farming has been started in the area of the Cold Mountain shelter by environmentally conscious urban families with high cultural capital, through mosaic land use, involving significant knowledge and innovation and labour. As a result, eroded soils are being restored, forested areas are being converted into cultivated land and productivity is being improved. Land-use change may temporarily reduce the value of the area from a conservation point of view, but in the long term it benefits the area.</p>
Soil physical degradation	<p>As a result of decades of poor management, erosion by water and wind in exposed areas, especially due to sudden high rainfall, slow humus formation, thin, eroded topsoil, difficult to fertilize. This results in significant soil degradation, erosion, poor water holding capacity, low nutrient content.</p>

Over-exploitation of resources	Overuse of resources can be observed in the areas of overgrazing, deforestation, overuse of slowly renewing aquifers (for irrigation), and overuse of human labour, self-exploitation. As a result, soils can deteriorate further, deforestation and overgrazing can increase wildlife damage, and human self-exploitation can lead to displacement and system collapse.
Pests and invasive species	Invasive species and diseases. The emergence of natural and artificial enemies of pests, insects: nut fly, bedbugs, cherry borer, invasive plants: ragweed, bindweed, silk borer, slugs, bacteria, nematodes. They are difficult to control, they attack, weaken and destroy plants, reduce the quality and quantity of products, and reduce diversity.
Demographic Changes	Demography - gentrification. The area has become fashionable, property has become very expensive, sold out, there are many land deals and new owners. Producers cannot buy land to expand production, conflicts between actors due to different land uses, cultural background become frequent.
Demographic Changes	Demography - eco-community. The eco-conscious farming community on Cold Mountain brings significant knowledge and labour into production, with other newcomers creating a new, solvent demand for local produce.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 106 Infographic of results in Transdanubian Mountains

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: The most important drivers based on the questionnaire were precipitation, temperature and erosion. These are the factors that local producers must battle with every day. However, the two, interconnected directions of demography and land-use changes are very strong, definitive factors for the medium-long term. Wildfire is not an issue in the area, though as a potential danger was mentioned by various interviews, it did not include amongst the drivers. Pollution was not too relevant either, so it was decided to leave it out too.

About trends: Concerning past trends and future projection the answers to the questionnaire were highly scattered, and especially for future projection we received many 'I don't know' answers. This is especially true for climate related drivers. Precipitation problem trends, for example, were classified both growing and reducing during the past 20 years. Socio-cultural drivers (land use change and demography) were interpreted much more clearly by respondents.

About sensitivity: Patterns of sensitivity differed significantly of the ranking results. Far the most important was considered soil degradation, however, precipitation and temperature, that were the most important in the ranking, were way down the line here. Our suspicion is that this is because of the VC actors are already counting with some adaptation when planning, and this could not be taken out of the context at the workshop however we tried. Very strong potential negative is carried by our Demographic changes (gentrification) – displacement driver, representing the trend of rich urban people and agricultural entrepreneurs buying up abandoned land and turning it into holiday homes or intensive plantations, subsequently, squeezing out other owners and sustainable agricultural production from the area. The positive drivers, Demographic changes and land-use (eco-communities) – representing the actors participating in the VC and their agro-ecological practices have potentially very positive effects on the amount of food produced through sustainable land management is also important. It was predictable, though it was also reinforced by the external participants of the workshop.

List of adaptive mechanisms

We had 42 adaptive capacity ideas after processing the interviews, in 7 categories: (1) Physical circumstances of farming (no tillage, e.g.); (2) Holistic circumstances of farming (diversity, planning, etc.); (3) Water management (contour ditches, ponds, etc.); (4) Varieties; (5) legal environment; (6) communication; (7) technological solutions. On the workshop they selected 8 of these as most important ones for the local production. We then went through the points of the analysis.

- Variety choice: **Resistant, drought and heat tolerant vine and fruit varieties**
New, resistant vines and fruit varieties, planted in the right place and in the right way, tolerate the new conditions much better, without the need for spraying, fertilising, and watering. However, they are not called the classic varieties (Italian Riesling) and this causes marketing difficulties for the vine.

- Management, physical: **Water retention through ditches, terraces**
Building terraces, with the right scale and the right choice helps build soil, eliminate degradation
- Management, holistic: **Diversification, small scale**
Many types of products, something is always growing, small-scale production system, quality and products change every year, this makes the activity authentic, no big machines on a small scale, good for the soil
- Management, holistic: **Monitoring, conscious, adaptive planning, management, trial and error, experimentation**
We must consciously monitor, record and analyse the environmental impact, the harvest, the results of the various actions, and always plan the next steps on the basis of these. Think ahead.
- Management, holistic: **Area appropriate farming.**
Well-chosen site, no farming perpendicular to the contour lines
- Management, holistic: **Permaculture design**
Complex, system-level complex landscape planning. High degree of adaptation to the natural environment
- Legal: **In addition to architects, climate and social scientists are needed to define 'local building codes'**
They can adequately control urbanisation pressures, built-up areas, social processes
- Water retention: **Water retention, collection, and storage of rainwater - creation of cisterns**
More irrigation is needed every year, a storage tank should be built, the land is sloping and there is a lot of roof space, all this could be used, an underground tank of 20-30 cubic meters should be built

08 - Central Apennines. Italy

Context

Study case: Caciocavallo cheese.

Value Chain name: Alto Molise dairy production. Caciocavallo cheese.

Land-use system name: Agro-silvo-pastoral system (largely relevant for the VC).

Photo 107. Cows grazing

Source: Giuseppe Nucci;

Photo 108. Traditional local Caciocavallo cheese

Source: Letizia Bindi

Figure 108: Land use system map in Central Apennines

Source: MOVING Project (WP3) according to *Malek and Verburg, 2017*

Figure 109: Land system map in Central Apennines

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Levers et al, 2018*

Short description land-use system

The Central Apennines MRL is a hilly-mountainous zone with a few valleys close to rivers and streams. Towns are located between 1,421 and 806 meters MSL. The close UNESCO biodiversity reserve “Collemeluccio-Montedimezzo” and other natural parks/areas confirm the high territorial biodiversity. As accurately reported in the land-use system map, the context presents mainly extensive pastures and wood areas involved in the agro-silvo-pastoral economy, such as the livestock sector (cheese and meat) and forestry-related products (wood, honey, and truffles). Intense annual crops are limited, and natural forests are mainly present. In MRL prevail low-intensity livestock farming and low-intensity grassland areas.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

Permanent grasslands and meadows. Cheese productions characterise MRL, and the dairy value chain connects the environmental setting, particularly permanent grasslands and meadows, with livestock farming (in the past linked to the transhumance practice) and socio-cultural heritage (e.g., mountain farming and artisan culture). In particular, a high quality “caciocavallo cheese” (a symbol of the MRL and a DPO food) needs to be made with raw milk from grazing cows in mountain permanent grasslands and meadows. In this way, cheeses acquire peculiar sensory features, and mountain grazing contributes to territorial management. At the same time, farming costs, milk prices, and depopulation reduce mountain grazing, while climate change affects permanent grasslands and meadows productivity.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 75: Driver description and components in Central Apennines

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought (rains and snowfall). Very relevant. Precipitation is one of the most relevant factors that affect "grassland resource". Rainfalls are increasingly intense and distribute in a not usual manner (long period of drought and short intense storm). Snowfalls are also lower, and snowpack is less persistent. This situation changes the hay-mowing period.
Temperature	Very relevant. Grassland is suffering by the unusually and more frequent high temperature in summer and low in winter. It is becoming difficult to forecast temperature trends. For this, the area records relevant dry grassland and changing in the mowing period (anticipated or postponed). Temperature also affects hay quality & quantity. Sudden thermal changes also hit livestock health or fertility, and consequently, milk production.
Extreme events	Late frosts. Relevant. Some extreme events negatively influence the "grassland resource". During haymaking period events like very intense and consistent rains, high temperature and hot wind or hailstorms during. Those events contribute to hydro-geological instability. However, late frost (in spring) is becoming frequent and seem the most dangerous event for grassland.
Wildfire	Potentially relevant. Not recorded significant wildfires in the area. However, last summer (2021), there was a large fire that affected woods zones. Wildfires could be a problem for "grassland resources" forced by some drives (e.g., woods mismanagement and uncultivated/unused lands) in the following years.
Pollution	Not relevant. Pollution does not affect the "grassland resource" due to the absence of pollutant sources in the area related to urban lifestyles, industries, or agricultural activities.
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Wildlife (e.g., boar). Potentially relevant. Now, these aspects are not relevant on the "grassland resource". However, some drives could affect it, making these elements more significant (e.g., increasing some dangerous weeds already recorded in the area). One relevant problem is the increase presence of wild boars that compromises the quality of soil for agriculture.
Over-exploitation of resources	Not relevant. The "grassland resource" is underutilized or sustainably exploited. Depopulation seems the main cause of the underutilisation of grassland.

Demographic changes	Ageing & population decline. Very relevant. Despite some young people is engaged in managing or opening new farming and several dairies support/need breeder activities (specifically in Agnone), the area records depopulation, ageing of population and contraction in workforce turnover in agriculture / breeding businesses. Moreover, the immigrate workforce does not reduce the trend. It deeply affects "grassland resource" (increasing of uncultivated/unused land and territorial mismanagement, contraction of livestock & breeders, etc.).
Soil physical degradation	Erosion and fertility loss. Relevant. If cattle's droppings and the woods advancement can enrich the soil, climate events are compromising the soil quality in the area. Higher temperatures "pulverize" the soil, intense rainfalls erode the soil surface, less persistent snowpack contributes to reduce soil ability to store water. Moreover, depopulation (and the consequent farmers/breeder's contraction) outlines land mismanagement, contributing to compromise the soil.
Land-use and land-cover change	Renaturation (woods expansion). Relevant. Although some farmer (try to) grows new crops and the traditional family vegetable garden is still present in the area, there is a trend in grassland abandonment and the increase of uncultivated/unused lands due to the contraction of farms number. It leads to the disappearance of "tratturi" (livestock tracks) and useful channels for agriculture. It also leads change in the vegetation (brushes & not suitable herbs for grazing emerge) and woods increase while grassland disappears. For this, they record loss of biodiversity as well as lower hay quality & milk.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 110: Infographic of results in Central Apennines

Comments on the results about ranking, trends and sensitivity

About Ranking: It was clear that the most relevant drivers that affect permanent grassland and meadows are 4 (precipitation, temperature, demographic change and extreme events). These drivers in part affect the other relevant ones, while two are not important ("pollution" and "over-exploitation"). In addition to climate change, there is a complaint that demographic change reduce the chance to identify appropriate actions to face the climate change. During the workshop, the MAP validated the drivers' rank; nevertheless, it stressed that wild boars (in driver "pests, diseases, and invasive species") affect the reference variable in some areas of the MRL.

About trends: Data and information collected confirm that the "demographic change" driver seems crucial for the reference variable. Depopulation declined markedly in the past, and the perceived trend is a dramatic contraction that will affect territorial governance and grazing activities. Other drivers that will continue to worsen in the future are the climatic ones (precipitation, rainfall and extreme events). Still, for climatic drivers, the trend seems to be less dramatic than depopulation. Other drivers are considered irrelevant both in the past and future (such as accidents or pollution). Emerge the idea that the population can put (or push for) mitigation and resilience actions, but this is compromised by population reduction and ageing.

About sensitivity: During the workshop, the chance to face the climatic-demographic changes affecting the reference variable seems not particular high because the most relevant driver (demographic change), that seems related to others, tends to increase and it will negatively impact the possible adaptive responses. Nevertheless, some adaptive responses have been proposed. The current shifting trend in livestock activity from grazing to stables, feeding cows with fodder produced or purchased, is a change that is occurring. This shift partially explains why on other drivers (change in land use, physical deterioration of the soil, etc.), there is no clear predominant opinion, even if MAP stakeholders assume a worsening trend for them that will negatively influence the reference variable. In short, the reference variable risks being less relevant for the value chain as a consequence of current adaptive initiatives despite it characterizes the MRL's dairy value chain and it is the pivotal variable for some cheesemakers.

List of adaptive mechanisms

This work activity identified ten adaptive mechanisms to face climatic-demographic changes that affect the reference variable. These mechanisms may have different impacts on drivers of change. On the one hand, the mechanisms linked to new cultivation practices or experiments (new vegetable varieties or the better use of existing reservoir) appear more viable to implement. In contrast, those related to agriculture and territorial policies (new quality standards for milk, new grazing services, new reservoirs, etc.) seems less feasible due to the complexity necessary for their implementation. On the other hand, solutions linked to business innovations that imply a higher business risk (business diversification, technological innovation, breeding experiments, etc.) seem to have low availability. Local livestock farms are small companies, and it is tough for them to invest in innovative solutions. In this sense, agriculture policy initiatives can promote the innovation processes to preserve the reference variable by improving the profitability and services

related to the sector. In addition, the different mechanisms seem to influence the contraction of the negative impacts of precipitation and temperature, soil erosion and change in land use, and demographic change. However, the assessment is "slight positive impacts".

Below, some examples to describe each of ten adaptive mechanisms.

- **Technological innovation:** introduction of machineries useful to collect, processing and store hay and herbs in advance to reduce adverse climate events (e.g., spring frosts).
- **New farm practices:** adopting some farm practices (like the organic farming) that increase the market chances for local farmers preserving the environment and local natural resources.
- **Cultivation experiments:** introduction of new vegetable varieties that are arid resistant that reduce the damage of rain variability.
- **Breeding experiments:** try to introduce new cow varieties (or to reintroduce local traditional ones like the “podolica”) that can produce milk in worst climate conditions reducing farm costs.
- **Business diversification:** To reduce economic damages for climate causes, diversifying farm the activity (e.g., rural tourism, goat and sheep breeding, energy production with animal by-products).
- **Socio-territorial services:** increasing services like health, transportation and so on can help people to continue to live in those areas reducing disadvantages to be in a mountain area and increasing the attractive for business.
- **Grazing services:** in order to reduce climate pressure on grazing activity, would be useful to increase services like water supply in mountain graze areas to reduce water stress for animals.
- **Area mapping/monitoring:** common pasturing areas are not clearly defined, and it does not help an adequate management of those lands (e.g., some farmers obtain to use those areas for years reducing the possibility for others).
- **New standards for milk quality:** milk price is defined considering just few aspects (e.g., rate of fat) but it does not take in consideration other elements that characterize the quality of mountain milk production reducing the profitability of this activity. A new standard can help farmers to continue their activity in mountain.
- **Artificial reservoirs:** improve or build new water reservoirs to collect more water that is abundant in unusual period of year. In this way in dry period, it will be possible to obtain water for farming.

09 - Eastern Alps. Italy

Context

Study case: Eastern Alps

Value Chain name: Trento Doc Wine - Mountain viticulture in Alto Trentino

Land-use system name: Permanent cropland

Photo 111 and 2 Vineyards in Alto Trentino

Source: UNIMOL

Figure 112: Map of the land-use system within the Eastern Alps MRL

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Levers et al. 2018*

Short Description land-use system

The land use system is a permanent cropland: vineyards for to wine production. In Trento province, grape cultivation for quality wines production covers more than 12000ha, 14% of them above 500m on sea level. The specific territorial situation, from the geological and pedological point of view, is characterised by large central valley and several smaller later valleys. Vineyards at higher altitude are often grown on terraces, strongly connected to the mountain landscape. In the higher areas, vineyards are not grown on large plots but are intertwined with other land use systems (orchards, pasture, meadows, forest).

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

We have defined the reference variable as the **vineyard productivity and grape quality**, as these two key parameters determining wine production in the region are the most vulnerable in the face of different drivers of change.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 76: Driver description and components Eastern Alps

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. Changes in intensity, frequency, distribution along the seasons of rainfall. For "high altitude viticulture in Trentino", the most relevant element is intense rainfall events alternated with long periods of drought. This has a significant impact on the water availability and, consequently, on soil structure and plants development, as well as on pathogens. Among the consequences, landslides should be mentioned and collapses that compromise production in long term, have negative effect on vineyard productivity and, especially if during the flowering period, increase the risk of infections.
Temperature	it refers to the increase in average temperatures, especially in the intermediate seasons (spring and autumn) with a potential (but also already concrete) influence on the vegetative cycle of the vineyard and the biological cycles of pathogens and parasites. Increasing temperature allows grapes to grow at altitude, where ripening takes place more slowly with the development of aromas, while maintaining acidity. A general anticipation of the vegetative cycle makes evident the positive effect of planting vineyards in higher altitudes in order to have a later harvest. Increasing temperature can interfere with the severity of certain pathogens (e.g., downy mildew). The earlier development of vegetation in Spring increases the risk of frost damage.
Extreme events	Changes in the intensity, frequency, or seasonality of extreme events (heavy rainfalls, wind, heat peaks, hail, etc.). For "high altitude viticulture in Trentino", the main components are the episodes of intense rainfall, hail and the risk of spring frosts. Hail becomes more frequent over the last years and level of damage can be extremely variable, sometimes up to 100% of annual production. Late frosts have the same frequency as in the past, but the earlier plant development increases the risks: at high altitudes risk is lower because they occur in periods of vegetative rest, as germination happens later.
Wildfire	This driver is not relevant within the MRL.
Pollution	Contamination of soil, water (surface and groundwater) or atmosphere by discharge/spillage of harmful substances. In the MRL context the danger is represented mostly by water and soil pollution by pesticides (insecticides, herbicides, fungicides including copper...) also used in viticulture. Air pollution should be considered as well in certain areas (traffic from tourism, but not only).
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Pest. Changes in the intensity and frequency of pests and pathogens, both native and invasive. The main components are: increasing incidence of <i>Flavescence dorée</i> (could be caused by increasing temperatures), increasing <i>Drozophila Suzukii</i> attacks, changes in the biological cycles of some pathogens, increasing incidence and distribution of downy mildew and powdery mildew. Another problem in some areas is wildlife (ungulates, bears).

Over-exploitation of resources	In Trentino there is a growing risk of an excessive water withdrawal for vineyard irrigation in the context of gradually rising temperatures and prolonged drought periods and the low water stocking capacity of soils. The vineyard at higher altitudes lacks collective water management systems (that can be developed if needed), while in areas of viticulture expansion water storage systems become undersized. Irrigation needs to be reviewed with the aim of harmonising water use with a view to be saving quantity and using it in the right way for quality.
Demographic changes	“Demographic change” refers to the depopulation of rural areas in high mountains, the abandonment of marginal and diffuse villages and localities, as well as small-scale farming activities and difficulties in generational change in agriculture. The problem exists but it is not as heavy as in other areas, in last year’s newcomers into farming established back in remote areas. The combination of tourism and farming plays a relevant role in appealing young people and assuring jobs and revenues. Small scale/family farming is decreasing but still present (more than in other areas). The role of women is changing slowly and remains marginal in agricultural business in leading roles.
Soil physical degradation	Physical deterioration of soil due to loss of organic matter through erosion, poor tillage, or excessive compaction. Main components in the MRL: erosion and landslides caused by heavy rainfalls where a loss of organic matter due to tillage (depending on specific agricultural practices) occurs, cases of water logging.
Land-use and land-cover change	it refers to the abandonment of pastures, where woodland mostly takes over, and only a small part of those abandoned areas are used for new vineyards.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 113: Infographic of results Eastern Alps

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: the results of pre-workshop questionnaire showed clearly that climatic drivers (except wildfires) are considered the most important ones. Regarding endogenous drivers it's evident the big concern about pest and diseases, which has emerged already during the interview stage. It was surprising to see relatively high scores gained by pollution driver, while during the interviews it did not seem an important issue for the area. The reason could be that the participants of interviews were more concentrated on the reference variable, while during online questionnaire they were perceiving pollution as a problem on a global scale. The high variability in the responses regarding demographic change driver can be explained by presence of two opposing trends: depopulation of rural areas in the mountains in the 60s and 80s and later a partial return to agriculture, combined with other activities (e.g., tourism). It can also be interpreted as very site specific, meaning that it varies among valleys.

About trends: the perception of past trend is quite connected to the perception of driver's importance. As expected, according to the respondents the trend has increased the most over the last 20 years for the following drivers: increasing temperatures, pest and diseases, extreme events. There is a less homogeneous perception of the pollution driver: some participants consider that the situation generally became better over the last years, other still have the impression of an increasing trend.

About sensitivity: Sensitivity survey results are a bit more difficult to analyse: the participants were working in small groups (4 and 6 people), and sometimes were a little bit confused regarding the repeatability of the questions as mentioned in section 2. Anyhow, the results stand in line with importance and past trends perception. A very important point is the fact that the majority of participants sees the effect of increasing temperature on mountain viticulture positively. It was already mentioned during the interview stage that viticulture in higher altitudes could be a solution to contrast the climate change problems in valleys.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Respect of vocationalist in the choice of vine varieties, including resistant varieties**
For new plantings in mountain regions the rootstock and the clones must be chosen in function of the pedo-climatic, market and regulatory conditions foreseen for the future, considering the use of new crossbreeding grape varieties with resistance to the main vine pathogens to reduce treatment
- **Longer rest period before replanting vineyards**
Due mainly to regulatory restrictions (National regulation on grape-vine planting rights) and to farm economic approaches, when a vineyard is uprooted the new one is replanted immediately after, usually within 12 months. For the prevention of pest and diseases and to allow a better structuring of the soil, it would be advisable to wait a longer period before replanting (3 years at least) and in the meanwhile the soil should be covered with cover crops. The implementation of the mechanism would require a regulatory change.

- **Maintain territorial biodiversity (different crops, and presence of wild areas)**
To increase functional biodiversity at landscape area (beyond the farm) increases the resilience of vineyards towards pest and diseases. It increases the presence of beneficials but also created micro-climates that contribute to decrease pest and disease presence.
- **Farms multifunctionality (combination of viticulture with animal husbandry) that is directly linked to family farming**
For healthy vineyards soil fertility and vitality is key. Extensive animal husbandry, with the use of fodder and pasture and the side-production of manure is beneficial to viticulture soils as the manure can be used as fertilizer and pasture and fodder crops can precede and alternate to vineyards (see point 4). Extensive animal husbandry and mixed farming can be implemented only by family farms, where labour can be shared and farm income benefits from diversification of the offer (including touristic offer).
- **Sectional sub-irrigation with moisture sensors for precision irrigation**
Water scarcity in mountain vineyards depends on the thickness of cultivable soil, drainage capacity, greatly variable within the same lot. Precision sub-irrigation controlled by sensors in the soil can help in reducing both water usage and vine stress.
- **Wrap-around nets**
Plastic nets covering the canopy on the top and on both sides, protect the vines from insects attack and reduce wetting of the vegetation and therefore incidence of fungal diseases. The nets should be installed late in the summer, when the growth of shoots has ended
- **DSS based on simulation models for the selection of new areas for high altitude viticulture**
Decision Support System can be very useful in reducing number of treatments while decreasing the risk of pathogen attack, although the mathematical models at their bases should be adapted to the different environmental conditions of the vineyards in altitude

10 - Northern Apennines. Italy

Context

Study case: Northern Apennines

Value Chain name: Chestnut flour

Land-use system name: High intensity plant forest / Agroforestry

Photo 114. Large chestnut trees

Source: Leaf Creations

Photo 115. The traditional metato and its chestnut grove

Source: Simone Batini

Photo 116. Apuan alps before the sunset (on the right)

Source: Leaf Creations

Figure 117: Crop Map in the MRL, Seravezza and Stazzema in the Apuan Alps

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *d'Andrimont et al 2018*

Short Description land-use system

The land-use system at theoretical level is **High intensity plant forest** or agroforestry (Type 1) in practices considering the different level of abandonment we are in an agroforestry in abandonment (Type 2) or in a mixed forest dominated by chestnuts (Type 4). In the next future the land use could become Type 3 and Type 5. Nowadays, the land use of the area presents a structure dominated by the forest vegetation, extending from the bottom of the valley up the mountain top, where pastures are still prevailing along the ridges of the highest mountain (Pania della Croce). The most common forest types are those characterized by the presence of chestnut (64%), these are followed by stands with the presence of hornbeam (about 20%) and other typologies of forest.

Chestnut flour is produced by secular chestnut tree planted from 500 meters to 1000 meter that usually represent the highest altitude.

Figure 118: Types of chestnut agroforestry systems

Source: “Sweet chestnut agroforestry systems in North-western Spain: Classification, spatial distribution and an ecosystem services assessment”, Forest Systems 2018

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable was the “**chestnuts tree varieties**” that influence the high quality of the chestnut flour but also the annual **production (quantity) of chestnuts**.

Due to climate change, some famous variety as carpinese, having a shorter cycle, are affect more than other by the drought. This means that it is important to have different varieties of chestnut plants.

Table 77: Driver description and components Northern Apennines

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	<p>Reduction of summer rainfall Alta Versilia is one of the Italian areas with the highest rainfall rate due to the combined effect of various factors. Precipitation in the study area is considered as the absence of rain in the late summer period (after the 15th of august). What is worrying is drought seen as the prevention between weakening of rain, rising temperatures and reduction of humidity. In drought, the chestnut slows down its functions and goes into summer seeds, but if it rains too late, the chestnuts cannot close the production cycle from flowers to seeds, because the plants begin to lose their leaves and are no longer able to complete the grow of the fruit.</p> <p>The early varieties, having a shorter cycle, are unable to recover the necessary water in September, this means that it is important to have different varieties of chestnut plants.</p>
Temperature	<p>Increasing in high temperature. The rise in temperatures combined with the lack of rain leads to drought. In recent years, the days with average temperatures above 35 degrees Celsius that damage the chestnut grove have increased. Very high temperatures reduce pollination (dry pollen), fertility and the quantity of chestnuts. Few or no direct solutions apart from planting trees at a higher altitude or in the forest located in the north part of the valley, where the temperature are lower compared to the south where the sun have a direct irradiation on the ground.</p>
Extreme Events	<p>Extreme Climatic Events. Due to the morphological configuration and the pluviometric characteristics, which produce very short run-off times, the Apuan Alps therefore represent one of the areas with the highest hydraulic risk in Italy. Extreme events certainly have an important role in the chestnut wood, but they do not appear to be the most impacting ones even if are quite frequent in the area. During the 1996 flood, the solid transport of rivers and streams was very significant due to the large amount of rock and vegetal debris mobilised by the landslides. It was estimated that about 175000 trees had fallen, due to the landslides, for a total volume of 41000 m cube of timber. In this extreme event, the large chestnuts contributed to the collapse of the woods, especially in the terms of timber volume (80,4%) and less in terms of trees numbers (4,7%) (Parco Regionale Alpi Apuane 2017, Rains and ruins in the Apuan alps for disaster risk reduction)</p>
Wildfire	<p>The wildfire does not appear to be so impacting compared to the other. In general, conifers have a greater flammability than deciduous broad-leaved trees such as chestnuts</p>
Pollution	<p>There isn't any problem of pollution</p>
Pests and invasive species	<p>Pest This driver is expressed in this case study as pests and diseases that cause weakness and death of trees. The main pest is: <i>Criphonectria parasitica</i> (since 1938), <i>Phitophrora cambivora</i> (since 1985), <i>Dryocosmus Kuriphilus</i> (since 2002) Parasites continue to be a problem despite the (<i>Dryocosmus Kuriphilus</i>) seems to have greatly reduced with the proliferation of its antagonist. As happened in Piedmont, where the wasp had spread before to arrive in the Apuan Alps, after ten years their number has strongly stabilized. In any case, the evolution of the gall wasp must be monitored carefully as it could resume expanding</p>

	<p>rapidly, should the antagonist insect fall. It is a classic example of relationship between prey and predator, where the contraction of the prey also involves the contraction of the predator.</p> <p>Recently (2019) also (<i>gnomoniopsis castanea</i>) have start to spread in Apuan Alps. The fungus is consistently associated with nut rot and caused the disease when artificially inoculated to fruits or flowers the quality of chestnut fruits can be affected in pre- and post-harvest by insects and moulds.</p>
Over-exploitation	<p>There are no problems in this direction. The number of chestnut trees per hectare is very high when compared with other areas, but this does not lead to excessive exploitation of the soil. The quarries, on the other hand, have a negative and unsustainable impact on the chestnut grove itself</p>
Demographic changes	<p>Historically in the mountains we have always had strong migrations towards abroad and towards the plains. At one time, however, the family structure was so numerous that there was always someone to whom to pass on the knowledge and carry out the management of the chestnut grove, today, on the contrary, it is very complex to have a generational change. Those who carry on this profession often come from the city. Today it is necessary to have a renewal, which is no longer familiar but with people who come from other territorial contexts. In this perspective, since the intergenerational transfer of knowledge is lacking, training is also essential through technical updating. Today we have a precision technology capable of dealing with climate change that is unlikely to spread to our mountains if it is not conveyed by technicians capable of solving local agronomic problems</p>
Soil physical degradation	<p>Soil Physical degradation caused by rainfall. At the moment, it does not appear to be one of the major problems even though drought could trigger soil degradation phenomena</p>
Land-use and land-cover change	<p>Land cover change. The present landscape distribution of chestnut woods is heavily linked to past human settlements. <i>Castanea sativa</i> is still the dominant species but, in many cases, the abandon of the last forty years has increased the grow of other species as: <i>Quercus pubescens</i>, <i>Prunus avium</i>, <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>, and <i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>. The absent of forest management and a specific forest planning that don't give the possibility to consider different aspect of the use of the forest.</p>
Demographic changes	<p>Lack of silvicultural practices. Abandon in the first component of absence of forest management, The absence of chestnut pruning, cleaning of the undergrowth from other broad-leaved trees, planting or grafting of new plants and any targeted irrigation in specific periods. The new technologies in forest management, harvesting and processing increase the productivity potential. The chestnut ecosystem in addition provides agro-forestry co-productions (honey, choice edible mushrooms, pasture, game, healthy plants, forage and litter) and externalities. The high landscape value of chestnut forests, created by centuries of human activity in the mountainous and hilly areas, can be enjoyed nowadays in Europe by low-impact tourism. (G Bounos 2005 The chestnut: A multipurpose resource for the new millennium)</p>
Pests and invasive species	<p>Wildlife Damage (animal Wandering). Wildlife compromises new chestnut plants, damages graft attempts and removes chestnuts for feeding</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 119: Infographic of results Northern Apennines

Comments on the results about ranking, trends and sensitivity

About Ranking: Usually we don't have note a large deviation from expected results the drivers that have obtain the bigger score are the lack of silvicultural practice (average 0,825), pest (average 0,8124) and reduction of summer precipitation (average 0,7624) Only in the case of wildlife damage (0,575) we aspect a lower result. The high variability of responses in the wildfire driver, could be caused by the different knowledge of participant.

About trends: The participants are aware of all the problematic whit a negative impact on the chestnut grove but in many cases, they have some difficulties to imagine the next future.

Save the mountain from the abandon do not appear an easy matter without an intensive public intervention and an active collaboration by the private people.

In any case the failed experience done in the last 26 years (after the flood of 1996) do not help to imagine a better future. In many case the stakeholders do not have a future projection (they say I don't Know).

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Maintenance of different varieties of chestnut trees with the creation of local forest nursery**

In the Apuan Alps forest are located different varieties of chestnut tree as: Carpinese, Salcese, Pelosola, Pontecosa, Mazzangaia, Verdola, Gentile, Rossola, Polano, Cardo polpo, Nerone, Gombitello This aspect is very important because give the possibility to maintain a constant production in the different years. Some variety as Carpinese has a yearly production. A high drought, in the last part of summer, is link with a high reduction in the plant productivity. For these reasons it is very important to have from early to late-ripening chestnut tree to avoid the absence of production during some years. The creation of small local forest nursery will be collecting all these varieties and give the possibility to local farmer to reproduce new chestnut trees with the graft techniques.

- **Introduce water save practices of irrigation in specific period of the year**
Usually, chestnut tree is not irrigated. To avoid climate change effects, could be important to introduce innovative irrigation, where it is economic sustainable, also in some specific period of the years to avoid drought stress to the plant. Usually in mountains there are many small streams but the water it is not harvesting in the right way. Chestnut trees located near this stream could be easy irrigated
- **Localisation of local monumental chestnut trees and reproduction of new plants with graft.**

Giant trees that have demonstrated long-lasting resilience to prolonged climatic events, such as the medieval warm period, the Little Ice Age, and modern anthropic pressure, constitute a conservation priority and an incredible source of information for eco-physiology, genomics, and productive studies.

In this context, it appears of great importance to search, inventory, and evaluate the genetic identity of large old chestnuts across the species range, in order to preserve the

capacity of adaptation and long-term survival to climate change, human pressure and new pests of its natural, naturalized,

- **Knowledge transfer**

Training and information to increase the transmission of local and traditional knowledge to the new generation. Collaboration projects (Technology centre, universities, owners). Interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder groups to generate synergies between technology, science, and local knowledge

- **Monitoring of pests:** Increase the activities that are already done

- **Increase the forest management reduction the abandon**

Consider the possibility given by Regional Forest Law to implement the "Forest Community" as a new way to forest management capable to reduce the abandon

11 - Maleshevski mountains. North Macedonia

Context

Study case: Rural tourism in Maleshevski mountains

Value Chain name: Rural tourism

Land-use system name: Mosaic/landscape of Maleshevski region (predominant medium intensity /natural forest)

Photo 120 : Landscape Maleshevija

Photo 121 : Landscape Maleshevija

Source: Darko Shumanski

Figure 122: Land use system map of Maleshevija

Source: MOVING Project (WP3) according to *Malek and Verburg, 2017*

Short Description land-use system

Maleshevski mountains are in the eastern part of the Republic of North Macedonia. Maleshevski region covers the municipalities of Berovo and Pehchevo and is characterized with the natural and cultural wealth. Two rivers cross the region, Bregalnica and Strumica. Forests covers 52% of the Maleshevija region, while pastures around 20%. Maleshevija is part of the National strategy for tourism development of North Macedonia. It has a big potential for alternative and rural tourism. Has a clear identity and very good natural resources for rural tourism development. There are hiking trails that are made for recreation, hiking, mountain biking, and enjoying the clean mountain air. The trails are part of the Balkan Mountaineering Transversal and are published in the mountain trials maps. There are numerous rapids, small cascades, and waterfalls (up to 10 m high) along the mountain rivers in the region.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

Landscape of Maleshevija. The destination of Maleshevija is visited by national and foreign tourists. Most of the tourists are keen to visit this region due to its landscape, calmness, and fresh air. Most products and services in the tourism sector served in Maleshevija are provided by local small enterprises and families, with a few exceptions. Because tourism is both produced and consumed at a local or 'destination' level, the best results are usually obtained. The tourism value chain in Maleshevija is linked to different industries from accommodation, restaurants, agricultural products, tourist guides, etc. until the banking sector.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 78: Driver description and components Maleshevski mountains

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. Precipitation is linked to drought. It causes low river flow of Bregalnica and Radevska river. Same happens with Pehchevski waterfalls. The water is falling lesser and lesser. Raining and snowing is rare. Production of potato in Maleshevija is reduced as well as other agricultural products in the region. This driver affects the reference variable negatively.
Temperature	Temperature is changed in Maleshevija. Short cold winters, fresher mornings and evenings during summer. The forest shrinks and goes up, due to beech trees, which need lower temperatures to keep the balance. This driver affects the reference variable negatively.
Extreme events	There is no evidence for any extreme events in the region of Maleshevija
Wildfire	Fires. There are wildfires in Maleshevija. Last year happened the biggest one. Pine forests suffered. The landscape from tourist point of view is damaged. More wolves in the countryside. Less oxygen from the forests. This driver affects the reference variable negatively
Pollution	Maleshevija in general is a clean area. There is no pollution. The threat of pollution is coming from a few small-scale production capacities. There is no big factory. Around Berovo lake, wastewater treatment plan is missing. This driver affects the reference variable negatively.
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Pest. The mountain pine pest, <i>Thaumatopea pityocampa</i> is massively causing weakening to pine trees. Aerial treatment with insecticide is a necessity. This driver affects the reference variable negatively.

<p>Over-exploitation of resources</p>	<p>Over-exploitation. Farmers in the region of Maleshevija are threatened from lesser water in the region, and this causes irrigation problems for agricultural products.</p> <p>This driver affects the reference variable negatively</p>
<p>Demographic changes</p>	<p>Emigration is occurring constantly in Maleshevija. More and more youth are leaving the region and replace it with urban life within the country or abroad. The skilled workforce for the tourism sectors is absent in the region.</p> <p>This driver affects the reference variable negatively.</p>
<p>Soil physical degradation</p>	<p>There is no soil degradation and erosion. This driver has neutral effect on the reference variable.</p>
<p>Land-use and land-cover change</p>	<p>Land use change. The Maleshevija region suffers from illegal logging from individuals, which negatively impacts the landscape. There is less arable land in the region.</p> <p>This driver affects the reference variable negatively</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 123: Infographic of results Maleshevski mountains

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: In general, participants highly ranked the main drivers such as: demographic changes, pine pests, temperature, precipitation, and wildfires, while less relevant: pollution, overexploitation, physical soil degradation and land use. The top-ranking driver is demographic changes, participants ranked it at highest level.

About trends: The projections for the future are not so encouraging. Participants envisaged almost all drivers to continue in the same direction and trend in the future period. The most challenging driver: the temperature, which is a global issue, the perception of participants are that it will continue with an upward trend in the future, while it negatively impacts many sectors in the Maleshevija region, including the rural tourism.

About sensitivity: The outcome of participants about sensitivity, emphasised that almost all drivers of change will be with an upward trend, and expected to have a negative impact over the main reference variable. Although there were differences in scoring points, the stakeholders agreed on the negative impact coming from the drivers of change.

List of adaptive mechanisms

Following there are the main recommendations on the adaptive capacity mechanisms for the main drivers of change.

- **Socio-economic development of Maleshevija** needs more attention by the central authorities (the national government of the country). Youth employment policy, opportunities, and privileges for opening a business, building the roads, and opening the cross border with Bulgaria.
- Regarding the proper water management in the Maleshevija region, public authorities should assure **sufficient water irrigation** for the agriculture in the reference region.
- Regarding pollution, it is required to set filters for **prevention of pollution** to production capacities in the region of Maleshevija. In this regard, it's needed to set up stations for monitoring and measuring the pollution, which are lacking.
- The participants required **more forest police in the region**, to exercise a greater control to the human factor in the forests of Maleshevija, aiming prevention from the fire. Faster response and coordination of fire services in case of forest fires.
- Further, was appealed to perform Aerial **treatment with insecticides against insects** in the forests of Maleshevija by the Crisis Management Centre.

12 - Cordilheira Central. Portugal

Context

Study case: Cordilheira Central

Value Chain name: Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese

Land-use system name: Extensive Open Rangeland (3), more specifically, highland and lowland pastures

Photo 124. Bordaleira da Serra da Estrela sheep breed flock

Source: Teresa Pinto-Correia

Photo 125. Serra da Estrela DPO Cheese

Source: www.queijaria-portuguesa.pt

Figure 126: Land systems at the Cordilheira Central MRL

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Levers et al. (2018)*

Short Description land-use system

Bordaleira da Serra da Estrela and Churra Mondegueira sheep breeds, that produce the milk for Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese, feed on common or private local pastures, at highlands (during summer) and lowlands (all year). Pastures may be of two types: 1) natural pastures – made up of spontaneous vivacious grasses and 2) cultivated pastures – constituted by white clover and underground clovers. Traditionally, shepherds would go to highland pastures with their sheep, during summer, where there is still green pasture at that time of year. Currently, there are fewer and fewer shepherds using highland pastures, as lowland ones are often enough for current animal numbers.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable for the vulnerability analysis is “**Pasture area**”. Pasture is the main feed resource for Bordaleira da Serra da Estrela and Churra Mondegueira sheep breeds which produce the milk for Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese. Pasture area has been decreasing in the last decades, because of the decrease in the number of shepherds (as this job is often seen as unattractive, due to being physically demanding, in sometimes harsh weather conditions, and with increasingly low profitability) and animal numbers. Shrub encroachment is, on the one hand, taking place of previously agriculture and pasture dedicated areas, due to land abandonment. On the other hand, it also poses a barrier to the maintenance of pastoral activity, as shrublands are often difficult to clean, due to rough terrain and lack of manpower, when shepherds want to recover pasture area. Less “Pasture area” means there are less animals and thus less milk to produce Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese. Some local actors do believe that this product is at high risk of disappearing.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 79: : Driver description and component Cordilheira Central

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. In Serra da Estrela we observed a reduction in Precipitation, in the form of rainfall and snowfall, with an impact on rivers and aquifers, on soil and on vegetation. The decrease in rainfall in spring and autumn reduces pasture productivity.
Temperature	In Serra da Estrela we observed an increase in annual and seasonal Temperatures. In higher altitude areas, higher temperatures in winter limit plant species that need the cold. In lower altitude areas, higher temperatures in summer benefit pasture productivity.
Extreme events	In Serra da Estrela we observed Extreme Events, such as changes in the intensity, frequency or timing of heat waves, storms, hail and frost. Summer heat waves negatively affect pasture productivity.
Wildfire	In Serra da Estrela we observed the Wildfires increase in intensity, frequency or timing. Intense and/or recurrent wildfires in summer destroy pastures, burning seeds, have a negative long-term impact on soils and pasture area, and alter forest areas and disturb the landscape pattern.
Pollution	In Serra da Estrela we did not observe Pollution, such as contamination of the soil, water (surface and underground), nor of the atmosphere by the discharge of harmful substances. This driver was not considered a problem for pastures.
Pests, diseases and invasive species	In Serra da Estrela we observed Pests, Diseases, and Invasive Species, as changes in the intensity and frequency of pests and diseases, both native and invasive. This driver has little effect on pastures. A low heather species is invading highland pastures. The Asian wasp is altering bee abundance and hence pollination.
Over-exploitation of resources	In Serra da Estrela we did not observe overexploitation of resources, such as overgrazing. This driver was not considered a problem for pastures.
Demographic changes	In Serra da Estrela we observed Demographic Changes, such as depopulation and population aging, which negatively affect the number of sheep and goat producers, increase land abandonment and alter traditional management systems.

Soil physical degradation	In Serra da Estrela we observed Soil physical degradation through soils loss of organic matter, due to erosion, and soils contamination, due to the use of agro-chemicals. Soil physical degradation is mainly due to fire, heavy precipitation, the machinery used for shrub clearing, and the use of agro-chemicals in some lowland pastures.
Land-use and land-cover change	In Serra da Estrela we observed Land use and land cover changes as changes in vegetation composition and/or density. Shrub encroachment is increasingly occupying former pasture areas. Shrub favours the wild boar abundance, which destroys crops for animal feed.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 127: Infographic of results Cordilheira Central

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: Despite the pre-workshop questionnaire having been sent to 21 stakeholders, only 5 responded, which can affect the representativeness of the results obtained. The most relevant drivers (considering the mean), in descending order, were Demographic Changes (0,88), Wildfires (0,84), Precipitation (0,72), Soil Physical Degradation (0,68), Land Use and Land Cover Change (0,68) and Temperature (0,68). From the semi-structured interviews experience, we anticipated that Demographic Changes was the most relevant driver influencing Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese value chain, as depopulation and population aging combined with hard work conditions and low rentability are limiting shepherds' generational renovation. Wildfires and Land Use and Land Cover Changes relevance was also expected to be high, as shrub encroachment, caused by agricultural land abandonment, is increasing the risk of fire which destroys peripheral pastures and degrades soil and is often difficult to clean when shepherds want to recover pasture area. The other relevant drivers mentioned above are mainly related to pasture productivity.

About trends: Regarding Precipitation and Temperature drivers, all actors who responded to the pre-workshop questionnaire pointed out that, in the last 20 years, the former has been decreasing and the latter increasing, and most expected these trends to continue in the next 20 years. In the case of Wildfire, we registered 2 different perceptions from local actors - some note that wildfires have remained constant, while others say they have sharply increased. Concerning Land Use and Land Cover Change, such as shrub encroachment, most respondents agree it has been increasing in the study area. Regarding Soil Physical Degradation, local actors show two different opinions - some believe it has remained constant while others perceive a slight increase. The former doesn't expect the trend they identify will continue in the next 20 years, while the later do.

About sensitivity: Stakeholders ranked very similarly the sensitivity of the reference variable to the different discussed drivers. It was also said that the impacts of precipitation and temperature cannot be addressed separately. The same is true for demographic changes and changes in land use and land cover. These two big groups in turn will dictate the incidence of wildfires.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Increase attractiveness of the territory** through maintenance and improvement of accessibility and infrastructures, and special tax benefits including housing bank in urban areas and land bank of abandoned areas
Improve the accessibility of the region, with better connections with nearby cities and within the region itself through public transports and improved roads. Create special benefits for the people living in the region or that want to move there, allowing them tax breaks. Have housing and land banks to make it easier for people looking for primary homes or land to work

- **Landscape and shrub management**, with support from other activities to the maintenance of the landscape (ex. tourism) and of the activities that maintain it
Have mechanisms that support landscape management, and in particular shrub management (which is deemed expensive and under subsidized under current policies). An example is a tourism tax that would be used to control shrubs as tourism also benefits from maintaining the landscape
- **Education and technical support for shepherds**
Have Technicians in the field available to support shepherds in practical matters as mastitis, pasture improvement, selective breeding, but also in administrative matters as in applications for subsidies.
- **Better adjusted CAP - favour native species, pay for grazing services, adapt the extensive grazing payment to the minifundium**, support to new entrants, regardless of their age
- **Pilot area to manage the landscape with fire and grazing**
Have a pilot area to define a plan to manage the landscape and prevent shrub encroachment through controlled fire and grazing, to understand what mechanisms work in promoting shepherding and how it can or not be concealed with controlled fire, that used to be the traditional way of clearing the land.
- **New governance models**. Both at the local level through more cooperation and associative and at a regional level to increase influence near political power
Promote cooperation and associative to gain scale. At the local level among the shepherds in the collection of milk so that they have more power in the transaction. At the regional level among municipalities and other stakeholders to have a bigger influence near political power and raise awareness to the particularities of the region.
- **Control of boar population**
Control the population of wild boars through hunting or other mechanisms such as reduce their refuges near pastures by clearing shrubs.

13 - Maciço Noroeste. Portugal

Context

Study case: Douro Superior

Value Chain name: Douro Wine Value Chain

Land-use system name: Permanent cropland

Photo 128 and 129: Vineyards in Douro Superior

Source: Vinidea

Figure 130: Map of the land-use system within the Maciço Noroeste MRL

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Levers et al. 2018*

Short Description land-use system

The Douro Demarcated Region (DDR) is the eldest demarcated and regulated region in the world, since 1756. It was elevated to “World Heritage of Humanity” by UNESCO for Cultural, Evolutive and Living Landscape in 2001. Another point of interest are the cave engravings of Vila Nova de Foz Côa, classified as World Heritage, by UNESCO, in 1998, that can be found displaced over an area of 200km².

The DDR includes two Designation of Origin (DO) Douro wine and Port wine for a total surface of 250 000ha of vineyard. This mountain region also has a considerable area of olive and almond trees

The soil is mostly compound by schists and granite with different textures and physical and chemical characteristics and a general low content of organic matter and carbon sources. Native wine grape varieties are particularly relevant.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

We have defined the reference variable as the vineyard productivity and grape quality, as these two key parameters determine wine production quality and value and are influenced by the different drivers of change.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 80: Driver description and components Maciço Noroeste MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought . Change in: intensity, frequency, seasonality (more rain in spring, less in September). For "mountain viticulture in the Douro Superior", the most relevant element is intense rainfall events. This has a significant impact on the structure of the soil, as well as on the biological cycle of pathogens. Among the consequences: landslides, increased risk of infections during the flowering period.
Temperature	Refers to the increase of average temperatures, with an influence on the vegetative cycle of the vine and the biological cycles of pathogens and parasites. The increase in temperature allows the grapes to grow at altitude, where maturation occurs more slowly with the development of aromas, while maintaining acidity. A general anticipation of the vegetative cycle in lower areas makes evident the positive effect of planting vines at higher altitudes in order to have a later harvest. The increase in temperature may interfere with the severity of certain pathogens (e.g. downy and powdery mildew). Earlier development of vegetation in spring (that is happening now in lower areas) increases the risk of frost damage.
Extreme events	Changes in the intensity, frequency or seasonality of extreme events (heavy rainfall, wind, heat peaks, hail, etc.). For " mountain viticulture in the Douro Superior ", the main components are episodes of intense precipitation, hail and the risk of spring frosts. Hail has been more frequent in recent years and can lead to a total loss of annual production. Frosts are a huge problem because of the earlier development of the plants: at high altitudes the risk is lower because they occur during periods of vegetative rest, since germination occurs later.
Wildfire	Fires . This driver is not relevant within the MRL.
Pollution	In the context of MRLs, the danger is represented mainly by soil pollution by pesticides (insecticides, herbicides, fungicides including copper...) used in viticulture.
Pests, diseases and invasive species	Pest . Changes in the intensity and frequency of pests and pathogens, both native and invasive. The main components are: existence of new pests such as golden flavescence, black rot; wood diseases and invasive species (Arundo donax, Ailanthus, Rhus)
Over-exploitation of resources	In Douro Superior, despite the possible need for vine irrigation, there are plenty of water reserves available. For this reason, we do not consider that this resource is under-exploited. We may speak of over-exploitation of the soil due to the growing area under vineyards, olive groves and almond trees.

Demographic changes	"Demographic changes" refers to the depopulation of rural areas in the mountain region (low birth rate and increased emigration), ageing of the population and the abandonment of young people for lack of qualified job opportunities. The problem exists and is growing exponentially.
Soil physical degradation	Physical deterioration of soil due to loss of organic matter, caused by poor tillage, leads to erosion. and excessive compaction. Consequently landslides, due to heavy rains, occur. All the process ends up in loss of soil fertility and loss of biodiversity
Land-use and land-cover change	Refers to the increase in the area under vineyards, olive groves and almond trees to the detriment of forest

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 131: Infographic of results Maciço Noroeste MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: The results of the pre-workshop questionnaire and interviews coincided on the drivers considered most important changes in temperature and precipitation and demographic changes. The demographic change was the factor that causes the greatest unanimous concern among stakeholders. It is already a problem and it is expected to increase exponentially. Also the preoccupation for land use system and soil degradation exist.

About trends: the perception of past trend is closely related to the perceived importance of the driver. The trend has increased more in the last 20 years for the following drivers: changes in precipitation and temperature, demographic changes and extreme events. There is a less homogeneous perception of land use and land cover change, soil physical degradation.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Respect of vocationality in the choice of vine varieties, including resistant varieties**
For new plantings in mountain regions the rootstock and the clones must be chosen in function of the pedo-climatic, market and regulatory conditions foreseen for the future, considering the use of new crossbreeding grape varieties with resistance to the main vine pathogens, in order to reduce treatment
- **Planting vines in areas of higher altitude**
The plantation of vines at higher altitudes is seen as an alternative to climate change (increase in average temperatures, among others). In this way, the acidity and harvesting times can be maintained, which now are increasingly anticipated due to the early ripening of the grapes.
- **Soil management through minimum tillage**
- Minimum tillage in order to maintain the structure of the soil and to maintain some biodiversity that has been lost along the years (Douro landscape mosaic).
- **Increased organic matter in soil, compost with any local source of organic matter**
- **Availability of irrigation in case of need**
Water reserves in case the introduction of irrigation is necessary, in order to avoid water stress on the plants. Dams already exist but there must be systems in place to make water available to plants in case of need.
- **Create a special regime for seasonal agricultural workers and university students (without implications for other social benefits)**
Creation of a special scheme, for seasonal workers, in order to fill the growing labour shortage in the region. The population is ageing and those who can still work live on a social insertion income. Often, in order not to lose this subsidy, they do not accept to work.

Besides, to create a system for university students that can fill gaps at the time of grape harvests or more concentrated work in the vineyard.

- **Encouraging mixed cropping (including grazing)**

Demonstrate the importance of mixed cropping with introduction of grazing. This is an area where there is both livestock and cropping and the combination of the two can be very beneficial to viticulture soils as the manure can be used as fertilizer and pasture and fodder crops can precede and alternate to vineyards.

- **Regulation of the expansion of vineyards**

Regulate the expansion of vineyards in order to avoid monoculture. the landscape in this area is regulated and there is a current programme aimed at maintaining biodiversity.

14 - Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains. Romania

Context

Mountain Reference Landscape: Piatra Craiului National Park (and surrounding area)

Value Chain name: Certified Ecotourism

Land-use system name: Mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland

Photo 132. Certified ecotourism in Piatra Craiului National Park.

Photo 133. Piatra Craiului National Park.

Figure 134: Map of the land-use system within the Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL

Source:

MOVING project (WP3) adapted from *van Asselen and Verburg (2012)*

Short Description land-use system

We describe the land-use system of our case study area in the Southern Romanian Carpathians as “mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland”.

According to the Land Use System classification provided by the WP3 and as seen on the map above, this “mosaic landscape” is comprised of:

- medium intensity/natural forest,
- high intensity/planted forest,
- extensive open rangeland,
- urban (especially around Bran and Moieciu communes) and
- agro-silvo-pastoral system.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable that was identified together with the stakeholders consulted is “landscape composition”. This was not discussed in any quantitative terms but was considered more subjectively as the basis of the “highly appreciated natural beauty of the area”. It was felt by local stakeholders that this natural beauty represented the most important asset for the certified ecotourism in the area because it is the primary reason that tourists visit the region. Other important assets such as biodiversity (especially the large carnivores that the region is famous for) are additional variables that are intimately connected with “landscape composition”.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 81: Driver description and components Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Precipitation: heavy rainfalls. Large quantities of rain falling in short periods of time which results in localised flash flooding of the local villages.
Temperature	Temperature: sudden changes during winter and spring that results in the early melting of the snow which affects the touristic function / value of the region.
Extreme events	Flooding and heat waves. The extreme events happening in the region are: flooding, heat waves and a Foehn wind (a dry, warm, down-slope wind), especially during spring.
Wildfire	Wildfires (human-caused). Wildfires caused by locals, especially during spring, in order to burn the dry grassland.
Pollution	We identified all three types of pollution in the area: soil and water (mainly caused by agricultural activities and plastic pollution made by tourists) and air pollution (from the local paper factory).
Pests, diseases and invasive species	Heat waves causing the appearance of bark insects that affect the spruce trees (<i>Picea abies</i>) in the region.
Over-exploitation of resources	During the questionnaires and workshop stages, we have divided this driver into two: forest overexploitation (by the local business operators) and water overexploitation (by the locals and local business operators in tourism) . See comments above about the pressure from tourism - especially during peak holiday periods
Demographic changes	During the questionnaires and workshop stages, we have divided this driver into two: depopulation and emigration of the local population .
Soil physical degradation	Soil erosion.
Land-use and land-cover change	During the questionnaires and workshop stages, we have divided this driver into two: chaotic and uncontrolled building development and under-used / abandoned farmland .

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 135: Infographic of results Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: During the first stage of the process (the interviews) the drivers that were considered most important were the changes in land use and land cover (chaotic and uncontrolled building development) and socio demographic drivers (depopulation and emigration), followed by forest overexploitation and water, soil and air pollution.

Drivers caused by climate change were not considered as so important - but those which were identified as most relevant by stakeholders are: extreme events (flooding and heat waves) and sudden changes in temperature.

About trends: Regarding the perception of past trends, almost all drivers were perceived as increasing in the last 20 years. As hinted in the interviews, the drivers of change about changes in land use and land cover: chaotic and uncontrolled building development and abandoned farmland were perceived as having the highest increased in the last 20 years, followed by sudden changes in temperature, water resources overexploitation and demographic changes (depopulation and emigration).

In regard to future projections, the stakeholders expect that almost all drivers will increase in the next 20 years, with the exception of forest exploitation, which came as a deviation of the expected result.

About sensitivity: Regarding the sensitivity analysis, the results were very similar with results of the ranking of the drivers. The drivers that were considered to affect the landscape composition totally negatively were the changes in land use and land cover (chaotic and uncontrolled building development) and socio-demographic changes (depopulation and emigration). The drivers caused by climate change (precipitation, changes in temperature and extreme events) were perceived as only having a partial negative effect upon the landscape composition.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Strict (and simplified) regulations enforcement with penalties in domains related with touristic activities (i.e. building development, waste management, ATVs usage)** – the current regulations are often perceived as being too difficult to comprehend or to enforce; furthermore, even though regulations and penalties are existent, often times they are not properly enforced by the local authorities.
- **Adopting public policies on sustainable development, including low impact accommodation** – currently, the public policies regarding sustainable tourism at the local, regional, and national levels are not considered to be enough by our stakeholders.
- **Developing a destination management unit, to efficiently manage the eco-destination – Zărnești** – Piatra Craiului region is the only one of the „10 eco-destinations” promoted by AER that doesn't have a destination management unit (which was determined as essential for any sustainable touristic destination).

- **Developing and supporting short food supply chains and local markets** – now, the region is not recognized for its local products because of a lack of interaction between local producers, business operators and local authorities.
- **Investing in the quality of education in the region, to contribute to enhancing the attractiveness of the region for future generations** – like other mountain regions, the migration of local population represents an issue in Zărnești – Piatra Craiului region. However, recent studies (such as Euromontana’s report ‘Being youth in a mountain area’) have reported that Romanian youth that currently live in the mountain area want to continue to live there (88% of the respondents), and more than half of the respondents have the wish to live in a mountain area. However, the biggest obstacle to youth remaining and/or moving to mountain areas is the dissatisfaction over access to health, education, and employment services. Thus, by investing in the quality of education, public authorities can contribute to the increase in the region’s attractiveness.
- **Developing centres for indoor and outdoor sportive and recreative activities** – besides nature exploring, the Zărnești – Piatra Craiului region lacks any other leisure activities, that are considered important from the touristic point of view.
- **Re-designing the landscape (forest design)** – the abandonment of agricultural land is contributing to the landscape being changed by the trees starting to expand in a chaotic manner, which negatively impact the touristic function of the region. The development of a forestry agency, which purpose will be the forest design, will maintain, and even enhance, the region’s touristic function.

15 - Dinaric Mountains. Serbia

Context

Study case: Dinaric Alps, Sjenica – Pester plateau

Value Chain name: Sjenica lamb meat (PDO)

Land-use system name: Extensive open rangeland /Mosaic cropland (extensive) and grassland with few livestock/

Photo 136 Sheep grazing

Photo 137 Sheep farm in village Ugao

Source: Mena Team

Mountain Reference Landscape description:

The MRL covers the main three municipalities of Sjenica, Novi Pazar and Tutin. The landscape is dominated by high mountain ranges and deep valleys interspersed with plateaus. The land use system connected to this LC system is that of forest with few livestock and that of heterogenous or mosaic cropland and grassland with few livestock. Forest management includes production forests for wood production. Agriculture is mostly extensive and often subsistence farming, with a few farms of a middle scale (300-1000 sheep, for example).

Figure 138: Land uses in Dinaric Mountains MRL

Short Description land-use system

Pešter is situated within the MRL in the municipality of Sjenica with some extensions to Novi Pazar and Tutin. The plateau is a large field/highland surrounded by high mountains. Altitudes of the plateau are between 900 and 1200 meters. Soil is mostly karst intermingled with pastures. Pasture management takes place through extensive grazing. The economy of the area relies primarily on animal breeding, mainly sheep. Pešter is famous for its dairy products, especially the Sjenica cheese, as well as lamb and prosciutto. The plateau is sparsely populated. Pešter is characteristic for its microclimate, which is particularly harsh in the winter months. Lowest temperatures during wintertime can go up to -35°C. Daily temperatures during summer have very wide amplitude – day temperatures can go up to 30°C, while night temperatures can be even around 0°C

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The main variable that affects the value chain and the quality of Sjenica lamb PDO, is productivity and quality of the pastures on the highlands. Robust and less demanding, this sheep is also a good choice for the fragile but rich pastures and meadows, and its management is crucial to secure enough supply of food.

Due to extremely harsh climate conditions and karst soil, the production of Sjenica sheep depends on supply of green feed in the short summer season. The grass yield needs to be sufficient to feed the animals through the winter season. The productivity is very affected by changes in weather conditions and climate trend. Also, water management is one of the key elements for maintaining production, while observing changes in precipitation and water supply for the flock. Due to all these reasons the productivity and quality of pastures is selected as a key variable that reflects the competitiveness of the VC and its products. Apart from lamb and sheep meat, the producers are involved in dairy processing (Sjenica cheese PDO, dried sheep meat with bones (Sjenica stelja PDO)

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Figure 139: Driver description and components in Dinaric Mountains MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. The water supply through precipitation is one of a few top factors that influence the productivity of the agricultural season. The overall intensifying trend is a sum of increased variabilities in precipitation which result in more dry periods during the warmer/summer season, and the increased overall quantity of rainfall are opposite. The months of May and June see the most rainfall which is strongly needed rain for grass production, while July and August are the driest. Due to precipitation shortage, 50% of the animal feed failed in the previous season.
Temperature	Temperature variability and climatic factors have always been an important feature of climate in Sjenica. Being one of the harshest regional specifics, the climate of the region is extreme mountainous and continental, with particular winter extremes. Nowadays there is a trend of earlier summer season (earlier by 10 days) and equally same (10days) of later cold weather. The winters are not that harsh (the far minus up to minus 40 is typical for this region) while each summer there are tropical days (over 30 degrees); Overall average increase of temperature in the last 40 years has been around 1.5 degrees.
Extreme events	Spring hail, heat weaves and storms are some of the extremes that note increased frequency. Still, the extreme events though overall more present are not that emphasized as one of the drivers affecting the variable. Winds that are contributing to soil erosion are also occasionally putting strong pressures on the production system. In addition to this, late spring frosts can be seen as extreme events, since the vegetation is starting earlier due to the temperature increment, causing damage on the earlier grown grass and lower quantity and quality of grass at the beginning of grazing season
Wildfire	Wildfires are not a common threat and happen relatively rare. There is no self-ignition due to high temperatures and usually they happen due to neglect. As forests are relatively low in percentage (less than 25%) the forest fires are also very rare
Pollution	The area of Pester has no industrial pollution, as livestock and agriculture are main economic activities. There is poor management of waste which contributes to surface pollution that is limited to particular landfills and illegal waste points that are spreading the waste by wind. There is no public wastewater treatment, but the pressures are small. Air pollution due to coal and wood heating is not that significant. The coal mine Shtavalj that is in the heart of Pester is polluting both water system of Pester and it surface/soils.

Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Pest. Some of the animal diseases such as nodular dermatitis or bluetongue disease, are to some extent linked to climate change and spread of areal of its vectors, insects and mosquitoes. There are no significant changes in the new pests regarding animal feed production.
Over-exploitation of resources	The vast land resources are sufficient for the livestock flock that is currently in production and there is a room for expansion. The management practices can be particularly taken care of when it comes to water resources, their regional connectivity and karst soil structure that does not retain water. Even some resources, such as soil and water are considered enough for the production, there are pressures at particular localities depending on the soil quality and infrastructural and natural water supply.
Demographic changes	Sjenica and Tutin demographic decline has been primarily driven by net out migration primarily to Western Europe and tan to the other regions of the country. Every year since 2002, almost 200 people have emigrated from Sjenica, and this trend is even stronger now. There is disbalance regarding the Young and women who leave the region faster. This makes negative influences on land use, some farms are disappearing and there is less farmers, but they become larger as modernisation requires less labor force. These migrations are also causing very high percentage of old population in the area
Soil physical degradation	There is not any significant degradation of soil as practices are not overly exploiting soil and using manure as fertilizer; still there is some decline in hummus percentage and the structure of soil can be improved by conservation soil management practices.
Land-use and land-cover change	There are some changes in land use as there is more meadows to pastures, and that contributes to better production systems, but to some extent also loss of biodiversity. However, there is also soil abandonment and change in right of use of common pastures. This driver is to some extent having negative impact on the quality and productivity of pastures.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 140: Infographic of results in Dinaric Mountains MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: There is overwhelming consensus that temperature and precipitation and two drivers mostly affecting the production from the natural and demographic changes from socio economic change.

It was pointed out that these drivers also bring some positive effects of climate changes, such as less harsh temperatures and therefore less death of young animals during their birth or that there is overall less temperature extremes in minus.

About trends: Precipitation and temperature are identified as two main drivers that are affecting the productivity and quality of pastures.

The information from the HyDrômeteorological institute as well as the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) of the European Commission indicate some trends that can affect the production and VC sustainability.

- The total average annual temperature has a trend of growth and increase of 1.5 degrees Celsius since 1981 onwards
- The number of days with frost decreased by about 30 in the same period
- Slightly more days with high temperatures during the summer (over 30 degrees)
- Annual precipitation is growing and there are slightly fewer dry days BUT precipitation is not evenly distributed, and the trend needs to be further investigated

Predictions

- Temperatures are expected to rise from 1.5 to 2.2 degrees Celsius till the end of the century
- The initial increase in precipitation will be replaced by dry periods in the second half of the century
- Increased drought and extreme events such as late frosts, storms, hail
- Heat stress for animals and humans and potential impact on economic effects are also in prediction

There is definitely drop in precipitation in months April and May, which are still the most abundant with the rain but still is crucial for the grass harvest that comes in early June.

About sensitivity: The drivers that have been identified as best ranked (precipitation and temperature) had different views regarding the sensitivity of the key variable in the next two decades. That particularly counts for precipitation that has covered all the responses including extremes of total positive and negative impact, indicating need for more depth analysis and understanding of the perceptions of the individual stakeholders, while temperature has both slightly positive and negative scores.

There is most consent regarding demographic changes and its affect to land use and management practices were unanimously considered as very negative. There is also quite some uncertainty regarding the potential effects and sensitivity to overexploitation and soil degradation,

as there are potentially devastating trends but with yet difficult to anticipate at full scope and impact.

List of adaptive mechanisms

There are not many implemented mechanisms that deal with the impact reduction but here are some of the potentials that can gain more application in the coming period.

- Water supply needs to be systematically addressed both through **improved water management** at the level of infrastructure and use, and by investing in construction of mini-infrastructural solutions for water collection such as water catchment and collection ponds.
- Use and develop **adequate mixtures of plants and grasses** (high quality grass, Leguminosae etc),
- **Conservation tillage** that preserves structure of soil and improves water retention is still not a common practice that can reduce expenses and introduce new management practices for soil improvement
- **Period of harvest of grasses needs to be adopted** to the new climatic conditions to keep the best quality of feed
- **Investment support for young farmers** is essential to keep their interest in agriculture and livestock production
- **Monitoring of animal diseases** is also a good tool to prevent and predict future trends and reduce impact and costs of such outbreaks

16 - Slovak Carpathian Mountains. Slovakia

Context

Study case: Slovak Carpathians

Value Chain name: Bio-honey

Land-use system name: extensive grasslands (pastures and meadows) and forest

Photo 141. Forests and grasslands in Low Tatras in Slovakia

Source: Jozef Gandžala

Photo 142. Beehives in Bravacovo, Slovakia

Source: Lukáš Zagata

Figure 143: Land use systems of MRL in Slovak Carpathians

Source: MOVING project (WP3) based on *Levers et al. (2018)*

Short Description land-use system

The principal land use systems for honey production in mountain areas in Slovakia are grasslands, including pastures and meadows, and forest areas. This mosaic of land use systems provides a diversity of plants having pollen or nectar sources for bees' healthy nutrition and for honey production.

The MRL is in Horehronie region, concretely in Polomka, Bacúch and Bravacovo municipalities. The altitude of the MRL area is in the range from 600 m up to 1,660 m above sea level. The main land covers are forests and grasslands. Overall, there is a decline in agricultural land in recent decades. The largest negative changes were in the case of arable land. There is also a slight decrease in the case of gardens. Non-agricultural land and build/up area increased slightly.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable is a diversity of pollen- and nectar – producing plants and honeydew from trees. This diversity of plants provides bees with diverse nutrition sources important for their health and for their honey productive capacity. The honey quality is also influenced by clear environment in mountain areas without chemical treatment in forests and grasslands.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 82: Driver description and components Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Precipitation in this study area is expressed as drought. "Drought" is a factor that describes precipitation-free periods that cause plants, soil, and air to dryness. Drought weakens plants, including their roots and their ability to draw nutrients from the soil. It also causes the predominance of drought-tolerant species and the eventual introduction of non-native species from warmer areas and the disappearance of some native nectar-bearing and pollen-bearing plants. The result is a less favourable species composition for bee grazing.
Temperature	<p>"Rising temperature" means a higher average temperature, especially in the winter months. Elevated temperature combined with drought, subsequent storms and low water retention in the country causes damage to some plants and consequent less plant diversity. It means poorer grazing conditions for bees.</p> <p>"Temperature fluctuations" mean irregular deviations from the average temperature in each season. The temperature fluctuations affect the time, length and frequency of flowering of plants. As a result, nectar and pollen production is damaged. Especially during spring, the month of February is often warmer than March. In autumn, the warm November associated with the flowering of some introduced plant species may disrupt the annual cycle of bees.</p>
Extreme events	"Extremes events" in our conditions mean especially heavy rains and heat waves. Heavy rain during spring and summer can mechanically destroy the flowers for the bee. Heat waves, especially in combination with drought, weaken plants, reduce plant nectar content and have a bad effect on insects important for honeydew production. All extremes can damage pasture quality for bees.
Wildfire	The wildfires are very rare in the studied area. So, they are considered as not relevant.
Pollution	Pollution is not relevant in the studied area in the last decades.
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	"Invasive species" mean the spread of invasive non-native plant species that replace some native species and are not suitable for bee grazing. A change in the composition of the plant species in this case means a reduction in the diversity for bee pasture. Some non-native plants can disrupt the bee's life cycle by flowering in the fall when the bees in the area should be wintering.

	<p>"Bears destroying beehives" refers to overgrown bear colonies looking for protein in bee larvae. In the event of excessive beehive destruction, the overall biodiversity in the site is threatened.</p> <p>"Bears destroying anthills" mean the mechanical destruction of anthills in search of protein food in the form of ant larvae. As ants are an essential player in the production of honeydew, their destruction threatens honeydew honey production. The destruction of anthills is also associated with the consequent threat to local biodiversity.</p> <p>Other pests (e.g., Varroa) and diseases affect bee colonies. This topic is highly relevant in beekeeping but there is no evidence that it is directly related with land use systems.</p>
<p>Over-exploitation of resources</p>	<p>Forest use for renewable energy. Inappropriate use of wood vegetation for renewable energy means excessive chipping of wood directly in forest stands or between former agricultural plots. On the one hand, the excessive use of wood for chipping reduces the amount of bee grazing plants. On the other hand, chipping carried out directly in the field (e.g. forest stands) causes soil compaction and thus impairs the productive capacity of the soil for plant growth. The so-called "grazing cleaning" is happening in areas forming the boundaries between the former agricultural plots, which have overgrown with nectar and pollen plants and shrubs / hawthorns, blackthorns, hazelnuts, rockets, dogwoods /. Of course, the pasture will not return there, but it goes one-off income from the sale of wood chips.</p>
<p>Demographic changes</p>	<p>"Life-style changes" are related to a decline of the permanent population, fewer people working in agriculture, and non-organic cultivation of agricultural crops and monocultures. Meadows and pastures are being abandoned.</p> <p>The transition from agriculture to recreational use of mountain areas also reduces species diversity in rural gardens.</p> <p>These changes ultimately lead to lower biodiversity for bee grazing.</p>
<p>Soil physical degradation</p>	<p>Soil physical degradation is caused by pasture abandonment. The soil misses the organic matter from animals.</p>
<p>Land-use and land-cover change</p>	<p>"Land use change" means abandonment or changes in grassland management. Abandonment of pastures and meadows begins the process of natural succession, which causes changes in plant composition. This process leads over time to reduced bee grazing diversity. Management changes occur also in meadows, where mulching replaces mowing. Mulching mechanically destroys plants from the roots and prevents the growth of new plants. In addition, mulching can also damage bees that have been grazing.</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 144: Infographic of results Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: There was a relative agreement between respondents about the importance of climate change drivers and the land-use changes. Interestingly, some saw the invasive species as an enrichment of plant types for bee pasture. However, more specialists on pasture lands stressed the negative aspects of these changes for the plant composition on pasture and meadows native ecosystems.

The high variability of responses was also observed about bears' damages to beehives and anthills.

About trends: Most of the respondents agreed that the climate change drivers (drought, temperature increase, temperature fluctuation and extremes) in last 20years increased and will continue in the next 20 years as well.

The land use changes, and life-style changes will also continue according to majority of respondents.

Answers were not so consistent in relation to problems with land use for renewable energy (wood chipping).

Diverse responses we have obtained also for problems with bears. Some stakeholders don't know whether it is a problem for bees and how it will evolve next 20 years.

About sensitivity: Stakeholders are concerned that some of the drivers of greatest impact are climatic and cannot be directly influenced and the bee pastureland uses will need to significantly adapt to these changes.

The factors to which the system is most sensitive is drought, temperature fluctuation and extremes because the intensity and the process of these changes is the most unpredictable.

In general, all analysed drivers are perceived as important for beekeeping in mountain areas and bee pasture is sensitive to them.

The forests are seen as less sensitive to analysed drivers than the pastures and meadows.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Mechanism 1 -Promoting sustainable practices in mountain farming and forestry** - the sustainable alias nature-friendly practices in agriculture and forestry also mean a bee-friendly environment with autochthonous species, diversity of plants for bee pasture, clean water low chemical treatment in farming and forestry.
- **Mechanism 2 - Motivation of people - to work in agriculture and subsidies for small farms** - support crop diversity; promote successful examples - A diverse landscape in mountain areas can be safeguarded by people willing to work in agriculture. People's motivation can be increased by promoting successful examples of new and/or successful

eco or bio farmers in mountain areas and subsidies for small-scale farming without enormous bureaucratic paperwork.

- **Mechanism 3 - Adjustment of agrotechnical procedures in meadow and pasture management**- to maintain suitable conditions for bee pasture. E.g., Use moving instead of mulching, adjust moving time after plants' flowering time, maintain a diversity of nectar and pollen plants.
- **Mechanism 4 - Support for research in beekeeping, e.g., drugs suitable for bio-production of honey, biotechnical methods, resistance to pests (hornets)** - Globalisation and climate changes bring new treats to beekeeping. Research should help find new ways of adaptation in beekeeping practices to safeguard resilient bee colonies in the Slovak mountains.
- **Mechanism 5 - Unification of conditions for organic production in agriculture within (Central) Europe** - According to MAP members, the requirements for organic production are stricter than in other Central European countries. Simplification of the process of organic production is believed to motivate more the organic production necessary for bio-honey production.
- **Mechanism 6 - Environmental education of children and youth** - an increased understanding across professions and sectors how the health of bees is interconnected with the health of an environment is needed.
- **Mechanism 7 - Regulation of bear population in the mountains** - Bears are currently overpopulated in the Slovak mountains. To avoid damages caused on beehives by bears, MAP members suggest regulating the bear population instead of protecting this animal species.
- **Mechanism 8 - Improve better understanding between farmers and beekeepers** - Some farmers are unwilling to improve bee pasture in their fields because it means more work for them. Incentives to enhance learning and collaboration between farmers and beekeepers would be helpful.

17 - Betic Systems. Spain

Context

Study case: Organic Mountain olive oil in Subbetica Cordobesa

Value Chain name: Organic Mountain olive oil

Land-use system name: Betic Systems

Photo 1. Mountain olive groves in the Priego de Córdoba mountain ranges

Source: Adegua Team

Photo 2. Olive harvesting in the Sierra de Zuheros

Source: Adegua Team (2021)

Figure 145: . Land use system map of Subbética Córdoba MRL

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Malek & Verburg (2017)*

Short Description land-use system

In the MRL the cultivated area, up to an altitude of 800-900 metres, is mostly covered by traditional olive groves. It is therefore an extensive, rain-fed 'permanent crop' (just over 100 olive trees per hectare). This description does not coincide with some of the descriptions on the attached map, where the permanent crop is mentioned as intensive/irrigated. Similarly, areas mentioned as "intensive annual crop", notably in Zuheros (LAU 14075) and marked as irrigated, do not actually correspond to this type of irrigated crop.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The productivity of organic olives (in terms of quantity and quality) is the Reference Variable of this mountain agro-system, being the main resource that supports the Value Chain of Organic Mountain Olive Oil in the three municipalities included in the MRL (Carcabuey LAU 14015, Priego de Córdoba LAU 14055, Zuheros LAU 14075).

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 83: Driver description and components Subbética Córdoba MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. Reduction and changes in the distribution of rainfall with a potential impact on the hydrological level (streams and aquifers), soil and vegetation. This decrease and marked irregularity of rainfall also occurs in spring and autumn, periods considered critical for fruit setting and ripening, as well as the process of olive oil formation, which may lead to lower production and loss of quality.
Temperature	Increase in seasonal or annual mean temperature, including changes in mean, maximum and minimum temperatures. Near-summer temperatures may start in spring and last until late autumn, with possible effects on fruit formation and ripening, as well as on the lipogenesis process.
Extreme events	Changes in intensity, frequency, or timing for the following components: heat waves, hailstorms, torrential rains, and reduced frost periods. Due to their unpredictability and extreme character, they can cause very negative impacts locally and temporally.
Wildfire	Uncontrolled fires that affect the forest and soil to varying degrees, the ecological mountain olive grove under appropriate management contributes to the creation of a mosaic landscape that limits the frequency and intensity of forest fires.
Land-use and land-cover change	Land use changes" are understood as those involving a conversion of crop types, a change of system or the inclusion of mixed crops, among others. In organic mountain olive groves, trends can be seen that may lead to abandonment or intensification.
Soil physical degradation	Loss of organic matter due to erosion, poor tillage, or excessive compaction. In organic highland olive groves, no tillage and permanent covers represent a positive change by increasing organic matter in the first cm of the soil, preventing erosion and without causing excessive compaction as machinery traffic is lighter. Furthermore, in the water basins, these organic mountain olive groves are water donors if there is a balance, and the water does not become a factor of erosion.
Over-exploitation of resources	Inadequate extraction of resources such as river or groundwater, as well as other management that jeopardises the sustainability of the agro-system itself. Organic highland olive groves rarely exert pressure on water resources. Controlled grazing can bring mutual benefits in the form of canopy management and livestock feeding.

Pests, diseases, and invasive species	<p>Changes in the intensity and frequency of these pests, whether indigenous or invasive. Organic olive groves in the sierra are not affected by diseases such as Xylella or verticillium, while pests such as the olive fruit fly can be more negative when climatic conditions favour their spread or when they spread from conventional olive groves. However, the presence of auxiliary flora and fauna helps to maintain biological controls.</p>
Pollution	<p>Introduction of harmful substances into the agrosystem causing loss of quality and negative impacts on soil, water, or atmosphere. In organic mountain olive groves, methods and substances are used that do not generate these impacts, so pollution tends to be zero. The difficult mechanisation also reduces the use of motor vehicles and machines with the consequent reduction in the consumption of fossil fuels and associated polluting emissions.</p>
Demographic changes	<p>Decline and ageing of the rural population leading to changes in management practices, changes in land use and abandonment of the land. In the organic olive groves of the sierra, despite the difficulties of management and low or non-existent profitability, considering the environmental functions, the complementary income and the cultural attachment of the population to the land, abandonment can be avoided if effective policies to improve prices and recognise multifunctionality become a reality in the coming years, also contributing to the fixation of the population.</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 146: Infographic of results Subbética Córdoba MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: Two climate factors (Drought and Temperature) lead the ranking while showing a high concentration of responses. At the other extreme, several factors (e.g. overexploitation, pollution, forest fires), show a large dispersion of responses, suggesting some controversy linked to the benefit derived from the practice of organic production and how it contributes to the reduction of negative impacts.

About trends: A high concentration is evident when assessing the increase in temperature or reduction in precipitation over the last 20 years, while at the other extreme, extreme events and demographic changes show significant increases in their impact over a similar period for a large majority of stakeholders. Some factors such as Fires and Land Use Change show significant percentages of lack of knowledge or indecision.

Regarding future projections, there are again factors such as rainfall, temperatures and extreme events whose trends will continue to negatively affect the agro-system, others such as fires will hardly affect or show controversial opinions in the case of land use or over-exploitation.

About sensitivity: There is a notable dispersion in the analysis of the sensitivity of the system to certain factors such as over-exploitation of resources, pests and diseases or soil degradation.

List of adaptive mechanisms

we would like to explore in a more in-depth and participatory way the feasibility, required commitments and impacts of the described mechanisms in the next stages of MOVING.

It should be underlined on the one hand that most of the eight mechanisms show a medium to high degree of economic and technical viability, while the environmental benefit stands out for its generally high valuation. The social acceptability of a couple of mechanisms is low (regarding the change to organic production and the implementation of soil conservation measures), which will require greater political commitment in terms of regulation and associated incentives. The current implementation of these mechanisms is partial and of low intensity, which augurs immediate and successful impacts derived from a decisive policy related to these mechanisms.

The complete reduction of the negative impacts produced by the different factors analysed is considered rare. However, moderate, and slight reductions can lead to substantial and progressive changes in a transition policy towards sustainability.

Below is the prioritised list of mechanisms with a brief explanation.

- **Awareness-raising campaigns on good practices**, water management, and prevention of illegal uses. Promoting groups for analysis and knowledge exchange, as well as the development of pilot actions, study visits, and dissemination of good practices.
- **Increase in CAP aid for organic mountain olive groves**, including specific modernisation plans and the allocation of aid complementary to agri-environmental aid for the most fragile olive groves (biodiversity, slopes, etc.).

- **Actions to raise awareness and disseminate Good Practices** linked to organic mountain olive groves, generating added value for them, via price differentials based on eco-systemic services and promoting specific quality labels within the framework of the European Union.
- **Specific informative actions on this model of agro-system**, encouraging the change of model for the benefit of organic production in the mountain olive grove, as well as specific training actions aimed at offering added value to the practices that producers, service companies, cooperatives, etc. must carry out. Contributing to the creation of a professional sector that is trained and adapted to the management needs required by this particular agro-system.
- **Construction of new composting plants using organic waste from olive groves and olive oil mills**, streamlining administrative processes, encouraging experimentation, and providing incentives for the production and use of these products.
- **Practices adapted to Climate Change** (pruning system according to the water deficit; controlled management of covers; bringing forward the harvesting season and timetables adapted to climatic conditions combined with anti-production alternation measures and better prices for first season oils...).
- **Adapted soil management and erosion control practices** (mixed cover management with livestock, prevention, and control of gullies and streams...), through preventive practices and, where appropriate, by means of environmental engineering corrective measures.
- **Dissemination of the benefits associated with the eco-systemic services** provided by the ecological mountain olive grove (environmental, economic, and cultural). Through training, information, and dynamisation activities aimed at local actors and stakeholders in the value chain.

18 - Sierra Morena. Spain

Context

Study case: Sierra Morena

Value Chain name: PDO Los Pedroches Iberian Ham

Land-use system name : Agro-silvo-pastoral system

Photo 147. Dehesa system in Los Pedroches

Photo 148. Dehesa system in Los Pedroches

Source: Guillermo Palacios

Figure 149: Land use systems of MRL Sierra Morena case of study

Source: MOVING project (WP3) based on *Malek and Verburg (2017)*

Short Description land-use system

The Dehesa is an agrosilvopastoral system where the historical relationship of human beings with their environment has created an open forest landscape where *Quercus* species (usually holm oaks, but also cork oaks, and gall oaks) coexist with crops or pastures.

The MRL is in the region of Los Pedroches (Cordoba, Spain), and more specifically covering three municipalities of Villanueva de Córdoba, Pozoblanco, and Cardena. From a geological point of view, this area has a constant presence of plutonic rocks (granodiorites and granites), which usually outcrop igneous bodies, although quartzite and slate are abundant to the north and south of the sector. As a result, erosion is low, which does not, however, imply good soil quality.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable is the production of **grass and acorns**. The fact that the pigs spend part of their lives (during the 'montanera' period in Autumn) eating acorns and pasture freely in the Dehesa is what makes the difference in the quality of the ham. This practice is what gives high quality Iberian ham its differentiating value compared to other hams from pigs fed on feed and under intensive production regimes.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 84: Driver description and components Sierra Morena MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	«Precipitation» in this study area is expressed as Drought . Drought causes water stress and weakening of the tree. Importance of the autumn: Rain in September and the first weeks of October, which is when the acorns gain weight. Also, for the grass, as it helps it to germinate. Drought also influences grass production. This is essential to supplement the acorns in the feeding of pigs. Drought in spring causes less flower setting, less flower production and therefore less acorn production. Also, the pastures are of poorer quality. Gradient between the Pozoblanco area with less rainfall and Venta del Charco (Cardeña) with more rainfall.
Temperature	Less cold winters, the holm oaks flower earlier, which exposes them to possible frost. If flowering is brought forward too much, the acorns will not set as well. Holm oaks need cold in winter to kill pests and diseases. Pigs also benefit from cold in winter. Some farms in colder areas are benefiting from it, avoiding frosts.
Extreme events	Late frosts (cold waves): Can have a major impact if flowering has been brought forward. The impact depends on the temporal and spatial heterogeneity of flowering. Hail: Causes defoliation and fruit drop, localised. Heat waves: cause acorn abortion (unripe acorns fall off). Torrential rains: uneven rainfall. Possible erosion in areas with steep slopes. Causes: increasing and intensifying because of climate change.
Wildfire	There are no fires in the dehesa. If there are livestock, it is very difficult to have fires.
Pollution	The main source of contamination would be the slurry, but it is very controlled, and it is usually spread around the farms. Is caused by slurry coming from the enclosures and feedlots (for species other than Iberian pigs)
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	This driver is expressed in this case study as pests and diseases that cause weakening and death of trees. Phytophthora cinnamomi: It is favoured by the weakening of trees caused by drought (in places like Cardeña, with higher rainfall and the same soil it does not affect so much). Careful handling can lead to spread. Ceramix spp.: Attacks dead wood, e.g., by bad pods or old trees. When there is a pest, it cannot be stopped. Other pests affecting holm oak: Lymantria, Tortix. Lack of coordinated control of existing pests. Poor management at farm level.

Over-exploitation of resources	High stocking density and water consumption. The farms associated to the PDO Iberian ham have a strict regulation regarding the stocking density, so it is quite controlled, but in other farms where this is not the case, this is a problem.
Demographic changes	This could affect the production of acorns and pasture insofar as skilled labour and local management know-how are lost. However, it could also lead to a change in farm management, through professionalisation. No land-use abandonment., as long as there is profitability on the farm, they are maintained. Depopulation: causing the emigration of the population to other places. Economic factor. Intensive cattle farming, which is pulling heavily. Danger of intensification. Lack of dignified work in the countryside. In our MRL there is a large distribution of land, which is socially important, but there is a danger of concentration of ownership due to depopulation.
Soil physical degradation	Where there is cultivation there is less organic matter than where there is grazing. Cattle trampling (in places with a high stocking density and no movement). In temporary enclosures for Iberian pigs the soil degrades a lot.
Land-use and land-cover change	In the area (MRL) there aren't major trends in changes of land-cover, although other dehesa areas outside the MRL have pressure of agriculture land. The main problem is the reduction of tree cover in the dehesa. The loss of trees has to do with poor management (bad pruning), overgrazing, pests or diseases, lack of regeneration, old age of the trees.
Land abandonment	(Note In the ranking and in the workshop this driver was specifically asked and assessed, but in the end it will be a component of the demographic change driver) Related to Demographic changes , if there is profitability on the farm, they are maintained. There may be a change in the profile of owners, rather than abandonment. Owners who have the farm as an economic complement, or owners from outside the territory (large landowners, investors, or investment funds), would take over the farms, probably causing a concentration effect. In the area, due to the historical conditioning of Los Pedroches, the farms are very socially distributed.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 150: Infographic of results Sierra Morena MRL

Comments on the results

About Ranking: Some of the most important drivers are climatic (drought and extreme events) although drivers such as overexploitation, pests and diseases, demographic changes and soil degradation are of similar importance in our case study. It is interesting to note that the issue of temperature increase is the one with the highest number of "don't know/no answer" responses, 45%, although these were mostly given by people who do not live or have not lived there in the last 20 years. This was not the case for other responses such as extreme events, for example. The high variability of responses in the Soil physical degradation driver, with researchers giving the highest scores, and producers and extension officers the lowest, is noteworthy.

About trends: Is quite consistent with the ranking data. The drivers that are most important according to the ranking are the ones where the trend has increased the most in the last 20 years. Certainly drought, livestock stocking (overexploitation), pests (especially Phytophthora) especially, but also land use change, increasing temperature and extreme events, and depopulation are drivers whose trend has increased over the last 20 years.

In terms of extreme events, the opposite trend was found since some extreme events (such as frost or snowfall) are less frequent.

About sensitivity: Stakeholders are concerned that some of the drivers of greatest impact are climatic and cannot be directly influenced.

The driver to which the system is most sensitive is drought, not only because the lack of rainfall affects acorn production and passage, but also because it can affect the trees by weakening them, making them more susceptible to diseases and pests, and even an extreme drought can wipe out the trees, as happened in some parts during the drought of 1994-96.

Extreme events are also an important factor, because they can cause acorn abortion or flower drop, severely affecting productivity.

Overexploitation, temperature and diseases and pests are three on which the reference variable has a similar sensitivity. In the rest of the drivers analysed, the perception of sensitivity is between mild and moderate, with mild being more predominant.

List of adaptive mechanisms

As mentioned in the previous section, some of the most important drivers are climatic. On a local scale, there is no mitigation capacity for these drivers, but there is a capacity for adaptation. In this sense:

- **Recommendations for a rational and efficient use of water** for the Dehesa through a catalogue of good practices, can help to make better use of water, as well as improve management related to the hydration of animals, so that this does not negatively affect the soil.

There are other broader measures that require specific programmes led by the regional administration with the support of other administrations and entities in the sector, such as the following measures:

- Technical and economic **support for the complete implementation of an integral management system** that guarantees the sustainability of the Dehesa at farm level and the mechanism. In addition, in this mechanism there may be reluctance on the part of producers due to the bureaucracy involved and the greater dependence on external agents.
- Technical and economic **support for the densification and rejuvenation of the woodland.**
- **Spanish Ministry's proposal (July 2021) on eco-schemes.**
- **Encourage and generate spaces for the participation of landowners in decision-making bodies and the development of regulations** (local, regional, national, European) in relation to the factors with the greatest impact on the Dehesa, continues to be a demand, although the sector has representatives and there are spaces for consultation, these are not really considered.
- Public Awareness Strategy, and **raising awareness of the environmental, social, and economic benefits of the Dehesa**, is aimed more at society in general, and is important to raise awareness of the importance of the Dehesa, and to be able to generate a willingness to pay more for high-quality products.

19 - Spanish Pyrenees. Spain

Context

Study case: Spanish Pyrenees

Value Chain name: Mountain Wine Value Chain (Spanish Vignerons from pre-Pyrenean mountains)

Land-use system name: permanent cropland

Photo 151 and 152: Vineyards in Ayerbe

Source : Vinidea Team

Figure 153: Map of the land system within the Spanish Pyrenees MRL

Source: MOVING project (WP3) according to *Levers et al. 2018*

Short Description land-use system

The land use system is a permanent cropland: vineyards for wine production. Huesca is a historic vineyards region in Aragon. Due to depopulation in last half century, a lot of vineyards were uprooted and now what remains are small productions with identity value. The agro-ecological system is polyculture, each farmhouse in the area maintains a very small winery put at risk by aging of the farm population. In the last decade several professional farmers showed interest in getting engaged into the local highly identified production and offer their knowledge and support to local producers. The plots of vineyards are small, they coexist with olive oil, almonds, cereals, and pastures.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

We have defined the reference variable as the vineyard productivity and grape quality, as these two key parameters determining wine production in the region are the most vulnerable in the face of different drivers of change.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 85: Driver description and components Spanish Pyrenees MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Drought. Changes in terms of intensity, frequency, distribution or seasonality. For "high altitude viticulture in the Aragonese Pyrenees region", accidents are increasing and in very extreme years the differences in rainfall are notable, concentrating in fewer events, but with the possibility of large downpours followed by heat waves, so that there is a lot of pressure from pathogens and the plant suffers significant imbalances. In rainfed areas, the problem is greater, as the plant cover is more limited in its use.
Temperature	It refers to the increases in average temperatures, increasing solar radiation influence on the plants and on the ripening of the grapes, especially in short-cycle vine varieties. The mountains are still an opportunity. The temperature difference between day and night, essential for the aromatic profile, is not changing at high altitudes. The mountain favours higher plots, which allow the adaptation of varieties with longer cycles.
Extreme events	Changes in the intensity, frequency or seasonality of extreme events (heavy rainfalls, wind, heat peaks, hail, etc.). For "high altitude viticulture in Aragonese Pyrenees region", the main components are risk of frost, rainstorms and hail. Rainstorms will always do less damage in the mountains than in the valley, because the water flows downwards.
Wildfire	This driver is not relevant within the MRL.
Pollution	Water and soil contamination by phytosanitary products (insecticides, herbicides, fungicides, including copper...) also used in viticulture. Variation in CO2 levels at the macro level affect the vine vegetative cycle. Human factors are to blame in most of the most polluting cases.
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	Changes in the intensity and frequency of pests and pathogens, both native and invasive. The main components are: fungal attacks, especially downy mildew, powdery mildew and wood disease, with mites and moths as possible vectors. There is increasing danger from wild species such as rabbits, which eat green shoots, wild boar and roe deer.
Over-exploitation of resources	It refers to changes at the level of "overexploitation", although in mountain areas there is sufficient surface water and groundwater due to their good drainage capacity, that must be maintained.

<p>Demographic changes</p>	<p>“Demographic change” refers to the depopulation of rural areas in high mountains. Empty mountainous regions are the consequences of the mistake of replacing agricultural practices with investments by large financial companies, running out of sufficient labour. Main components are: Large decrease of the local population in the 1960s, viticulture disappeared in the region and was replaced by cereal crops. Essential services are at the limit of sustainability. Labour shortage for agricultural operations occurs.</p>
<p>Soil physical degradation</p>	<p>The changes occurred at the level of "physical degradation of the vineyard soil", due to the abusive use of tillage, damaging the porosity and structure of the soil and causing strong erosive phenomena and soils, with landslides and degradation of the clay-humic complex, which causes biodiversity reduction. Intensive farming with the addition of chemicals changes the composition, both chemically and microbiologically. Erosion problem is due to the soil structure loss (due to soil mismanagement and loss of organic matter) and water can wash away soil even to the point where the roots of the vine are uncovered. Every storm picks up part of the soil and carries it away. Boulder and sandy soils are more resistant.</p>
<p>Land-use and land-cover change</p>	<p>It refers to changes in "land use and land cover changes", with the dominance of tillage over vegetation cover and grazing disappearing. In addition, it is currently very difficult to obtain planting rights for new vineyards; on the contrary, some fertile soils are occupied by solar panels.</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 154: Infographic of results Spanish Pyrenees MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: the results of ranking of the drivers of change clearly showed that climatic drivers (except wildfires) are considered the most important ones. Regarding endogenous drivers it's evident the big concern about soil physical degradation and invasive species, which has emerged already during the interview stage. It was surprising to see relatively low scores gained by demographic changes driver, while during the interviews it was raised by many stakeholders as an important issue for the area. The high variability in the evaluation of demographic changes can be explained by different perception of these problems by various actors, depending also on the fact if they are operating within or outside MRL.

About trends: the perception of past trend is quite connected to the perception of driver's importance. As expected, according to the respondents the trend has increased the most over the last 20 years for the following drivers: increasing temperatures, pest and diseases, extreme events, demographic changes, soil physical degradation, pollution. There was a very surprising trend indicator for precipitations driver, but we consider it a result of a confusion: some stakeholders opted for decreasing trend considering that precipitation level has decreased in the last decades, when they should select the increasing trend of decreasing precipitation amounts.

About sensitivity: Sensitivity survey results put in evidence the value chain can be potentially more affected by the endogenous drivers as soil physical degradation, invasive species and pollution. Regarding the climate factors, only the extreme events bring an unquestionable negative effect, while some stakeholders consider that temperature and precipitation changes can have a positive influence on the viticulture in mountain context.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Introducing vine varieties producing grapes with high value but long ripening period**, in the past not considered because not able to reach ripeness in high altitudes, but now the positive effects of climate changes that allows to obtain fully ripe grapes with outstanding enological potential.
- **Valorisation of autochthonous varieties (Parraleta, Vidadillo)**, that resist much better to drought, being all the mountain vineyard without irrigation system.
- **Implementation of protective nets in large and concentrated vineyards** mainly against hail damages, but also advantageous with respect of some pests and diseases.
- **Promoting organic viticulture**, whose adoption is easier in mountain context and can provide extra economic and environmental value.

- **Implementation of fencing and use of repellents** to reduce the damages to vines caused by rabbits and deers, that eat sprouts at early spring causing the complete loss of grape production of the attached shoots, or great mortality in new plantings.
- **Advantage small farmers committed to the land** - who looks to the long-term, having next family generations in mind - versus outside investors who don't necessarily leave value in the territory.
- **Encourage young entrepreneurs** to establish winegrowing activities in mountain regions with the donation of soft loans and planting rights in recognition of their efforts to build a local value chain.

20 – Swiss Alps. Switzerland

Context

Study case: Swiss Alps

Value Chain name: Mountain Grain value chain (Grisons Mountain Cereals)

Land-use system name: Cropland extensive

Photo 155. A cereal producer weeding a field in the Grisons Alps

Photo 156. A field of barley in the Grisons Alps

Source: GranAlpin

Figure 157: Land use system in the Swiss Alps MRL

Source: MOVING Project (WP3) according to Asselen and Verburg (2012)

Figure 158: Distributions of agricultural zones in the canton of Grisons (MRL)

Source: Swisstopo, 2021, Edit by ZHAW

Short Description land-use system

The LUS is characterised by steep mountain slopes that are almost exclusively covered with pasture and forest or are bare (rock, mountain flora) above the tree line at 2000 masl. In Switzerland, agricultural land is divided into 7 zones, which are also based on how difficult it is to grow crops in an area due to the given terrain. Cereals are mainly grown in the lowlands, while mountain cereals are still an exception. In our study region, most cereals are grown in "mountain zone 3". The highest of all zones is not agricultural land, but is used exclusively as extensive grazing land for transhumance. Arable farming in the mountains is extensive and takes place in mixed systems with cow husbandry.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

We have chosen to focus on the reference variable "cereal yields" in kg/ha, although other variations of yields were discussed and should be considered as important as well:

- Yields of the whole region/value chain
- Yields in efforts/revenue

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 86: Driver description and components Swiss Alps MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	<p>Decrease in rainfall. The timing of rain (or snow and hail) is much more important for yield than the amount. Too much or too little rainfall during the main growth phase of cereal crops has a major impact. Producers perceive the total amount of rainfall as more or less unchanged, but the intensity and regularity of rain has changed drastically, making it difficult to rely on empirical values for yield planning. Heavy rain or drought are more common, but unpredictable and the main problem.</p> <p>Some cereal varieties react more critically to strong rainfall fluctuations: Rye, wheat, oats, barley, old cereals (early germination).</p>
Temperature	<p>Average temperatures in the main growth phase are most important for yields, while long periods of extreme temperatures have the greatest impact on yields. In their most extreme form, these are drought and frost. Temperature is not yet seen as a major problem for yield, more growing days are welcomed, and heat waves are not yet a problem.</p>
Extreme events	<p>Weather extremes. The extreme weather events relevant to yields mainly concern precipitation: Heavy rain or drought, snow too early or too late, but also frost. Here, too, the timing is crucial; events in winter have no influence on yield. The intensity and irregularity of the weather is the main problem. This driver and the driver precipitation have often been understood together.</p> <p>Some cereal varieties react more strongly to weather extremes: rye, buckwheat, spelt, wheat, tall-growing old varieties.</p>
Wildfire	<p>Not a concern in this region for this VC.</p>
Pollution	<p>Was not selected by any participants in the questionnaire.</p>
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	<p>For us, it made sense to supplement this driver with "weeds". Because pests and diseases are still an insignificantly small problem for this crop at this altitude.</p> <p>However, weeds are a problem throughout the growing season. All our contacts rely on organic weed control (mechanical), and this depends heavily on perfect timing: If the weather is too bad, the reaction time window can be missed. Weed control is a lot of manual labour. Newer varieties seem to have less weed pressure than older varieties because they have better tillering.</p>

Over-exploitation of resources	<p>For this driver, water availability was the main issue. In most areas of the MRL, water availability in the form of rainfall is sufficient to irrigate crops. In a few drier valleys, irrigation infrastructure is in place. Most farmers indicated that irrigation is not a logistical or infrastructural problem, so drought is not a problem for cultivation. Farmers feel that the availability of water has remained the same. However, it became clear that many farmers do not seem to be aware that water is becoming scarcer due to the lack of snow and the formation of glaciers in winter. It was mentioned that farmers in the Grisons mountains do not irrigate with groundwater, which makes it clear that their understanding of the sources they use for water supply is different from the groundwater sources used by farmers in lower areas. Barley was mentioned as especially resistant to lack of water.</p>
Demographic changes	<p>Does not appear to be a concern related to cereal yield in this region.</p>
Soil physical degradation	<p>While the quality of the soil is perceived to be more or less consistent, it was mentioned that mechanical tillage is the biggest problem as it can lead to erosion and a loss of biodiversity and subsequently nutrients.</p>
Land-use and land-cover change	<p>This does not appear to be a specific concern, however, some of it is covered by other drivers such as soil physical degradation.</p>

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 159: Infographic of results Swiss Alps MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: In general, the ranking turned out as expected. We were expecting the precipitation and water related drivers to come out at the top of the list due to what we learned in the interviews and from the climate scenarios. For the “Pests etc.” driver we initially did not focus on weeds, which would have led to a different ranking – weeds are seen as a major problem. We were expecting “pollution” to rank higher, however we believe the issue was that the driver was too broad. If we had talked about “soil nutrients-management” and the (over-)use of manure, it could have come out a bit differently, although perceptions might vary a lot.

About trends: Participants found it difficult to make assumptions about these trends, even though we made it clear that we wanted to know their perception and experience, not measurements. For those who have been farming in the region for more than 20 years, it was easier to assess the past trend. For younger farmers, this question was difficult because it was not possible to clearly define what had happened on the farm in the last 20 years.

Interestingly, one participant (researcher) who knows exactly the topic of our case study mentioned that if we had made the period longer (>30 years), we would have got very different results, as there used to be almost no cereal cultivation. Since then, farmers have become much more innovative and climate mitigation has become an important issue in agricultural projects and on farms in the region.

About sensitivity: In general, our expectations were in line with the results in terms of the factors we assessed as having the greatest influence on yield. However, at this point we would like to clarify that we assessed how farmers perceived and experienced these influencing factors and their development. We mention this because it was surprising that water scarcity was not seen as a pressing problem, as we know it is from calculated climate scenarios. Also, farmers said that in the past they did not share their experiences of what influences high yields and in what ways, as there used to be a lot of competition. Today, farmers are organised in cooperatives and share their knowledge more freely. Farmers are now particularly proud when they can share how they can achieve high yields without additional inputs, e.g., by using only organic practices and fertilisers etc. from their own farm.

List of adaptive mechanisms

We have identified the following measures from interviews and questionnaires. They were all also mentioned by the actors in the workshop. Some are already being implemented at the suggestion of the local authorities, who are also willing to provide financial support in the future.

- **Mechanism 1: Local adaptability - Selection of adapted mountain cereal seeds and local research/testing**

The knowledge and technical resources to improve or intensify research into locally adapted seed (for mountains) and cultivation techniques would be available in Switzerland, and there are several (state) institutions for agricultural research. However, the economic factor can be a problem, as seed development can take a long time and the outcome is uncertain. It is also a challenge to compete for attention with this research for

lowland agriculture (better accessibility, higher yields, etc.). There are other issues like that the production of seeds is strictly regulated and requires permits, so mountain farmers don't do it themselves, and historically, the local seeds have been lost.

- **Mechanism 2: Advanced soil practices - Further Sensibilisation on soil preservation and intercropping, goes together with climate mitigation strategies**

This includes practices, techniques and tools that are already widely available today. This mechanism therefore depends only on the willingness of producers to adapt and on their financial and social capital to acquire the necessary knowledge and resources. This mechanism was most often mentioned as already in practice or under development. These techniques (reduced tillage, soil cover crops, etc) can allow to retain more humidity in the soil and adapt to water shortages for example.

- **Mechanism 3: Strengthening of downstream parts of the value chain to guarantee price and purchases.**

For the people closest to GranAlpin management, this was the most urgent mechanism. There are serious bottlenecks in the VC downstream areas (e.g. grain storage). However, the measures needed to alleviate these problems are quite complicated, both in terms of the actors involved and the required willingness to adapt, as well as the purely financial investment and technical possibilities. Actors emphasized that increasing yields is fine and relatively easy but will bring nothing if the storage and processing capacity downstream is not there.

- **Mechanism 4: Water capacity - New water storage solutions for summer**

This is the issue that producers seemed to be least aware of. However, the researcher and the policy participants mentioned this as the most pressing issue in terms of environmental impacts. In Switzerland, research is being done on this issue, but not yet specifically for mountain cereal production, and there are many unresolved use conflicts as a result. Some projects were mentioned of combining it with hydropower reservoirs, for which the potential in the Alps is huge, but also for that the potential of conflict is there (as well as concurrence with tourism or other use, like use for artificial snow).

21 - Swiss Jura. Switzerland

Context

Study case: Swiss Jura

Value Chain name: Tête de Moine PDO

Land-use system name: Extensive open rangeland

Photo 160 Pastures in the Franches Montagnes region

Source: FRIJ

Photo 161: Pasture located at 1000 m, at the time of the drought on 14 July 2015 (left) and shortly after the return of rains on 26 August 2015

Source: AGROSCOPE Science | No 49 / 2017

Figure 162: The geographical area as defined in the specification of the PDO

Source: FRIJ

Figure 163: The Mountain Regional Landscape Swiss Jura

Source: MOVING Project (WP3) according to *Asselen and Verburg (2012)*

Short Description land-use system

The geographical area comprises the mountain region and the summer alpine pastures (included in the mountain region) of the districts of Franches-Montagnes, Porrentruy, the municipality of Saulcy and the district of Bernese Jura except for the municipalities of Nods, Diesse, Lamboing, Prêles and La Neuveville. This area has been defined by the actors of the value chain and is included in the specifications of the Tête de Moine PDO.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

The reference variable is the annual production of grass and fodder expressed in terms of quantity and species diversity. It is linked to milk production for cheese processing. This is set out in the PDO specification, which sets a minimum limit of 70 % fodder from the geographical area. The remaining 30% may come from elsewhere, except for silage, which is forbidden.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 87: Driver description and components Swiss Jura MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Decrease rain and snow precipitation. The rainfall regime is impacted by climate change (more frequent anticyclones). Snow is also less abundant. The phenomenon is more marked in the plains, the mountains are more resistant. But everywhere the lack of rainfall has a direct impact on grass and forage growth.
Temperature	The average temperature tends to increase. There are more sunny days, especially in summer, which can lead to a slowdown in grass growth (evapotranspiration), in a context of shallow, calcareous soils.
Extreme events	Droughts can lead to significant forage losses. These phenomena seem to be more frequent and prolonged. They also reveal a kind of 'ease' in managing the fodder resource, as many producers rely on being able to buy 30% of the fodder from outside the PDO geographical area. Hail is also an extreme problematic event as it can negatively affect the quality of the forage.
Wildfire	Fires are exceptional and have no impact on production (to date)
Pollution	Pollution is rather endogenous, linked to unbalanced manure balances. According to scientists, the cause of these imbalances is to be found in the supply of external fodder. Nevertheless, these are isolated and punctual phenomena.
Pests, diseases and invasive species	Voiles can cause serious problems, especially in years when their populations are abundant. They burrow into pasture soils, negatively affecting productivity. Some exotic plants are also spreading, although this is more pronounced in the lowlands than in the mountains and should be monitored in the medium term.
Over-exploitation of resources	Over-exploitation of resources is latent, i.e. it appears during prolonged droughts, which cause fodder yields to fall. Some farmers may then run out of fodder. They buy it from outside or acquire plots of land (including outside the PDO geographical area) dedicated to this purpose. These phenomena are rare for the moment and seem to be linked to particular configurations (sloping pastures, very stony, chalky and shallow soils, difficulties in storing hay).

Demographic changes	Demographic changes can be a problem within the farming population, as it is increasingly difficult to find new farmers. Another issue is the increasing number of tourists, especially since the pandemic. This leads to a positive response at fairs and markets, but also to over-frequentation by hikers and walkers, which can cause problems for the breeders.
Soil physical degradation	Breed selection. The soils are naturally fragile, as they are shallow and calcareous. There are some compaction phenomena linked to the interventions of the machines, which must be taken care of, but on the whole, the pastures are managed correctly and are preserved.
Land-use and land-cover change	Landscape changes (Wooden pastures). The main changes concern the wooded pastures, typical of the Franches Montagnes. This change is manifested by a bipolarisation with forests on one side and pastures on the other. This dynamic mainly concerns cultural and identity values linked to the preservation of a traditional landscape, but biodiversity is also impacted. The value chain is not directly impacted by this change.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 164: Infographic of results Swiss Jura MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: According to the participants, the most dominant drivers of change for herb and fodder production are exogenous factors; above all there are droughts, which interact with decreasing precipitation and increasing temperatures. The demographic changes were mainly related to the difficult generational turnover in the agricultural population. The driver of overexploitation and pollution was raised mainly by the scientific experts, and it was evaluated mainly as a future potential threat.

About trends: The effects of climate change on pastures are well documented in the scientific literature and are known by the actors of the value chain. However, stakeholders tend to minimise the effects of human practices, and more particularly those of intensive agricultural practices. Thus, during the collective workshop, while I recalled the opinion of scientists, tending to point the finger at this type of practice, some actors in the value chain, notably economic actors (i.e. interprofessional, chamber of agriculture, ...), rather defended existing agricultural practices.

About sensitivity: The results of the sensitivity survey converge: all participants agree that the increase in average temperatures, the frequency and intensity of extreme events (droughts, but also hail), and the decrease in precipitation, have a negative impact on grass growth. Nevertheless, discussions were lively, as these impacts can vary within the MRL, especially in higher areas where, paradoxically, these factors can also have a positive role, e.g. a longer season and therefore higher forage production.

List of adaptive mechanisms

A collective exercise allowed the prioritisation of the proposed mechanisms. It can be noted that the priority solutions are essentially economic in nature, and do not directly aim to mitigate the effects of climate change or improve the resilience of the territory. The five proposals with the most points were discussed collectively. They are listed below, in order of importance

- **Better use of the milk potential when the seasons are favourable**
Due to climate change, vegetation starts earlier and earlier. Autumn also lasts longer and often offers favourable grazing conditions. It is therefore important to exploit the opportunities at the beginning and end of the season, as they can partially compensate for the more unfavourable periods in the summer.
This collective strategy should be extended to the other stages of the value chain. Demand for Tête de Moine is concentrated at the end of the year (with a peak in December), while milk is abundant between May and June. It is therefore necessary to work collectively to de-seasonalise consumption (sale of pre-packaged rosettes, marketing, and communication, ...), or to improve the storage and maturing of cheeses (temperature-controlled cellars), or, at farm level, by encouraging the installation of barn dryers to better store fodder, which is lacking in winter.
- **Continue to position Tête de Moine AOP in the premium quality segment in order to ensure an income and quality of life for producers.**

The quality of life of producers is essential and cannot be neglected. To date, the PDO has proven that it can provide a satisfactory income thanks to a better remuneration of the milk and a higher added value for the territory (especially compared to industrial milk). The requirements of the PDO contribute to the high quality of this cheese, which is appreciated on the Swiss and international markets. That's why it's important to keep Tête de Moine in this profitable niche.

- **Improve the link between the value chain and the specific resources (such as wooded pastures).**

The wooded pastures are a cultural landscape that contributes to the collective identity of the Franches Montagnes district and even of the Jura region. The pandemic has shown the extent to which the population is attached to this territorial resource, which also enables other value chains to exist, for example the breeding of Franches Montagnes horses, the only endemic breed in Switzerland. Furthermore, it has been proven that trees create "fresh islands effects", so their presence can provide a buffer against extreme droughts.

- **Maintain an attractive price, to attract industrial milk producers to the Tête de Moine value chain.**

Idem as (2). It should be noted that an important project (Créalait), which has obtained funding from the Swiss Confederation, has just been launched to convert industrial milk producers to "quality milk" (Tete de Moine PDO).

- **Strengthen the division of labour between the enterprises in the area (management of mother cows, heifers, cheese dairies, etc.).**
- Greater **division** of labour may result in increased specialisation, but it also highlights the degree of interdependence of the value chain with other value chains such as meat production for example. These interactions and complementarities between roles and functions should be optimized.

22 – Beydaglari. Turkey

Context

Study case: Beydaglari MRL

Value Chain name: Greenhouse Tomato

Land-use system name: Intensive annual crop / irrigated

Photo 165: Greenhouse areas in Elmalı (LAU)

Source: Hakan ADANACIOĞLU

Photo 166: Drought effect in the regional lake (Avlan lake) of Elmalı (LAU) before (2011) on the left, and present time (2021) on the right.

Source: Hakan ADANACIOĞLU

Figure 167: Spatial distribution of the land cover classes in the Reference Region of Beydaglari in 2018

Source: CORINE Land Cover, level 2

Short Description land-use system

Elmalı (LAU) is a small plateau in the Beydağları range of the western Taurus Mountains. Beydağları is close to the Mediterranean and has an inland climate of cold winters and hot summers. Near to Lake Avlan there is an area of cedar forest, rare in Turkey. The 37% of the land is planted. Greenhouse cultivation is widely practiced in the region. Fruit growing is common in open agriculture. The total area under greenhouse tomato cultivation in Elmalı (LAU) is about 835 hectares.

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain

Reference variable and value chain is the same.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 88: Driver description and components Beydaglari MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	<p>Drought. It was emphasized that the decrease in precipitation creates a problem in accessing the water required for irrigation. The problem of access to irrigation water causes a decrease in tomato yield.</p> <p>Drought increased due to decreased precipitation. Therefore, problems arose in accessing sufficient irrigation water. The problem of access to water adversely affected fruit set, especially during flowering.</p>
Temperature	<p>Temperature increases negatively affect fruit set during the flowering period. This leads to a decrease in productivity. In addition, product quality decreases due to the increase in temperature.</p>
Extreme events	<p>Unexpected climatic events in the region are usually caused by floods and storms. Floods and storms cause damage to tomato greenhouses. This leads to loss of production.</p> <p>Due to climate change, the damages caused by the flood in Elmalı started to emerge. Flood damages tomato roots in greenhouses. This reduces tomato production. Another reason for the flood in the region is the wastes such as garbage and medicine boxes that are thrown unconsciously on the stream beds.</p>
Wildfire	<p>Since there is no forest in the production area, forest fires are not seen as a risk for tomato production greenhouses in the region.</p>
Pollution	<p>It has been stated that since Elmalı is in a mountainous region, greenhouse tomato producers in this region do not encounter problems such as soil and water pollution. In addition, due to the fact that Elmalı is located far from the city, the obvious effects of soil, water and air pollution are not encountered.</p>
Pests, diseases, and invasive species	<p>The main reason for the decrease in quality and yield is due to the red spider mite. It has been stated that the red spider mite damages the root of the plant. It is suggested that the red spider mite appears due to the increase in temperature.</p> <p>Some pests and diseases cause a decrease in quality and losses in production. <i>Orobanche</i> spp. and fungal diseases are the main ones.</p>

	Orobanche spp. and fungal diseases. It is claimed that fungal diseases are caused by the unconscious excessive use of water by the producers.
Over-exploitation of resources	<p>The widespread unconscious use of groundwater in the region restricts producers' access to water. Difficulties in accessing irrigation water cause decreased yield and quality. Groundwater level is decreasing due to unconscious use of groundwater. This increases the cost of drilled boreholes. As a matter of fact, drilling deeper to access water in boreholes requires an extra expense. This increases the greenhouse tomato production cost.</p> <p>The groundwater level has decreased in Elmalı. Neighbouring producers cause the reserves of each other's existing water wells to decrease. At the same time, since excessive well drilling causes water to be extracted from deeper depths, both the water decreases and the cost increases.</p>
Demographic changes	Traditional commitment to production is high in farmer families dealing with greenhouse cultivation. In addition, since greenhouse production activities are generally profitable, alternative production activities are not considered. These positive factors cause production not to be adversely affected by demographic changes.
Soil physical degradation	<p>The negativities caused by excessive tillage and unconscious chemical fertilisation negatively affect the yield and product quality in greenhouse tomato production.</p> <p>Producers who do not have soil analysis use unconscious fertilizers. This leads to a decrease in yield and a decrease in quality.</p>
Land-use and land-cover change	Due to drought and price variability, greenhouse tomato producers can make changes in their land use plans. As a result, producers either reduce the tomato production area or tend to alternative products. This causes a decrease in tomato production.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 168: Infographic of results Beydaglari MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: According to the ranking of driver's the most important driver is over-exploitation in Elmalı. Over-exploitation is defined as over-extraction of groundwater. The groundwater level has decreased in Elmalı. Excessive use of groundwater and unconscious water use lead to a decrease in product yield and an increase in costs. The other essential drivers are precipitation, pest and invasive species, temperature respectively. Wildfire is the least related driver in Elmalı. Forest fires do not pose a risk in terms of tomato production. The tomato production areas are not within the forest area.

About trends: Stakeholders have thought that over-exploitation, pests and invasive species, pollution, temperature and land-use and land-cover change have increased sharply in the last 20 years. Soil physical degradation, extreme events and demographic changes have increased slightly in the last 20 years. And the most important point is precipitation. Stakeholders have thought that precipitation has declined sharply in the last 20 years. Most of participants said that this trend will continue in the following 20 years.

About sensitivity: According to participants who attended workshop, over-exploitation, precipitation, pests and invasive species, soil physical degradation, temperature, pollution, and extreme events are totally affect tomato production negatively. Land-use and land-cover change, and demographic changes affect tomato production severely. Drought increased due to the declining precipitation. Therefore, problems arose in accessing sufficient irrigation water. The widespread unconscious use of groundwater in the region restricts producers' access to water. The major problem is using irrigation water as illegal. Wells are mostly drilled illegally. This caused the groundwater level to drop.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Agricultural insurance:**
Agriculture insurance has been emphasized that farmers should take out agricultural insurance to cover damages in greenhouses and losses in production due to unexpected climatic events such as floods and storms. Farmers do not tend to have agricultural insurance although it has covered financial loses of farmers.
- **Planning of greenhouse investments:**
The high profitability in greenhouse tomato production causes an increase in investments in greenhouse cultivation. This causes production to be uncontrollable. Physical infrastructure control and planning should be done before greenhouse installation. This is situation of expanding area of greenhouses versus overexploited water resources. This is under responsibility of ministry of agriculture and needs to be done new regulations.
- **Encourage youth for agriculture:**
Farming can be made attractive to young people by using smart agricultural technologies. Social life should be improved especially for young people (education, health etc.). This

would be happened by public support especially directed to young generation. Social statue of farmers which is accepted as lowest rank with image problem.

- **Development of drought resistant varieties / using virus-free varieties:**
Temperature increases during the flowering period can have a negative effect on tomato yield. In order to reduce this negative effect, it has been suggested to develop heat-tolerant varieties. In the area, there is an important research institute on vegetable breeding which is an advantage for this mechanism.
- **Smart agriculture systems:**
It is important that use smart agriculture systems in irrigation and using smart farming systems for the control of temperature in greenhouses. Farmers are willing to use smart agriculture system for controlling temperature, humidity, soil components etc. But this needs new investments and to have public support especially for small scale farms.
- **Precautions for irrigation:**
The irrigation water to be used for production must be calculated. More regulations for excess water consumption should made by extra payment.
- **Good agricultural practices:**
Organic fertilisers should be used to reduce soil degradation. To reduce the effect of some pests such as red spider mite, it is necessary to apply pesticides in a timely manner. Otherwise, reductions in product yield and quality occur. However, it is considered important to use biological control methods, especially in the fight against diseases and pests. Some farmers are using organic fertilisation. Good agricultural practices (GAP) certification doesn't provide them any price advantage in the market.

23 - Highlands and Islands. UK-Scotland

Context

Study case: Water quantity in connection with Speyside Malt Whisky production

Value chain name: Speyside Malt Whisky

Land-use system name: Extensive Rangeland

Photo 169: Upper catchment of River Spey, near Newtonmore

Source: Rachel Creaney

Photo 170: River Spey restoration and management work on Glenlivet Estate

Source: Martyn Roberts

Figure 171: Map of the land cover/use for the Speyside MRL

Source: Hutton Institute

Short description of the land-use system

The Speyside and West Moray MRL with an area of just over 3,413 km² is an example of upland and mountain land use systems in maritime N.W. Europe. While the maximum elevation is low for a mountain region (1,309 m) the higher elevations within the MRL have sub-alpine vegetation communities and in places skeletal soils and long periods of snow cover. This contrasts over short distances with valley floors (e.g., Aviemore at ~240 m) where it is possible to practice arable agriculture. The MRL is also transitional in terms of climate from very wet western mountains (mean annual rainfall – 2,934mm) to the much drier eastern coastal plains into which the valley opens (731mm). The area has substantial areas of deep peatlands (1,018 km² or 30% of the MRL area with >50cm of peat in first 100cm of soil), 73% of which need some degree of hydrological and/or vegetative restoration. For agricultural capability, the MRL has 12% of the area with very limited agricultural capability (the lowest LCA class, 7), with a further 49% capable only of supporting rough grazing (LCA6.1-6.3). Land capable of supporting improved grassland makes up 24% (LCA classes 5.1-5.3) with a further 13% capable of supporting mixed agriculture (LCA 3.2-4.2). The higher ground is typically covered with a mix of semi-natural vegetation types - heather (*Calluna vulgaris*), white bent (*Nardus stricta*), flying bent (*Molinia caerulea*) and bog mosses (*Sphagnum* spp), while lower slopes will see more palatable grasses (*Festuca* spp and *Agrostis* spp). These

pastures have some use as pasture (for sheep) but higher elevations are mainly used mainly for hunting (e.g., red grouse – *L. lagopus*, red deer - *Cervus elaphus*, and mountain hares – *Lepus timidus*), the first including the extensive use of fire for vegetation management (there are 8,935 grid cells (200m) with >50% of their area burned or 35,740 ha). The River Spey and its tributaries (1,760 km within the MRL) have world renowned sport fishing for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*). There is also extensive recreational use, skiing, mountaineering, hillwalking, and camping. Forestry has increased from 14% of the MRL in 1988 to about 20% in 2020 (Scotland has 18%). The woodlands are typically concentrated in the valleys and lower hillsides, but recent plantings have often been specifically riparian. The objectives for woodland creation are both timber production (softwood plantations) and habitat creation (native woodlands), including assisting natural regeneration. Improved pastures (permanent or temporary grass) make up most the remaining land with 6% and 1% and are used for raising cattle and sheep though with fewer animals taken direct to slaughter with most being sold for finishing in the lowlands. The MRL has a total population of 37,941 in 2020 with Badenoch and Strathspey having 13,948 and West Moray 23,966. Aviemore is the only settlement large enough to be defined as a *remote small town* (population 3-10,000, with a 30–60-minute drive to a settlement of >10,000) with 5% of area *accessible rural*, 36% *remote rural* and 59% *very remote rural* (<30, 30-60 or >60-minute drive times to a >10,000 settlement).

Name of the reference variable and linkage to the value chain (Speyside Malt Whisky)

The **reference variable** is **Water Quantity**. Initially, both water quality and quantity were discussed, via interviews, but it became clear that quantity was of greater concern especially for looking forward. Speyside malt whisky is a global value chain with strong cultural and geographical links to natural resources originating in the mountains. Whisky draws attention to water, often an unvalued resource in mountain regions. Land cover, use and management can positively, or negatively, impact on water resources. Climate change may affect both the water quality and quantity, so it was important to engage with all those with a stake in whisky, water or managing upstream land uses about these links.

Drivers' description and components based on the analysis of the interviews

Table 89: Driver description and components Speyside MRL

Driver	Description and Components
Precipitation	Decrease Rainfall Changes to the overall annual average rainfall. This impacts on the surface and groundwater quantity available for use within the whisky (process water) and a larger volume of water used only for cooling. There is also the need to also consider evapotranspiration loss to the atmosphere for a net input to surface and ground water funds.
Temperature	Snowmelt. Changes in the snowfall regime, which impacts on the intensity and frequency of snow melt. Snow is a good means of longer-term water storage and slow release which is necessary for year-round abstraction for process and cooling uses. Conversely large amounts of non-melting snow may also reduce water quantity in winter. Rate of melt may also be associated with flooding events (dealt with separately).
Temperature	Air Temperature. Average annual air temperature. Water temperature is the direct driver for the reference variable but is infrequently measured, not mapped and there are no future projections, so air temperature is used here as a proxy.
Temperature	Water Temperature. Average annual surface water temperature. Higher water temperatures in sources used for abstraction for cooling purposes means more volume must be abstracted. Higher water temperature may also influence the fermentation processes.
Extreme Events	Changes in the frequency and/or extent of flooding and drought. Climatic drought influences the availability of surface water (and potentially spring water) necessary for year-round abstraction for process and cooling in whisky distilling. The main current risk is to cooling water volumes but future availability of process water in also a concern. Floods can damage the physical infrastructure of the distilleries; and increase the sediment in the water intake.
Wildfires	This driver was not seen as relevant to the reference variable, except potentially indirectly through other drivers. A more specific driver, muirburn, was though used.
Wildfires	Muirburn. Extent and intensity of muirburn influences vegetation cover, water retention and potentially drainage (see the Peat Soil Condition driver). This can lead to more sediment or dissolved organic carbon entering the surface water, and potentially the distillery water intake. This driver was discussed in relation to water quality which by the completion of the analysis was seen as less vulnerable due to the sources used and the degree of control possible in the distilling processes.
Land Use and land cover Change	Land Use Change. A change in land cover, use or management, in particular the change from rough grazing to forestry. Depending on the location, type and management of the forestry, this can have impacts on the soil-water balance (positive or negative) with implications for surface and ground water flows. This can have impacts on the availability of water for abstraction. Land use/management influences on water quality and quantity can be both diffuse and indirect (e.g., via the mix of land use over the catchment as a whole) or localised and direct (e.g., via riparian woodlands creating microclimates to reduce water temperatures).

Soil physical degradation	Peat Soil Condition. Changes in the extent of vegetation cover loss that leaves soil vulnerable to erosion, being washed into surface waters during intense rain fall events, and potentially entering the distillery water intake. The ability of peat soils to function as water stores, buffering higher inputs and minimising low flows at other times.
Over-Exploitation	Over Exploitation of Water Resources. Extraction of surface water or groundwater beyond the sustainable limit, meaning that the quantity of water available for distilleries (and other users) to abstract is limited to retain environmental flows on which river ecosystems depend.
Pests, Diseases and Invasive Species	This driver was not seen as relevant to the reference variable, except potentially indirectly through other drivers.
Pollution	Water Pollution. This driver was not seen as relevant to the reference variable, except potentially indirectly through other drivers.
Demographic Changes	This driver was not seen as relevant to the reference variable, except potentially indirectly through other drivers.

Results of participation, ranking, trends, sensitivity, and adaptive mechanisms.

Figure 172: Infographic of results Speyside MRL

Comments on the results about ranking, trends, and sensitivity

About Ranking: The ranking of the drivers conforms with expectations and driver prioritising from the interviews and reflects discussions in the vulnerability workshop. Overall, the high average values confirm that the drivers discussed were relevant. The graph shown in the infographic above is useful to show the degree of concern about the change in the reference variable. The highest ranking comes from the most direct driver (over exploitation), where the impacts of a range of drivers are brought together to influence the operation of the distilleries. These factors/drivers include both the size of the fund or flow of water but also who else may want/need to use it. The other high ranked factors/drivers relate to the biophysical aspects of the size of water flows (rainfall, floods, and droughts) and the key quality (temperature). It is worth noting that for all drivers there are fairly widely varying degrees of concern, perhaps reflecting differing stakeholder perspectives or priorities. Lower ranked drivers tend to be associated with either factors/drivers that underpin the capability of the land to retain water (snow melt or peat soil condition) or influence its quality (land use change). The lowest range drivers are either proxies (air temperature) or have effects that can be readily mitigated within the industry (muirburn).

About trends: After the completion of the stakeholder interviews, the pre-workshop questionnaire gathered perceptions of past trends and future projections of the effects of the biophysical drivers on water quality and quantity that related to Speyside whisky production. With only five respondents to the questionnaire, any conclusions need to be carefully caveated, but in many cases, there are either research base studies or expert knowledge that can confirm the trend, provide future projections, and reduce or quadrantify uncertainty. The trend graph indicates in most cases moderate increases (trend mean = 0.5 - slightly increased), for all responses (4) for drivers such as air temperature and thus also for water temperature and extreme events such as floods and droughts. For some drivers, it reflects disagreement on the direction of trends, e.g. peat soil conditions and snowmelt, with minima of -0.5 (slightly decreased), and maxima of 0.5 and 1 (slightly or sharply increased). For the over exploitation of water resources (a key driver in the Driver Ranking above), there was also disagreement in direction of trend, and a perception for one of the stakeholders that overexploitation had sharply increased (max = 1). The views here may need to be further investigated, particularly in the light of the deliberations within the vulnerability workshop. In the case of rainfall there was variability in the responses, as the lived experience within the LRM would give, depending on the location, different perceptions of the trend (SW is increasing and NE decreasing).

About sensitivity: The sensitivity results conform with the expectations generated by ranking and trend analyses. The table shows an overall pattern of negative effects (indicated by the values M- and L-) – with only two cases in which potentially positive outcomes of the drivers are noted. The stakeholders were most certain of the impacts for over exploitation, extreme events and water temperatures but with some variability in the degree of impact (L- y M-). Where there was most uncertainty was in some cases with more complex drivers such as land use change, where the range of options, and their relative magnitudes, made it harder to come to conclusions. For others such as snow melt, there were different emphases on interpreting the driver, generating the widest divergence in anticipated sensitivity. Overall, the greatest

sensitivity was assigned to those drivers with the clearest mechanistic links to the reference variable.

List of adaptive mechanisms

- **Collaborative Water management:** Avoiding over-use of water through collaboration and resource sharing:
 - Collaborative water sharing solutions based on dialogue
 - Sharing monitoring data between catchments
 - User 'digital dashboards' to regulate timing and amount of water between abstractors
- **Distillery Water Management:** Changes to water management by distilleries including coordination with other distilleries:
 - Onsite reduction of water footprint e.g., re-circulation
 - Increase on-site reservoirs
 - Alternative abstraction points and sources to reduce stress
 - Collaboration to collectively manage flows and levels
- **Sustainable Land Management / Land Use Change:** Changes to the wider pattern to land use and management that can impact aquatic systems:
 - Good agricultural practice (riparian fencing, buffer strips, spring cropping, minimal tillage, correct fertiliser inputs)
 - Good practice muirburn techniques
 - Land use change – rewilding beyond riparian planting
- **Rewetting Peatlands:** Interventions to reduce or slow the flow of water out of peatland areas
 - Grip (drain) and gully blocking to reduce artificial drainage
 - Increases water storage capacity and recharge rates
 - Reduces erosion of degraded/ dried out exposed peat (hags)
- **Peatland Habitat Restoration:** Restoring vegetation cover (e.g., sphagnum moss) to increase storage capacity of the habitat and influence the microclimate
- **Instream Restoration:** Changes within the rivers and stream:
 - Large woody structures instream e.g., to slow flow in floods and increase pools providing deeper cooler water and storage for flows downstream
- **Riparian Management:** Changes to the banks and flood plains:
 - Flood plain restoration to allow flood storage
 - Riparian woodland planting to reduce evapotranspiration; slow overland surface water flow; trap sediment; and shade water
 - Additional biodiversity benefits but trees must be slow growing & moisture tolerant 'right tree in right place'
- **Managing Infrastructure:** Changes to infrastructures beyond those of the whisky industry, predominantly grey not green infrastructure.
 - Change abstraction regimes for hydro-schemes to reduce stress
 - Combine hard flood risk engineering with natural flood management.

- Reduce new housing on private water supplies
- New Sustainable Drainage System (SuDS) schemes to manage pollutants from trunk roads.

10. Appendix II (T3.4): Auxiliary maps per MRL

1 – Austrian Alps MRL. Austria

The spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures at Austrian Alps MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of slope and exposition.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to calculate slope and exposition, within Austrian Alps MRL, using ArcMap software.

In the case of the exposition map, as in the spatial vulnerability matrix only North, West-East and South classes were contemplated, the original exposition values were grouped as indicated below:

- North, Northeast and Northwest were grouped in the class North,
- West and East were grouped in the class West-East,
- South, Southeast and Southwest were grouped in the class South.

Flat values of exposition were considered residual.

The maps of slope and exposition, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in

Figure 173 and

Figure 174, respectively.

Figure 173: Slope Map of Austrian Alps MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 174: Exposition Map of Austrian Alps MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Permanent pastures at Austrian Alps MRL were mapped considering the classes “Grasslands and meadows – Low”, “Grasslands and meadows – Medium” and “Grasslands and meadows – High” from Crop Management Systems Map suggested by Rega *et al.* (2020) (Figure 175), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for permanent pastures at Austrian Alps MRL is presented in

Figure 176.

Figure 175: Crop Management Systems according to Rega *et al.* (2020) at Austrian Alps MRL

Figure 176: Permanent Pastures at Austrian Alps MRL

3 – Sumava – Cesky Les MRL. Czechia

The spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures at Sumava – Cesky Les MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of elevation and distance to urban centre.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation within Sumava – Cesky Les MRL, using ArcMap software.

According to the regional MOVING partner, the only relevant urban centre with approximately 100,000 inhabitants is České Budějovice. A buffer of 50 km was created around České Budějovice, using ArcMap software, in order to map distance to urban centre within the MRL.

The maps of elevation and distance to urban centre, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 177 and

Figure 178, respectively.

Figure 177: Elevation Map of Sumava – Cesky Les MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 178: Distance to Urban Centre Map of Sumava – Cesky Les MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Permanent pastures at Sumava – Cesky Les MRL were mapped considering the classes “231. Pastures” and “321 – Natural grassland” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for permanent pastures at Sumava – Cesky Les MRL is presented in

Figure 179.

Figure 179: Permanent Pastures at Sumava – Cesky Les MRL

6 – Crete MRL. Greece

The spatial vulnerability matrix for agroforestry at Crete MRL considers the spatial explicit factors of elevation.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation within Crete MRL, using ArcMap software.

The maps of elevation, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, is presented in Figure 180.

Figure 180: Elevation Map of Crete MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

07 – Transdanubian Mountains MRL. Hungary

The spatial vulnerability matrix for the mosaic of land uses at Transdanubian Mountains MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of tree cover density and slope.

The Tree cover density 2018 spatial dataset from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, available at the respective website (<https://land.copernicus.eu/>) and the EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), were used to map Tree cover density and slope within Transdanubian Mountains MRL, respectively, using ArcMap software.

The maps of tree cover density and slope, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 181 and

Figure 182, respectively.

Figure 181: Tree Cover Density 2018 Map of Transdanubian Mountains MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 182: Slope Map of Transdanubian Mountains MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

8 – Central Apennines MRL. Italy

The spatial vulnerability matrix for the agro-silvo-pastoral system at Central Apennines MRL considers the spatial explicit factors of elevation.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation, within Central Apennines MRL, using ArcMap software. The map of elevation, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, is presented in Figure 183.

Figure 183 : Elevation Map of Central Apennines MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

The agro-silvo-pastoral system at Central Apennines MRL was mapped considering the classes “Low-intensity livestock farming” and “Low-intensity grassland area” from Land Systems map suggested by Levers *et al.* (2018) (Figure 184), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for the agro-silvo-pastoral system at Central Apennines MRL is presented in Figure 185.

Figure 184 : Land Systems according to Levers *et al.* (2018) at Central Apennines MRL

Figure 185 : Agro-silvo-pastoral System at Central Apennines MRL

09 – Eastern Alps MRL. Italy

The spatial vulnerability matrix for vineyards at Eastern Alps MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of elevation and slope.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used map elevation and to calculated slope, within Eastern Alps MRL, using ArcMap software. The maps of elevation and slope, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 186 and

Figure 187, respectively.

Figure 186 : Elevation Map of Eastern Alps MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 187 : Slope Map of Eastern Alps MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Vineyards at Eastern Alps MRL were mapped considering the class “221. Vineyards” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>). The map for vineyards at Eastern Alps MRL is presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 188 : Vineyards at Eastern Alps MRL

10 – Northern Apennines MRL. Italy

The spatial vulnerability matrix for high intensity plant forest (agroforestry) at Northern Apennines MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of elevation combined with exposition and distance from main roads or village.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation and to calculated exposition, within Northern Apennines MRL, using ArcMap software.

In the case of the exposition map, as in the spatial vulnerability matrix only North and South classes were contemplated, the original exposition values were grouped as indicated below:

- North, Northeast and Northwest were grouped in the class North,
- South, Southeast and Southwest were grouped in the class South,
- West, East and Flat were grouped in the class others (and excluded from the subsequent analysis).

To construct the map of the distances from main roads or village, a buffer of 100 m was created around main roads and villages, using ArcMap software. The spatial dataset of main roads used was an Italian road shapefile, and villages consist of all polygons classified as “112. Discontinuous Urban Fabric” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), within or in the close periphery of the MRL.

The maps of the combination between elevation and exposition and distance from main roads and village, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in

Figure 189 and

Figure 190, respectively.

Figure 189 : Map combining elevation and exposition at Northern Apennines MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 190 Distance from main roads or village Map of Northern Apennines MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

High intensity plant forest (agroforestry) at Northern Apennines MRL was mapped considering the classes “311. Broad-leaved forest”, “131. Mineral extraction sites” and “321. Natural grassland” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for High intensity plant forest (agroforestry) at Northern Apennines MRL is presented in Figure 191.

Figure 191 : High intensity plant forest (agroforestry) at Northern Apennines MRL

11 – Maleshevski Mountains MRL. North Macedonia

The spatial vulnerability matrix for mosaic landscape at Maleshevski Mountains MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of elevation and precipitation.

As the vulnerability levels presented in the referred matrix do not vary with elevation, only precipitation needed to be considered when building the vulnerability map.

The spatial datasets of spring, summer, autumn and winter precipitation bioclimatic variables from ClimateEU (more specifically, CMIP5-based climate data (1km resolution) for RCP 4.5 and 2020s (average for years 2011-2040)) – available at <https://sites.ualberta.ca/~ahamann/data/climateeu.html> – were summed through map algebra, using ArcMap software, to obtain a spatial dataset of the mean annual precipitation. This dataset was then used to map precipitation at Maleshevski Mountains MRL.

The map of precipitation, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, is presented in Figure 192.

Figure 192 : Mean annual Precipitation Map of Maleshevski Mountains MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

12 – Cordilheira Central MRL. Portugal

The spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures at Cordilheira Central MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of distance to forests and shrublands and elevation.

Forests and shrublands at Cordilheira Central MRL and its surroundings were mapped considering the classes “311. Broad-leaved forest”, “312. Coniferous forest”, 313. Mixed forest”, “322. Moors and heathland” and “324. Transitional woodland/shrub” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), after consulting the regional MOVING team. Buffers of 250 m and 750 m were created around this former map, using ArcMap software, in order to map distance to forests and shrublands within the MRL.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation, within Cordilheira Central MRL, using ArcMap software.

The maps of distance to forests and shrublands and elevation, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 193 and Figure 194, respectively.

Figure 193 : Distance to forests and shrublands Map of Cordilheira Central MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 194 : Elevation Map of Cordilheira Central MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Permanent pastures at Cordilheira Central MRL were mapped considering the classes “231. Pastures”, “321. Natural grassland”, “242. Complex cultivation patterns” and “243. Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for permanent pasture at Cordilheira Central MRL is presented in

Figure 195.

Figure 195 : Permanent Pasture at Cordilheira Central MRL

16 – Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL. Czechia

The spatial vulnerability matrix for Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of land cover type and distance from the infrastructure.

The map with the groups of Land cover types was created using CORINE Land Cover 2018 spatial dataset (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>).

Infrastructure at Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL and its surroundings was mapped considering the classes of “1. Artificial surfaces” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>). Buffers of 1.5 km and 3 km were created around this former map, using ArcMap software, in order to map distance from the infrastructure within the MRL.

The maps of land cover types groups and distance from the infrastructures, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 196 and Figure 197, respectively.

Figure 196 : Land Cover Classes Groups Map of Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

(CORINE land cover 2018 – level 3 classes in order of appearance in the map: 231 – Pastures, 242 – Complex cultivation patterns, 321 – Natural grasslands, 312 – Coniferous forest, 313 – Mixed forest, 311 – Broad leaved-forest, 324 – Transitional woodland-shrub, 112 – Discontinuous urban fabric, 211 – Non-irrigated arable land, 243 – Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation, 121 – Industrial and commercial units).

Figure 197 : Distance from the Infrastructure Map of Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

17 – Betic Systems MRL. Spain

The spatial vulnerability matrix for organic olive groves at Betic Systems MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of slope and elevation.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation and to calculate slope, within Betic Systems MRL, using ArcMap software. The maps of slope and exposition, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 198 and

Figure 199, respectively.

Figure 198 : Slope Map of Betic Systems MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 199 : Elevation Map of Betic Systems MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Olive groves at Betic Systems MRL were mapped considering the class “223. Olive groves” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>). The map for olive groves at Betic Systems MRL is presented in

Figure 200.

Figure 200 : Olive Groves at Betic Systems MRL

18 – Sierra Morena MRL. Spain

The spatial vulnerability matrix for dehesa at Sierra Morena MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of precipitation and tree cover density.

The spatial dataset of annual mean precipitation available at REDIAM was used to map precipitation at Sierra Morena MRL, using ArcMap software.

The Tree cover density 2018 spatial dataset from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, available at the respective website (<https://land.copernicus.eu/>) was used to map Tree cover density within Sierra Morena MRL, also resorting to ArcMap software.

The maps of precipitation and tree cover density, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 201 and

Figure 202, respectively.

Figure 201 : Precipitation Map of Sierra Morena MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 202 : Tree Cover Density Map of Sierra Morena MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Dehesa was mapped considering the classes “244. Agro-forestry areas”, “311. Broad-leaved forest”, “Mixed forest” and “324. Transitional woodland/shrub” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for dehesa at Sierra Morena MRL is presented in

Figure 203.

Figure 203 : Dehesa at the Sierra Morena MRL

19 - Spanish Pyrenees. Spain

The spatial vulnerability matrix for vineyards at Spanish MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of elevation and slope.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used map elevation and to calculated slope, within Spanish Pyrenees MRL, using ArcMap software. The maps of elevation and slope, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 204 and

Figure 205, respectively.

Figure 204 : Elevation Map of Spanish Pyrenees MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 205 : Slope Map of Spanish Pyrenees MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

21 – Swiss Jura MRL. Switzerland

The spatial vulnerability matrix for permanent pastures at Swiss Jura MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of elevation and tree cover density.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to map elevation, within Swiss Jura MRL, using ArcMap software.

The Tree cover density 2018 spatial dataset from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, available at the respective website (<https://land.copernicus.eu/>) was used to map Tree cover density within Swiss Jura MRL, also resorting to ArcMap software.

The maps of elevation and tree cover density, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 206 and

Figure 207, respectively.

Figure 206 : Elevation Map of Swiss Jura MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 207 : Tree cover density Map of Swiss Jura MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Permanent pastures at Swiss Jura MRL were mapped considering the classes “231. Pastures” and “321. Natural Grassland” from CORINE Land Cover 2018 (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, <https://land.copernicus.eu/>), after consulting the regional MOVING team. The map for permanent pastures at Swiss Jura MRL is presented in

Figure 208.

Figure 208 : Permanent Pasture at Swiss Jura MRL

22 – Beydaglari MRL. Turkey

The spatial vulnerability matrix for intensive/irrigated annual crop of tomato at Beydaglari MRL considers the 2 spatial explicit factors of slope and precipitation.

The EU-DEM (LAEA) spatial dataset available at *GISCO: Geographical Information and Maps*, from Eurostat website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>), was used to calculate slope, within Beydaglari MRL, using ArcMap software.

The spatial datasets of spring, summer, autumn and winter precipitation bioclimatic variables from ClimateEU (more specifically, CMIP5-based climate data (1km resolution) for RCP 4.5 and 2020s (average for years 2011-2040)) – available at <https://sites.ualberta.ca/~ahamann/data/climateeu.html> – were summed through map algebra, using ArcMap software, to obtain a spatial dataset of the mean annual precipitation. This dataset was then used to map precipitation at Beydaglari MRL.

The maps of slope and precipitation, taking into account the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in Figure 209 and

Figure 210, respectively.

Figure 209 : Slope Map of Beydaglari MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Figure 210 : Precipitation Map of Beydaglari MRL considering the classes presented in the Spatial Vulnerability Matrix

Intensive/irrigated annual crop of tomato at Beydaglari MRL was mapped considering the spatial dataset, provided by the respective regional MOVING partner, with the polygons of the tomato greenhouses within Beydaglari MRL. Resorting to ArcMap software, an aggregation of polygons (which consists of combining polygons within a specified distance of each other into new polygons) was performed, using a specified aggregation distance of 500 m, to define what was considered the area of the referred LUS.

The map with the area that was considered of intensive/irrigated annual crop of tomato at Beydaglari MRL is presented in

Figure 211.

Figure 211 : Intensive/Irrigated Annual Crop of Tomato at Beydaglari MRL

23 – Speyside MRL. United Kingdom – Scotland

The spatial vulnerability matrix for Scotch Whisky Distilling in Speyside considers two spatially explicit factors of Water Supply and Water Demand. The maps of these two factors, using the classes defined in the spatial vulnerability matrix, are presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** and

Figure 213, respectively.

Water supply is derived per sub-catchment from long-term average annual rainfall for 1991-2018. The rainfall data is taken from the mapping on a 1km grid of historic daily rainfall values derived from meteorological stations by the UK Meteorological Office. The sub-catchments associated with each distillery are derived from digital elevation models and stream networks using ARCGIS Pro. This process also defines a series of “nesting” relationships with headwater distilleries at the top of catchments being the first users of water but further down the catchment, while the volume of water available may be larger, there may be several distilleries making use of the resource. The specific level of water abstraction was not available at the time of analysis so as a proxy the volume of alcohol production was used (taken from the Scotch Whisky Year Book). Within the MRL there are both concentrations of distilling with clusters of multiple distilleries (see the inset mapping for the NE of the MRL) and single distilleries with substantial production reliant on smaller sub-catchments. In other areas by contrast single distilleries may be able to make exclusive use of water from large catchments (e.g., those in S and SW).

Figure 212 : Water Supply per Sub-catchment Map at Speyside MRL

Figure 213 : Water Demand per Sub-catchment Map at Speyside MRL

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